

Summary of the state of play of the demo cases using the CEIS

Deliverable 2.6

CIRC-PACK - Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain

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ABBREVIATIONS

1,4-BDO	1,4-butanediol
CIRC-PACK	Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain
CAPEX	CAPital EXpenses
CE	Circular Economy
CED	Cumulative Energy Demand
CEIS	Circular Economy Indicator System (CEIS)
DC	Demo Case
EoL	End-Of-Life
IRR	Investment Return Rate
LCA:	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC:	Life Cycle Costing
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LFI	Linear Flow Index
NPV:	Net Present Value
OPEX:	OPerational EXpenses
PE	Polyethylene
PET	Polyethylene Terephthalate
PP	Polypropylene
ROI:	Return Of Investment
S-LCA:	Social Life Cycle Assessment
UN	United Nations
VC	Value Chain
VCA	Value Chain Analysis
WP	Work Package

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22/ PLASTIPOLIS	PLASTIPOLIS

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

In this deliverable is has been analysed the current state of the different value chains (baseline) in terms of environmental impact, economic costs, social impacts and circularity.

For packaged products such as powder detergent, liquid soap, chicken and coffee, main contribution to environmental impact is due to the product itself. Contribution of packaging to environmental impact is very low for chicken or coffee. The highest contribution is observed for powder detergent, where it can reach up to 40% in some indicators.

Recycling leads to savings in all the environmental indicators for all these products, showing the best performance in global warming, fine particulate formation, eutrophication and fossil resource scarcity. The group of stakeholders involved in packaged products value chains is very heterogeneous from a social perspective. Among all, same and/or better performance and convenience is expected and communication activities towards intermediente and end-users engagement is frequent.

In terms of value chain circularity most products have a very high degree of linearity due to almost inexistent level of recycled material usage as raw materials, with the exception of packaging recycled cardboard. Laminated cardboard packs are not recycled now due to the difficulty in separating plastic layers from cardboard. PET trays recovery rate are moderate, but none of these packaging items are reused or may have a life extension, limiting the material circularity results.

For bags, main contribution to environmental impact is ascribed to raw materials and electricity used during manufacturing process. It has been observed that the use of recycled material reduces the impact in two different ways: a) plastic waste is used to manufacture the recycled material reducing the impacts associated to waste treatment or landfilling, b) less virgin polymers are used for the manufacturing of bags. In this vein, a hypothetical scenario with 100% of recycled content is proposed as ideal scope. According to EC reports the recovery rate for bags in Europe is very low. It has been seen in the assessment that non-collected bags, has significant contribution to ecotoxicity indicators where landfilled.

When compared the ultralightweight plastic bags (< 15 µm) with the thick plastic bags (> 50 µm) considering the reusability of the thick ones, it has been observed that impact of reusable bags is 6 times lower.

From a social point of view, changes on bag manufacturing are not expected to involve or increase risks, although they may hinder domestic waste management.

Bags' circularity results have one positive side, which is the use of recycled material in the composition (almost 50%), but on the contrary, the collection rate from end user is really low. Thick bags may be reused several times and extend the utility by carrying heavier loads than thin bags, increasing the circularity of the material by two.

For automotive components, it has been compared different EoL and the impact of recycling is lower than incineration and landfill in most of the indicators. Some of them (such as ozone depletion, ionizing radiation and eutrophication) show higher impact for recycling because of electricity used for recycling process. However, after applying a monetarisation procedure to obtain the overall environmental cost, it could be concluded that recycling

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scenario is favourable from the environmental point of view. The opportunity to recycle materials from automotive components may demand new skilled positions and hence, tailored training will be developed.

The circularity index is mainly affected by the high level of virgin raw materials consumed, due to the high internal rejection rate and the null usage of recycled compounds in the plastic composition. Although materials are collected in factory and sent to recycle, with an economic benefit, this does not translate into circularity benefits. This is the target of the CIRC-Pack innovation in this value chain.

Environmental assessment for packaging of **Absorbent Hygiene Products (AHP)** revealed that recycling lead to savings in most of the indicators, especially in toxicity related indicators, fossil resource scarcity and global warming. Regarding the recycling process for AHP wastes, it was observed that almost all the impact is associated with energy consumption (either by electricity, fuel or steam). Only in marine eutrophication indicators there is an important contribution of the wastewater generated in the process. According to social impacts assessment, packaging suppliers would be the main involved stakeholders regarding worker's health and safety. Due to changes on materials, it is expected a better communication of EOL options through specific labelling on products.

Despite the AHP recycling pilot plant in place, the collection rate of these products is very low and the materials recovered are modest. In addition, low recycling material inputs are now being used, affecting negatively the value chain circularity ratios. The development of new packaging with recycled materials will greatly improve the circularity values.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D 2.3 (State of play of the demo case using the CEIS) is prepared under the CIRC-PACK project as main output of Task 2.3 on “Baseline definition and preliminary assessment of the CIRC-PACK value chains”.

After overview of value chains assessment (VCA) scenarios (Task 2.1) and development of the methodology for CIRC-PACK value chains (VC) evaluation (Task 2.2), Task 2.3 focuses on evaluation of current state of CIRC-PACK value chains. This report is structured in different sections where different CIRC-PACK value chains are addressed. Every section begins with a brief description of the current situation (baseline) for the corresponding value chain (already presented in deliverable 2.2). Afterwards, different sub-sections address the environmental, economic and social assessment respectively. An additional subsection is included to address the overall scoring of indicators and interpretation of the assessment results.

The environmental, economic and social assessment of this task are focused on the baseline of different value chains. This will serve as reference to evaluate, in task 2.4, the improvements achieved in the value chains through CIRC-PACK innovations.

The analysis has been carried out with separated data for different steps and inputs in order to allocate contribution to the different steps and inputs/outputs to the environmental impact, economic cost and social impact. In this manner, the assessment carried out in Task 2.3 can be also useful to find potential improvements in the different value chains to reduce environmental impact and optimize cost and social aspects. This information has been described as an output of the interpretation step, where results from different assessment have been analysed.

Furthermore, in order to ensure high level of decision support, CEIS comprised of indicators under environmental, economic, social and life cycle assessment themes were analysed using a combination of set of criteria as well as Analytical Network Process (ANP).

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1 INTRODUCTION

CIRC-PACK project is focused on development of different innovations that would improve the sustainability of plastic packaging value chain by:

- 1) Decoupling plastic packaging value chain from fossil feedstock by using biodegradable polymers
- 2) Improvement of recyclability in multimaterial packaging products
- 3) Promote an effective reuse in the plastic economy

All these approaches contribute to reconvert the traditional linear plastic packaging value chain in a circular value chain. Figure 1 represents, in a general way, the value chain of plastic products and which steps host the different CIRC-PACK innovations (DC-A, DC-B, DC-C).

Figure 1. Scheme of innovations within CIRC-PACK project

As commented in D2.2, successful and sustainable innovations depend on having a clear understanding of the impacts and benefits of a product or service throughout the whole life cycle, from the sourcing of raw materials to ultimate disposal at end of life. In this framework, applying a life cycle thinking perspective is very useful to obtain a quantitative measure of sustainability for the process.

Life cycle methodologies can be used for quantification of the process impact (regarding environmental impact, economics, social impact and circularity), which can be analysed separately for different value chain steps to analyse their contribution to the overall impact.

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This tool is also very useful to compare two different scenarios in order to support decision-making process to companies or public entities.

In this framework, a comparative life cycle study is required to check and evaluate the improvements achieved in the overall impact of the value chain through the different innovations implemented during CIRC-PACK project. For such a comparative analysis, both situations (the current situation and the future situation) must be identified and characterized.

1.1 Objective

The objective of this task is to evaluate the impact of the current situation (baseline) of CIRC-PACK value-chains. The analysis will serve as reference to evaluate improvements achieved through CIRC-PACK innovations.

Moreover, the collection of data and impact assessment have been made in such a manner to allow allocation of impacts to different steps and inputs/outputs. In this manner, relevant information for the reduction of environmental impact and optimization of cost and social impact has been obtained as an output of the analysis performed during interpretation step. This step also includes checking the reliability of results by an iterative process involving the main stakeholders of each value chain.

The information derived from impact assessment is contained in a set of indicators related with different type of impacts (environmental, economic, social and circularity). These indicators (except for the circularity indicators) have been ranked according to a number of criteria including surveys collected from value chain actors, RACER criteria employed by European Commission to assess quality of indicators, literature screening of previous projects and studies in order to prioritize those with highest importance, facilitating more reliable conclusions about potential value chain improvements.

1.2 Scope

As a technical report to evaluate the current situation (baseline) of targeted value chains, this report includes the assessment of the different value chains regarding environmental impact, economics and social impact. The analysis is also complemented with the circularity assessment based on the circularity indicators proposed in D2.2.

Nine different value chains are addressed within the deliverable:

- 1) Production of biobased polymers
- 2) Multimaterial packaging for powder detergent
- 3) Plastic packaging for liquid detergent
- 4) Ultralightweight plastic bags (< 15 microns)
- 5) Thick plastic bags (> 50 microns)
- 6) Plastic trays and multilayer film for packaging of food products

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- 7) Plastic automotive components
- 8) Coffee capsules
- 9) Absorbent hygiene products.

Assessment includes all the steps in the value chain, from raw materials to end-of-life of targeted products.

1.3 Outline the methodology

During Task 2.1. it was already reviewed the state of the art regarding the Life Cycle Assessment of product value chains. Additionally, a review of most relevant indicators was also performed, paying attention to those focused on circularity where the methodology to be used at European level is still under discussion due to the differences among existing reports.

During Task 2.2, they were identified the different value chains and the methodology for the Life Cycle Assessment, including key items such as system boundaries, inputs/outputs to be considered, functional unit or characterization meth among others. Task 2.3 is based on this methodology developed in task 2.2

In task 2.3, **environmental assessment** started sending questionnaires to the partners in order they could fill them up with corresponding data.

Data received from partners was analyzed to check potential inconsistencies by carrying out a mass balance of inputs and outputs. In case of mismatches or missing information, an iterative process was carried out in collaboration with partners for refinement of collected data.

Once completed the questionnaire, the Life Cycle Inventory datasheet was prepared for every process (considering a process one single step of different value chains). This datasheet consists in a list with all the inputs/outputs of the corresponding process.

Once quantified all the inputs/outputs of the different processes, these processes were created into SimaPro software version Analyst 8.5.0.0 and grouped by value chain. Impact assessment of the overall value chains were performed in order to evaluate their environmental impact.

Economic assessment was carried out using excel files comprising all the economic inputs/outputs (allocated to the reference product) of the different processes (considering a process as a single step of different value chains). These processes were grouped by value chain for calculation of revenues and cost in the overall value chain.

Unlike, environmental and economic assessment, activities developed within task 2.3 regarding **Social assessment**, entail data collection of current situation in value chains, in order to obtain reference values for further comparison and scoring in task 2.4. For this purpose, questionnaires tailored for each partner were compiled, gathering information for indicators calculation and background understanding.

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Regarding the involvement of **consumers**, as key actors of the Circular Economy Model, and with the aim to boost social acceptance of products, main results from surveys carried out in 6 countries of the European Union, are shown in section 11.

Finally, a number of metrics to assess the product and process circularity is calculated. Economic related metrics assess the value chain net added value and in relation to the product mass, the virgin raw material mass and the resource economic value (materials + energy). The Ellen McArthur model indicators (EMF) describe the linearity of the product and the circularity of the materials in use. The CEIS metrics describe the amount of recycling materials, either from the end of life or from other value chains, that is fed back into the production process. Finally, the product utility with respect to the average standard of similar products, and the amount of total and relative wastes generated are also calculated. The units and calculation procedure is in the following table.

Table 1. Final selection of circularity indicators.

Set of circularity indicators.			
Type	Indicator	units	calculation
	Virgin raw material	kg/year	V: mass of input
	Product mass (w primary packaging)	kg/year	M: mass of output
Economic	Net added Value	€/year	NAV = sales - OPEX - CAPEX
Ec / EMF	Resource productivity	€/gr	RP = Net added value / V
Ec / EMF	Resource longevity	time / cycles	RL = product lifetime x recycling cycles x reusing cycles.
Ec / EMF	Value based Resource efficiency	%	VRE = Net value added / (E + M)
EMF	Linear flow index (LFI)	%	LFI = (V + W) / (2M + (Wf - Wc)/2)
EMF	Material Circularity index (MCI)	%	MCI p = max(0; (1 - LFI F(X)))
CEIS	End-of-life recycling input rates	%	FrM/V for plastic packaging
CEIS	Circular Material Use rate (CMU)	%	Fr+Fu but in interaction with other value chains.
CIRC-PACK	Degradation rate	%	Biodegradable / V; Biodegradable /M
CIRC-PACK	Compostable rate	%	Compostable / V; Compostable /M
EMF	Wastes	Kg/year	W'=Wo+W'o+(Wf+Wc)/2+(W'f+W'c)/2
EMF	Utility factor		F(X) = 0,9 / X
EMF	Utility		X = (L / L av) x (U / U av)

Since neither CEIS nor EMF's methodologies include a broader circularity level, which is the biological material restoration, two specific additional CIRC-Pack indicators are added to account for materials that may be degradable, or even compostable at the innovation level. These materials are demonstrated in CIRC-PACK's demo case A and may not have any influence, or even negative influence, on product life extension, recyclability and reuse rates. However, the benefit is clear in terms of lower fossil-based material consumption and

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the reduction or even elimination of long-term wastes, due to the fast degradability of the materials, returning the biological resources to the ground.

Finally, the results about ranking of indicators and interpretation were carried out. The basis of the methodology lies in evaluation of different indicators under certain criteria. The criteria included perceptions of value chain actors of the indicators selected in D2.2 and RACER criteria set. Each indicator was assessed using the relevant criteria and their performance was compared with each other through Analytical Network Process, which is a multi-criteria decision analysis method. The outputs of this assessment were the ranking of indicators based on their importance or significance and also weighing scores to be potentially used for obtaining single score indicators under environmental, economic and social themes.

2 PRODUCTION OF BIOBASED POLYMERS VALUE CHAIN

2.1 Value chain description

As described in deliverable D2.2, biobased polymers from NOVAMONT will be used as starting material for different innovations in DC-A (food trays, plastic bags, soap plastic bottles, AHP packaging film and coffee capsules). Nevertheless, some innovations will be implemented in the manufacturing of these biobased polymers and it will be considered as a separated value chain for easier combination of results (combination of different innovations).

Biobased plastics from NOVAMONT are based on polyesters obtained from renewable sources which are currently obtained by condensation of 1,4-butanediol (1,4-BDO) and azelaic acid. Azelaic acid is extracted from vegetable oils (e.g. cardoon oil), while 1,4-BDO is obtained through fermentation of sugars obtained from agricultural resources. During polymer synthesis (by reaction of 1,4-BDO and azelaic acid), some tetrahydrofuran (THF) is produced as by-product and not recovered.

These polyesters are blended with other polymers and additives in order to tune their properties for the intended application and processing techniques. Different biobased plastic grades will be developed within CIRC-PACK project:

- Polymer 1 for injection of coffee capsules
- Polymer 2 for blown-film extrusion of film and bags
- Polymer 3 for thermoforming of food trays
- Polymer 4 for blow injection molding of bottles

All these steps are (production of 1,4-BDO and azelaic acid, preparation of polyesters and formulation of biobased plastic materials) are carried out by NOVAMONT group (MATER,

MBP and NOVAMONT). The overall flow-chart for manufacturing of biobased polymers is represented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Flow chart of current state (baseline) for value chain of biobased polymers manufacturing process

2.2 Environmental assessment

In a first analysis, the contribution of different inputs to the environmental impact of biobased polymers production has been analysed. As it can be seen in Figure 3, the main contribution is ascribed to the raw materials which are typically above 95%. Highest contribution for the manufacturing process is observed for freshwater and marine ecotoxicity indicators.

Figure 3. Distribution of overall environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for different inputs/outputs in production of biobased polymers

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These results are the reference to evaluate the environmental impact of using cellulose from AHP as raw material. In addition, it is worth mentioning that the CIRC-PACK innovation in this value chain will lead to important environmental impact reduction due to the recovery of THF from a biogenic source, in contrast to its current origin which is mainly based on fossil resources.

2.3 Economic assessment

Regarding economic data, the contribution of operational costs, including raw materials represents around 83% of the overall cost for production of the biobased polymers, as it can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Contribution of different cost categories in manufacturing of biobased polymers

2.4 Social assessment

Within the production of biobased polymers, new job positions may be expected regarding AHP waste recovery (1 process engineer) and with regard to biobased polymer manufacturing as 60 per kton of biobased plastic production. It has to be noted that, despite of no gender preference for positions, workforce among the value chain is mainly masculine. As part of suppliers for other manufacturing processes or products, events or information communication, in some cases, may be intermediate-consumer oriented. It has to be highlighted that, although biobased polymer manufacture currently demands 100% virgin materials, NOVAMONT's environmental commitment requires renewable raw materials. Table 2 compiles indicators corresponding the baseline, although comparative scoring system developed prevents of further calculations among this stage.

Table 2. Bio-based polymers social reference point

Partner	MATER	MBP	NOVAMONT	FATER
Task/ Role	Production of 1,4-BDO	Polymerization of polyesters	Bio-based polymer manufacture	AHP waste recovery

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N° employees in the company	102	81	273	1,600
1. Equal opportunities/discrimination (gender issues)				
Male/female rates within workforce in the chain	Male: 85% Female: 15%	Male: 80% Female: 20%	Male: 75% Female: 25%	Male: 75% Female: 25%
Preference for positions	Indifferent	Indifferent	Indifferent	Indifferent
2. Training and education				
Is workflow process modified by innovations?	No	No	No	Yes
Training for workers in the chain	1,413 hours/yr	3,110 hours/yr	3,355 hours/yr	>20 hours/yr
Training programme	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
3. Workers' health and safety				
Do innovations involve or increase risks?	No	No	No	No
Average lost days per worker/year in the chain for health and safety reason	0 lost days/yr	102.8 lost days/yr	33.9 days/yr	0 lost days/yr
Safety trainee	Unknown	Unknown	2,500 hours/yr	> 8 hours/yr
Protective equipment availability in the chain	Yes. Sensors for fire, oxygen values, PPE	Yes. Sensors for fire, oxygen values, PPE	Yes. Sensors for fire, oxygen values, PPE	Yes
Severe accidents in the chain	0 accidents/yr	0 accidents/yr	1.29 accidents/yr ¹	0 accidents/yr
4. Consumers' health and safety				
Information/Signs available regarding features	Yes. (e.g. purity and others)	No. (confidential)	No	N/A
Storage conditions	Yes	-	Yes. Store Mater-Bi® in a cool and dry warehouse sealed in its original packaging, away from heat and light. Novamont recommends to convert Mater-Bi® within 6 (six) months from the delivery date.	N/A
5. End-of-life responsibility				
Clear information on EOL options	No. Intermediate product	N/A	Yes. EOL disposal info is reported for the end product	N/A
Impact on domestic waste management	N/A	N/A	Easier	N/A
6. Consumers' well being				
Quality expectation/ Performance and usability	N/A	N/A	Better	N/A

¹ Number of accidents/worked hours x 200,000

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User friendliness/ Convenience and acceptance	N/A	N/A	Better	N/A
7. Community access to material resources				
Certified environmental management system	No	Yes. ISO 14001	Yes. ISCC Plus, eLabel	Yes
Current materials origin in the chain	100% Virgin	100% Virgin	100% Virgin	100% virgin
8. Safe and healthy living conditions				
Corporate social responsibility policy	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Management effort to minimize use of hazardous substances	No hazardous substances use	No hazardous substances use	No hazardous substances use	No hazardous substances use
9. Local employment				
Workforce hired locally	Unknown	Unknown	10% Umbria, 90% Piemonte	20%
Local suppliers	Unknown	Unknown	5.2% (Terni)	100%
10. Community engagement				
Annual events/Workshops organized/participating locally	4-5 events	4-5 events	4-5 events ²	>20 events/yr
Impact in social media	528,352 views on Twitter, 1798 likes on Facebook	528,352 views on Twitter, 1798 likes on Facebook	528,352 views on Twitter, 1,798 likes on Facebook	Depends on campaign
11. Technology development				
Previous involvement in technology transfer program or projects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Investment in technology development	Unknown	Unknown	7% turnover	4% of turnover for R&D
12. Suppliers relationships				
Seal of quality/Management system required for suppliers	Yes. ISO 9001, ISO 14001	Yes. ISO 9001, ISO 14001	Yes. (ISCC-renewable raw materials)	N/A
Suppliers from countries with high estimated proportion of population in modern slavery	Unknown	Unknown	10% (Non-EU)	0%

2.5 Circularity assessment

The purpose of this innovation is to generate similar performing plastic packaging using biopolymers, and hence, reducing the fossil-based polymer consumption. Additional advantages may come from the possible biodegradability of the materials, which would contribute to reduce and even avoid the long-term wastes, or the compostability of the materials, leading to a higher value added from the waste reuse.

² (Ecomondo, K 2016, Novara Jazz and Fa' La Cosa Giusta)

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The design and production of these new biobased polymers will be tailored to each of the demonstrating value chains and it produces no direct impacts unless assessed within the frame of every value chain. Thus, the impact will be evaluated for the 8 identified value chains in the innovation assessment task T2.4. In particular, biodegradable materials are expected to neither have higher utility or reuse rates, nor longer life. This is still to be tested. The impact on material recovery and recyclability, metrics used for the circularity assessment, are expected to decline, due to null recyclability of these materials. The circularity main improvements will most likely show up in the resource biological restoration and the reduction of long-term wastes.

Most of the analysed value chains have zero or low values for biodegradability and compostability as of now (baseline). Biobased materials will contribute to improve these ratios, as well as environmental life cycle metrics.

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3 MULTIMATERIAL PACKAGING FOR POWDER DETERGENT VALUE CHAIN

3.1 Value chain description

Powder detergent products are usually commercialized in cardboard boxes. These cardboard boxes are combined with additional materials to provide barrier properties. Most typical scenario in Europe comprise a multimaterial consisting in cardboard with a PE laminate in the inner side of the box. This PE layer difficults the recycling process of paper and therefore, this type of packaging should be collected in mixed waste for landfill or incineration.

SAPONIA D. D. is already using another product with a starch coating in the inner side to provide these barrier properties. Due to degradability of starch, this coating does not interfere with paper recycling process and this packaging format can be therefore recycled. Nevertheless, some impurities and reject fractions are obtained during the process due to contaminants.

Cardboard for manufacturing of powder detergent boxes is made from **100% recycled cardboard** which, in terms of processes required, is quite similar to the production from virgin fibres. Virgin wood and/or cardboard wastes are pulped, screened and cleaned to obtain cellulose fibres (for packaging of SAPONIA D. D. only recycled fibres are used). These fibres are used afterwards to prepare a sheet that is dried and pressed. Finally, an additional drying process is performed and final cardboard product is produced by combination of several layers if needed.

In the case of starch-coated cardboard, starch coating is applied during pressing step (just after first drying process) of cardboard manufacturing process. In the case of PE laminates, the PE film is applied after the manufacturing of the cardboard product.

Once converted in boxes, they are filling with powder detergent and packaged by using different tertiary packaging products such as additional boxes (without coating or laminate), wrap films and pallets. These pallets are distributed for commercialization.

Regarding the end-of-life, **PE laminate cannot be recycled** with paper/cardboard because plastic impurities hinder and difficult the recycling process. Therefore, landfill or incineration are their EoL depending on the European country. On the other hand, **starch-coated cardboard can be incorporated into the paper/cardboard recycling** system.

The flow chart of this value chain is represented in Figure 5 for PE laminate and Figure 6 for starch-coated cardboard.

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Figure 5. Flow chart of current state (baseline 1) for value chain of packaged powder detergent products with with PE laminate boxes

Figure 6. Flow chart of current state (baseline 2) for value chain of packaged powder detergent products with starch-coated cardboard boxes

3.2 Environmental assessment

For preparation of Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), data for the following processes has been collected separately in order to allow environmental assessment separately:

- Manufacturing of cardboard-PE laminate
- Manufacturing of starch-coated cardboard
- Packaging of powder detergent with corresponding packaging format

The environmental assessment has been performed using ReCiPe2 016 v1.1 and Cumulative Energy Demand (CED) characterization methods. As a functional unit, 1 box of product of 280 g has been selected since they are the most typical formats.

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In a first analysis, it has been analysed the contribution of packaging to the overall impact of the packaged powder detergent. The EoL of different packaging materials have been also considered. For primary packaging, since it cannot be recycled because of PE content, incineration has been considered as EoL. For secondary packaging, based on cardboard, recycling has been considered as EoL with a sorting efficiency of 90% (data provided by BUMAGA BV). Regarding films used in palletizing, a recycling rate of 7% has been considered according to literature data [1].

In Figure 7 and Table 3, it can be seen the distribution of relative impacts using both Recipe and CED methods for different inputs/output associated with powder detergent packaged using box based on PE-cardboard laminate. As can be observed, main contribution is attributed to powder detergent, although box used as primary packaging (cardboard-PE laminated box) has also a significant contribution in some specific indicators such as ionizing radiation, freshwater eutrophication, fossil resource scarcity and toxicity related indicators. For other indicators, relative impact of primary packaging is below 5-20%. It should be mentioned that EoL of secondary packaging has a small negative impact because of recyclability of the film which acts as secondary packaging but that is not the case for primary packaging which is incinerated for PE-cardboard laminate.

Figure 7. Distribution of overall environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for different inputs/outputs of packaged powder detergent with PE-cardboard laminate box (per unit)

Regarding the CED evaluation, the relative impact of PE-cardboard box used as primary packaging has a 21% of relative impact. Major contribution is again attributed to powder detergent with 75% of the impact.

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Table 3. Cumulative Energy Demand for different inputs/outputs of packaged powder detergent with PE-cardboard laminate box

Cumulative Energy Demand of powder detergent packaged with PE-cardboard laminated box (per unit)			
Powder detergent	20,312	Primary packaging scrap	0,000
Box primary packaging	5,607	Fuel	0,014
Box secondary packaging	0,385	Electricity	0,198
Cardboard sheet pallet	0,005	EoL cardboard	-0,699
Plastic film palletizing	0,023	EoL plastic film	-0,019
Pallet	0,000	EoL primary packaging	0,010

Several publications report that main environmental impact of laundry products is associated to use phase, which is out of the scope of the assessment carried out in CIRC-PACK. In all of these reports, packaging has lower environmental impact than raw materials, which is aligned with achieved results [4, 5, 6].

In a second analysis, a comparison has been carried out between boxes based on PE-cardboard laminated and starch-coated cardboard. One of main advantages of starch-coated cardboard is that it can be incorporated in the current recycling scheme of cardboard and paper. On the contrary, PE-cardboard laminate difficults the recycling process and cannot be recycled. Therefore, it goes to landfill or incineration, increasing the overall environmental impact of the value chain.

The analysis compares both type of box (using PE-cardboard laminate or starch-coated cardboard) with and without the EoL. In this manner, it can be compared not only the manufacturing process but also the influence of the different EoL.

Results are represented in Figure 8. In all the indicators, the environmental impact is lower for the PE-cardboard laminated box (1st bar in each category) compared with starch-coated cardboard (3rd bar) when EoL is not considered. This is attributed to the impact of starch and liner which is higher than PE film used in the laminate. Nevertheless, when the EoL is included in the evaluation (2nd and 4th bar in each indicator), the overall impact of starch-coated cardboard is lower in most of the indicators. Highest differences are observed in mineral resource scarcity, land use and terrestrial ecotoxicity. This is aligned with previously reported results where the use of recycled fibres has allocated significant lower impact than the use of virgin fibres [7].

Figure 8. Environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for one box used as primary packaging of powder detergent based on: a) PE-cardboard laminate, b) PE-cardboard laminate considering the EoL, c) starch-coated cardboard, d) starch-coated cardboard considering the EoL

Similar observations are obtained using CED characterization method (Table 4). Required energy of cardboard-PE laminate is slightly lower when EoL is excluded from the analysis, but the situation is the opposite when considering the EoL in the assessment. It has been already described in literature that energy required in the manufacturing of paperboard when using virgin fibres is higher than the amount required with when using recycled fibres, which is in accordance with the achieved results [8].

Table 4. Cumulative Energy Demand for one box used as primary packaging of powder detergent based on PE-cardboard laminates and starch-coated (with and without considering the EoL)

Cumulative Energy Demand for different primary packaging formats of powder detergent (per unit)			
PE-cardboard laminate		Starch-coated cardboard	
PE laminate box (w/o EoL)	2,778	Starch-coated cardboard box (w/o EoL)	2,835
PE laminate box (with EoL)	2,790	Starch-coated cardboard box (with EoL)	2,119

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3.3 Economic assessment

Economic data about packaging of powder detergent has been also collected for the different processes in order to perform a LCC analysis. They are differentiated according to different categories such as raw materials, energy use, waste, maintenance (Operational Expenses – OPEX) and amortization of equipment (Capital Expenses - CAPEX).

As mentioned in deliverable D2.2, describing the methodology, labour cost has not been included because the innovations would not affect to them and there are high differences in labour costs among different countries. In this manner, results achieved when comparing impact of the innovations would have higher replicability across Europe. One year has been considered as temporary basis in order to avoid seasonal deviations.

It can be seen in Figure 9 that major cost is ascribed to raw materials for production of powder detergent. Packaging has a contribution around 23% of overall cost.

Figure 9. Contribution of different cost categories in manufacturing of packaged powder detergent

Regarding the manufacturing process of the different type of cardboard boxes, raw materials are the main contribution to the overall cost as it can be seen in Figure 10 (for PE-cardboard laminate) and Figure 11 (for starch-coated cardboard). In both cases, the main contribution is ascribed to cardboard with around 50% of overall cost. PE laminate represent 19% of the overall manufacturing cost while starch represent around 15% of the overall cost.

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Figure 10. Contribution of different cost categories in manufacturing of PE-cardboard laminate

Figure 11. Contribution of different cost categories in manufacturing of starch-coated cardboard

Finally, it is worth to mention that other indicators such as NPV, IRR or ROI have not been calculated for the baseline because they only have sense when comparing baseline with potential innovations. Regarding the net added value, this indicator will be assessed as a part of the circularity framework.

3.4 Social assessment

BUMAGA BV is the main manufacturer related to cardboard-based packaging, being responsible for cardboard and packaging manufacturing and following disposal and

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recycling. In fact, innovations do not modify SAPONIA D.D.'s manufacturing process and no new positions development are expected within this partner. Current positions in BUMAGA BV and SAPONIA D.D. related to the value chain require skilled and highly skilled employees. SAPONIA expects packaging having the same design, though consumers *may not see the difference except for material*. Innovations do not modify tasks in the production lines, as BUMAGA BV recalls, only the "recipe" is modified. However, easier domestic waste management is expected. Both stakeholders consider dissemination activities within local community productive, having active involvement on local events and workshops targeting intermediate and end consumers. The following table summarizes the reference point for further social evaluation within Task 2.4.

Table 5. Cardboard-based multi-material packaging for powder detergent social reference point

Partner	BUMAGA BV	BUMAGA BV	SAPONIA D.D.	BUMAGA BV	ECOEMBES
Task/ Role	Cardboard manufacture	Packaging manufacture	Detergent packaging	Disposal and recycling	Disposal and recycling
N° employees in the company	-	-	850	-	143
1. Equal opportunities/discrimination (gender issues)					
Male/female rates within workforce in the chain	Male: 90% Female: 10%	Male: 75% Female: 25%	Male: 50% Female: 50%	Male: 95% Female: 5%	Male: 50% Female: 50%
Preference for positions	-	-	Indifferent	-	Indifferent
2. Training and education					
Is workflow process modified by innovations?	No ³	No	No	No	No
Training for workers in the chain	20 hours/yr	20 hours/yr	10 hours/yr	20 hours/yr	30 hours/yr
Training programme	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
3. Workers' health and safety					
Do innovations involve or increase risks?	No	No	No	No	No
Average lost days per worker/yr in the chain for health and safety reason	2 days/yr	4 days/yr	0 days/yr	Unknown	1 days/yr
Safety trainee	24 hours/yr	24 hours/yr	20 hours/yr 60hours/yr ⁴	Unknown	Unknown

³ There is continuous training of the staff, we don't expect a completely new technology that requires very extensive training

⁴ 20 hours/yr- at employment on fire protection, general work safety and protective equipment. 60 hours/yr- at the beginning of work on specific machine on hazards and how to work safely, annual check-up by safety officer

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Protective equipment availability in the chain	Yes	Yes	Yes. Protective clothes, shoes, gloves, eye protection	Yes	Yes.
Severe accidents in the chain	0 accidents/yr	1 accidents/yr	0 accidents/yr	Unknown	0 accidents/yr
4. Consumers' health and safety					
Information/Signs available regarding features	No. Not mandatory & confidential	No. Not mandatory & confidential	Yes	N/A	N/A
Storage conditions	Low humidity	Low humidity	Low humidity	None	N/A
5. End-of-life responsibility					
Clear information on EOL options	Yes. Sometimes	Yes. Sometimes	Yes. Specific labelling	N/A	N/A
Impact on domestic waste management	Easier	Easier	Easier	N/A	Same
6. Consumers' well being					
Quality expectation/ Performance and usability	Same	Same	Same	N/A	N/A
User friendliness/ Convenience and acceptance	Better	Better	Same	N/A	N/A
7. Community access to material resources					
Certified environmental management system	Yes	Yes	Yes, ISO 14001	Yes	Yes
Current materials origin in the chain	5 % Recycled own process 95 % Recycled supplier	5 % Recycled own process 95 % Recycled supplier	100 % Recycled supplier	N/A	N/A
8. Safe and healthy living conditions					
Corporate social responsibility policy	Yes	Yes	Yes. Support UN Global Compact goals	Yes	Yes
Management effort to minimize use of hazardous substances	Yes ⁵	Yes	No hazardous substances use	Yes	N/A
9. Local employment					
Workforce hired locally	90%	70%	100%	90%	100%
Local suppliers	50%	50%	100%	N/A	100%
10. Community engagement					

⁵ There are hazardous substances being used but they are being managed in their use and disposal. They are clean at the paper mill wastewater treatment.

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Annual events/Workshops organized/participating locally	10 events/yr	10 events/yr	5 environmental events/yr 10 visits to/from schools/yr 5 sporting events/yr	10 events/yr	30 recycling initiative, programs/yr in (schools and citizen organization)
Impact in social media	On average, 250 likes on fb, 10,000 followers on LinkedIn	On average, 250 likes on fb, 10,000 followers on LinkedIn	100,000 people reached/yr	On average, 250 likes on fb, 10,000 followers on LinkedIn	10,000 people reached/yr
11. Technology development					
Previous involvement in technology transfer program or projects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Investment in technology development	Unknown	Unknown	1,200,000 €/yr	Unknown	25,000 €/yr
12. Suppliers relationships					
Seal of quality/ Management system required for suppliers	Yes	Yes	No, but have to satisfy quality requirements and prove that they will have consistent quality	N/A	Yes
Suppliers from countries with high estimated proportion of population in modern slavery	0%	0%	0%	N/A	0%

3.5 Circularity assessment

This value chain tackles the hardly recyclable multi-material packaging and it is demonstrated by the powder detergent packs produced by SAPONIA D. D. This value chain has a high packaging impact in terms of overall mass share and cost (23%). The aim is to increase the recyclability of the current laminated plastic cardboard, manufactured with recycled cardboard and an additional PE film layer applied to it. The material composition is 4.3% of PE film and 95.7% recycled cardboard. Due to the difficulty of separating these two materials, the full package unit is considered unrecyclable. The innovation will consist on the development of a starch coated cardboard pack, where the cardboard can be totally recycled after removing off the starch layer.

The demo product is a 300 g pack containing 260 g of powder detergent in a 34 g primary pack. Individual packs are boxed into bigger cardboard boxes, and then palletised on

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returnable pallets wrapped up with plastic film. This latest packaging materials are considered to reach the retailer, who unpacks and sends them to recycling through their own channels. All cardboards come from recycled material. In this value chain, the user does not send any material to recycle.

The value chain mass flow inventory is as follows. The user does not send any material to recycle.

Table 6. Mass inventory for circularity assessment. Laminated cardboard

material	Product g/unit	Packaging g/unit	% respect to M
Virgin material	276.0	16.0	94%
Product material	293.7	33.7	100%
User mat to recycle	0.0	0.0	0%
Mfg mat to recycle	64.3	64.3	22%
Recycled mat for mfg	82.0	82.0	28%
Wastes from end user	34.0	34.0	12%
Wastes from mfg	0.0	0.0	0%
Wastes from rec/sorting	0.0	0.0	0%
Biodegradable wastes	0.0	0.0	0%
Compostable wastes	0.0	0.0	0%

With these inputs, the circularity metrics of the detergent in laminated cardboard is in the next table.

Table 7. Circularity assessment for powder detergent in laminated cardboard

Type	Indicator	units	relative
Mass	Virgin raw material	%	94
Mass	Product mass (w primary packaging)	%	100
Ec / EMF	Resource longevity	time / cycles	1
Ec / EMF	Value based Resource efficiency	%	749
EMF	Linear flow index	%	52.8
EMF	Material circularity index	%	52
CEIS	End-of-life recycling input rates	%	30
CEIS	Circular material use rate	%	28%
CIRC-PACK	Degradation rate	%	0
CIRC-PACK	Compostable rate	%	0
Ec / EMF	Wastes	%	12
Ec / EMF	Utility factor		0.90
Ec / EMF	Utility		1

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Results show a high resource efficiency and productivity due to a good net added value with regard to the energy and material value. There is quite a high material circularity index (52%) due to the high recyclability of the cardboard, except for the primary material, and the full use of recyclable cardboard at all levels of the packaging. Secondary packaging is fully sent to recycle, decreasing the amount of final wastes to just 12%.

If using starch coated cardboard (4.5%), and assuming consumers follow the right instructions and send it all to recycle, the inventory tables would look like the following table, for the same amount of production. Additional costs for recycling are not accounted for.

Table 8. Mass inventory for circularity assessment. Starch coated cardboard

material	Product g/unit	Packaging g/unit
Virgin material	276.3	16.3
Product material	293.7	33.7
User mat to recycle	29.2	29.2
Mfg mat to recycle	64.3	64.3
Recycled mat for mfg	81.7	81.7
Wastes from end user	3.4	3.4
Wastes from mfg	0.0	0.0
Wastes from rec/sorting	1.4	1.4
Biodegradable wastes	1.4	1.4
Compostable wastes	0.0	0.0

Results show an improvement in all metrics

Table 9. Circularity assessment for powder detergent in starch coated cardboard

Type	Indicator	units	relative
Mass	Virgin raw material	%	94%
Mass	Product mass (w primary packaging)	%	100%
Ec / EMF	Resource longevity	time / cycles	1
Ec / EMF	Value based Resource efficiency	%	749
EMF	Linear flow index	%	47.8
EMF	Material circularity index	%	57
CEIS	End-of-life recycling input rates	%	30
CEIS	Circular material use rate	%	28
CIRC-PACK	Degradation rate	%	0.5
CIRC-PACK	Compostable rate	%	0.0
Ec / EMF	Wastes	%	1.4

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Ec / EMF	Utility factor		0.90
Ec / EMF	Utility		1.00

Focusing on the the packaging material flows, the improvement between laminated and starch coating package becomes more visible, with great leaps in the LFI and MCI indicators. The decrease in wastes is also important. Recycling input rates (ratio of recycled material vs new virgin packaging material) and CMU (ratio of recycled material in the manufacturing processes are above 100% due to the high proportion of cardboard used in the packaging and the assumption that all the cardboard is recycled).

Table 10. Circularity assessment for powder detergent. Packaging only

Value chain 5, DC-B, powder detergent, material only (SAPONIA)			
Indicator	units	laminated	starch coating
Linear flow index	%	74.3%	30.6%
Material circularity index	%	33%	72%
End-of-life recycling input rates	%	511%	502%
Circular material use rate	%	244%	243%
Degradation rate	%	0.0%	4.1%
Compostable rate	%	0.0%	0.0%
Wastes W/M	%	11.6%	1.4%

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4 PLASTIC PACKAGING FOR LIQUID DETERGENT VALUE CHAIN

4.1 Value chain description

Most bottles for liquid detergent products are based on HDPE or PET (PET in the case of SAPONIA D. D.). They are manufactured blowing plastic preforms previously prepared by injection moulding. Regarding caps, they are usually based on PP and they are prepared by injection moulding.

PET bottles are filled with liquid detergent, packaged within different tertiary packaging formats (e.g. boxes) and distributed. The flow-chart of this value chain is represented in Figure 12.

In the particular case of SAPONIA D. D., they produce final product by filling plastic bottles with liquid detergent and packaging for distribution (tertiary packaging). Additionally, SAPONIA D. D. produces (by blow-moulding) most common packaging formats such as PET bottles of 400 mL. Thus, these products have been selected to implement innovations of CIRC-PACK project. These materials **are currently based on virgin polymers**, which will be substituted by bio-based polymers during innovations. Scraps generated during manufacturing process are currently send for external recovery in order to use them in other applications.

Figure 12. Flow chart of current state (baseline) for value chain of packaged liquid soap products

Regarding the End-Of-Life (EoL), the amount of plastic recycled materials in Europe depends on the country. In the same manner, the non-collected material can end-up on landfill or incineration depending on the European country. In Figure 13 it can be seen the rate of recycling vs energy recovery in different European countries [10]. Therefore, both scenarios have been taken into account for the non-recycled material.

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Figure 13. Recycling and energy recovery rates for plastic packaging in European countries

4.2 Environmental assessment

Calculation of environmental impact has been made per unit of product but it also includes the allocated percentage of tertiary packaging (boxes, wrap film, pallet...). The environmental assessment has been performed using ReCiPe and CED characterization methods.

In a first analysis it is evaluated the contribution of different inputs/outputs of the packaging process. As it can be in Figure 14, main environmental impact when using ReCiPe indicators is associated to the production of liquid soap. PET bottles have a relative impact of around 10-20%. This effect is slightly compensated by external recovery of packaging components such as cardboard boxes, but the effect in overall contribution of packaging is not significant [2, 3].

Figure 14. Distribution of overall environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for different inputs/outputs of packaged liquid soap (per unit)

A similar situation can be observed when using CED characterization method. Data is available in Table 11.

Table 11. Cumulative Energy Demand for different inputs/outputs of packaged liquid soap (per unit)

Cumulative Energy Demand for packaged liquid soap (per unit)			
PET bottle	3,502	Plastic film palletizing	0,026
Liquid soap	28,163	Pallet	0,003
PP caps	0,371	Electricity	0,083
PET scrap	-0,086	EoL PET bottle (40% recycling + 60% landfill)	-0,829
PP scrap	-0,007	EoL PP caps (landfill)	0,001
Label	0,111	EoL cardboard	-0,280
Box secondary packaging	0,120	EoL plastic film	-0,021
Cardboard sheet pallet	0,036		

In the second assessment, packaging has been analysed separately. In this case, only raw materials for manufacturing of bottle (PET bottle and PP cap) and their EoL are considered. For PET bottles, a 40% of recycling rate has been considered as representative value for

Europe [10]. Two different EoL scenarios have been considered for the other 60%: landfill and incineration. PP caps are normally discarded for disposal in the first steps of the sorting process. Therefore, landfill or incineration have been considered as EoL for PP caps (same scenario than non-recycled PET bottles). An additional scenario with a hypothetical 100% recycling has been also evaluated. Recycling does not affect to PP caps, which has been considered going to landfill in this scenario. Results are represented in Figure 15. Recycling lead to reduce the impact of packaging to 15% (in the worst case for ionizing radiation) to 83% (in the best case for marine eutrophication). Regarding landfill and incineration, incineration has higher impact in several indicators such as global warming, ozone depletion or toxicity related indicators.

Figure 15. Environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for packaging of liquid soap (per unit) with different EoL scenarios a) 100% recycling of PET bottles, b) 40% recycling of PET bottles with incineration for no recycled material, c) 40% recycling of PET bottles with landfilling for no recycled material

The hypothetical scenario of 100% recycling leads to saving of around 1,5 MJ per unit of packaging as it can be seen in Table 12. Incineration and landfill for the 60% of non-recycled material have associated similar environmental CED impact.

Table 12. Cumulative Energy Demand for packaging of liquid soap (per unit) with different EoL scenarios

Cumulative Energy Demand for packaging of liquid soap (per unit)					
100% recycling	1,428	Incineration	3,006	Landfill	3,012

Results are aligned with those reported in the literature where recycling lead to savings in energy demand and other indicators [11, 12].

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4.3 Economic assessment

The different costs associated with manufacturing of packaged liquid soap products has been collected to perform the LCC analysis. They are differentiated according to different categories such as raw materials, energy use, waste, maintenance (OPEX) and amortization of equipment (CAPEX).

As mentioned in deliverable D2.2, describing the methodology, labour cost has not been included because the innovations would not affect to them and there are high differences in labour costs among different countries. In this manner, results achieved when comparing impact of the innovations would have higher replicability across Europe. One year has been considered as temporary basis in order to avoid seasonal deviations.

In Figure 16 it is represented the contribution of different categories to overall cost of the product. It can be seen that raw materials is the major cost with a 90% of the overall cost. Packaging represents a 67% of the overall cost.

Figure 16. Contribution of different cost categories in manufacturing of packaged liquid soap

Finally, it is worth to mention that other indicators such as NPV, IRR or ROI have not been calculated for the baseline because they only have sense when comparing baseline with potential innovations. Regarding the net added value, this indicator will be assessed as a part of the circularity framework.

4.4 Social assessment

The substitution of petrol-based polymers by bio-based polymers does not have relevant consequences on packaging manufacturing process from a social point of view. In this sense, no new positions are expected nor significant workflow variations. Changes are

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foreseeable at consumer and community level. Saponia, as cosmetics packer, expects new packaging having the same or better properties than current plastic packaging and the improvement of end of life management due to their better recyclability and/or biodegradability. It is notable that, among this value chain's stakeholders, no consensus is found regarding on the impact of innovations on domestic waste management as can be observed in Table 13. Related to partners' commitment, Tecno, Saponia, Calaf and Ecoembes rely on certified environmental certificates and 100% of workforce related to this production line is hired locally.

Table 13. Plastic packaging for cosmetics social reference point

Partner	TECNO	SAPONIA	CALAF ⁶	ECOEMBES
Task/ Role	Bottle manufacturing	Cosmetics packaging	Disposal and recycling	Disposal and recycling
N° employees in the company	23	850	26	143
1. Equal opportunities/discrimination (gender issues)				
Male/female rates within workforce in the chain	Male: 70% Female: 30%	Male: 25% Female: 75%	Male: 90% Female: 10%	Male: 50% Female: 50%
Preference for positions	Indifferent	Indifferent	Indifferent	Indifferent
2. Training and education				
Is workflow process modified by innovations?	Yes	No	No	No
Training for workers in the chain	24 hours/yr	10 hours/yr	80 hours/yr	30 hours/yr
Training programme	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
3. Workers' health and safety				
Do innovations involve or increase risks?	No	No	No	No
Average lost days per worker/yr in the chain for health and safety reason	0 days/yr	0 days/yr	0 days/yr	1 days/yr
Safety trainee	16 hours/yr	20 hours/yr 60 hours/yr ⁷	10 hours/yr	Unknown
Protective equipment availability in the chain	Yes. Gloves and safety shoes	Yes. Protective clothes, shoes, gloves, eye protection	Yes. ⁸	Yes.
Severe accidents in the chain	0 accidents/yr	0 accidents/yr	0 accidents/yr	0 accidents/yr
4. Consumers' health and safety				

⁶ Please note that Calaf's workflow is related to machine sensors development

⁷ 20 hours/yr- at employment on fire protection, general work safety and protective equipment. 60 hours/yr- at the beginning of work on specific machine on hazards and how to work safely, annual check-up by safety officer

⁸ Helmet, gloves, hearing protection devices (ear plugs and ear muffs), safety glasses, face shield, gas masks with different filters, safety shoes, gloves (leather, polyvinyl, polyethylene, textile, dielectric)

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Information/Signs available regarding features	Yes. Resin identification code	Yes. Specific labelling	Yes. Material certificates	N/A
Storage conditions	None	None	None	N/A
5. End-of-life responsibility				
Clear information on EOL options	Yes. Resin identification code	Yes. Specific labelling	Yes. User guide	N/A
Impact on domestic waste management	More difficult management (less impact on environment)	Easier	Same	More difficult
6. Consumers' well being				
Quality expectation/ Performance and usability	Same	Same	Better	N/A
User friendliness/ Convenience and acceptance	Same	Same	Better	N/A
7. Community access to material resources				
Certified environmental management system	Yes, ISO 14001	Yes. ISO 14001	Yes, ISO 14001	Yes
Current materials origin in the chain	100 % Virgin	95 % Virgin 5 % Recycled	100 % Virgin	N/A
8. Safe and healthy living conditions				
Corporate social responsibility policy	No	Yes. Support UN Global	No	Yes
Management effort to minimize use of hazardous substances	No hazardous substances use	No hazardous substances use	No hazardous substances use	N/A
9. Local employment				
Workforce hired locally	100%	100%	100%	100%
Local suppliers	20%	0%	50%	100%
10. Community engagement				
Annual events/Workshops organized/participating locally	5 events/yr	5 environmental events/yr 10 visits to/from schools/yr 5 sporting events/yr	1 events/yr	30 recycling initiative, programs/yr (schools and citizen organizations)
Impact in social media	1,800 people reached/yr	100,000 people reached/yr	609 people reached/yr	10,000 people reached/yr
11. Technology development				
Previous involvement in technology transfer program or projects	No	Yes	Yes	No
Investment in technology development	200,000 €/yr	1,200,000 €/yr	200,000 €/yr	25,000 €/yr
12. Suppliers relationships				

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Seal of quality/Management system required for suppliers	Yes, ISO 9001	No, but they have to satisfy quality requirements and prove that they will have consistent quality	Yes	Yes
Suppliers from countries with high estimated proportion of population in modern slavery	0%	0%	0%	0%

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4.5 Circularity assessment

The value chain assessed for circularity is the everyday cosmetic products, and in particular, the soap in plastic bottles fabricated by SAPONIA D.D. Soap comes in 350 g PET bottles. After filling, bottles are capped and labelled. This is the product that end users find available in supermarkets and drugstores. Cardboard boxes and palletising film are sent to recycling by the retailers and make part of the packaging but do not arrive to the final user. In other words, they are taken out of the waste flow. Internal manufacturing wastes (3% in capping and 1% in labelling) are fully collected by waste management companies. End user collection rate has been taken 40% according to European averages. PET sorting rate in mixed packaging wastes according to ECOEMBES's statistics is 90.5%. No recycled material has been accounted for in the raw material inventory, except for the box cardboard. No wastes from recycling are inputted since this data is unknown. A single use of the bottles is expected.

The annual mass balance for a full year production, is shown in the table below.

Table 14. Mass flow inventory for Soap in plastic bottles (SAPONIA)

material	Product g/unit	Packaging g/unit	% respect to M	% of M Pack
Virgin material	386.2	43.7	101%	103%
Product material	382.2	42.4	100%	100%
User mat to recycle	12.9	12.9	3.4%	30%
Mfg mat to recycle	10.2	10.2	2.7%	24.0%
Recycled mat for mfg	7.5	7.5	2.0%	18%
Wastes from end user	19.3	19.3	5.1%	46%
Wastes from mfg	0.0	0.0	0.0%	0%
Wastes from sorting	19.5	19.5	5.1%	46%
Wastes from recycling	0.0	0.0	0.0%	0%

With these hypothesis, the circularity indicators values for the baseline situation is the table below:

Table 15. Mass flow inventory for Soap in plastic bottles (SAPONIA)

Indicator	units	relative /M
Virgin raw material	%	101
Product mass (w primary packaging)	%	100
Resource longevity	time / cycles	1.00
Value based Resource efficiency	%	586
Linear flow index	%	56.3
Material circularity index	%	49
End-of-life recycling input rates	%	17
Circular material use rate (CMU)	%	18
Degradation rate	%	0.0
Compostable rate	%	0.0
Wastes	%	10.2

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Utility factor	%	0.90
Utility	%	1.00

A high material circularity index is obtained along the value chain due to the 100% recirculated material ratio assumed by the different value chain actors, mainly manufacturer and involved retailers, which limit the final amount of wastes. The use of recycled cardboard for boxes, also contributes. The open issue is the recovering ratio of the PET bottles, which ends up being 36%. This is the main area of improvement of the value chain, as well as the biodegradability of the bottles themselves.

The value added metrics regarding the resources used, both in terms of mass and economic value (586%) are really high due to the overall high net added value. The main contributor is the low cost of the main raw material (soap) with respect to the selling price. In this sense, this seems to be cost margin for innovative but more sustainable packaging solutions in the form of bio-based bottles.

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5 ULTRALIGHTWEIGHT PLASTIC BAGS VALUE CHAIN

5.1 Value chain description

Plastic bags are normally based on polyethylene (PE) because of their flexibility and good impact resistance. They are manufactured by two consecutive processes. In a first process, a tubular film is produced by blown-film extrusion from PE granulates. Afterwards, the film is converted (by welding & sealing) into the final product.

There are different type of bags depending on thickness and performance that are going to be assessed during CIRC-PACK project:

- Thick bags (> 50 microns) - *reusable*
- Ultralightweight plastic bags (< 15 microns)

The last ones are designed mainly for packaging of loose food (no load-bearing applications). The lightweight and ultralightweight plastic bags are considered as single-use plastic bags because their resistance is not enough to ensure reuse. Thicker bags are strong enough to be reused.

Lightweight plastic bags (< 50 μm) generate higher amount of wastes and member states should take measures to reduce their consumption. Because of this legislative restriction [13], innovations in plastic films have focused on carrier bags with thickness below 15 microns (ultralightweight bags) which generates less amount of waste, or thickness over 50 microns which can be reused (reusable bags).

Since their use phase is different and it can affect the overall impact of the product, those products have been evaluated separately. This section is focused on plastic carrier bags below 15 microns, whose disposal is being considered after one single use.

The disposal takes place through selective collection in packaging bins. Nevertheless, collection process is difficult and it is estimated that although a 40% of plastic packaging waste is recycled [10] only around 7% of the plastic used for carrier bags are recovered for recycling taking into account both European and worldwide statistics [1, 14]. The rest of the material goes to landfill or incineration. As in other cases, both scenarios have been evaluated for higher replicability of results across Europe.

As raw materials, a mixture of **PE and PELLD is used**. In the **current situation (baseline)**, a **50% of recycled material** is being used, percentage that will be increased during innovations. Recycled material is obtained internally in Mi-Plast facilities through grinding and re-granulating of internal scrap and external plastic wastes.

The flow-chart of this value chain is represented in Figure 17.

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Figure 17. Flow chart of current state (baseline) for value chain of ultralightweight plastic bags (< 15 microns)

5.2 Environmental assessment

The environmental assessment has been performed using ReCiPe and CED characterization methods using data collected for preparation of LCI.

In a first assessment, the environmental impact of inputs/outputs associated to the manufacturing process has been evaluated. A unitary weight of 4,5 g has been considered for these bags. The proportion of recycled materials is 50% between recycled PELLD and PELD (this percentage will be increase during CIRC-PACK project). Regarding the EoL, a 7% collection rate is considered as representative scenario. The other 93% is going to landfill. As in previous value chains, ReCiPe and CED methods have been used for comparison.

As it can be seen in Figure 18, virgin PE has a significant impact in several indicators such as global warming, ozone formation, particulate formation, acidification and fossil resource scarcity. The manufacturing process has also associated significant impacts in most of the indicators (from 20 to 80% in some cases). It can also be seen in Figure 18 that EoL of the material has also significant impact in some indicators such as those related with toxicity. It can also be seen that the use of recycled materials lead to savings in most of the indicators which can reach up to 20%.

Figure 18. Distribution of overall environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for different inputs/outputs of ultralightweight plastic bags (per unit)

When using CED indicator, main contribution is ascribed to virgin PELD (Table 3). Virgin material represents the 93% of raw materials, while recycled material only represents 7% (being both of them in the same amount since they are used at 50%). This results are in accordance with other assessments where it has been reported a significant lower impact for post-consumer resins than for virgin resins [11].

Table 16. Cumulative Energy Demand for different inputs/outputs of ultralightweight plastic bags (per unit)

Cumulative Energy Demand for ultralightweight plastic bags (per unit)			
Virgin PELD	0,184	Manufacturing	0,096
Recycled PELLD	0,002	EoL	-0,045
Recycled PE	0,011		

In a second assessment, different EoL scenarios have been considered for ultralightweight plastic bags. As it has been commented before, there is reported that average recycling rate in Europe for plastics bags is around 7%. Therefore, this value has been considered for the EoL. Two different possibilities have been considered for the other 93%: landfill and incineration. As in other value chains, a hypothetical 100% recycling scenario has been also

introduced in the assessment to evaluate potential improvements by boosting recycling of these products.

Results are represented in Figure 19. It can be seen that highest savings through recycling are obtained in fossil resource scarcity indicators and ozone formation. Other indicators with significant savings are global warming potential, particulate matter formation and water consumption. On the other hand, recycling has slightly higher impact in some indicators such as ionizing radiation, land use and human non-carcinogenic toxicity because of electricity used during recycling process.

Comparing incineration and landfilling, the first one has higher impact in ozone depletion and terrestrial ecotoxicity mainly. Landfill has significantly higher impact in human non-carcinogenic toxicity and marine eutrophication.

Figure 19. Environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for ultralightweight plastic bags (per unit) with different EoL scenarios a) 100% recycling, b) 7% recycling with incineration for no recycled material, c) 7% recycling with landfilling for no recycled material

The hypothetical scenario of 100% recycling leads to saving of around 0,61 MJ per unit. Incineration and landfill for the 60% of non-recycled material have associated similar environmental CED impact. These savings through recycling have been already reported in the literature [14, 15].

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Table 17. Cumulative Energy Demand for ultralightweight plastic bags (per unit) with different EoL scenarios

Cumulative Energy Demand for ultralightweight plastic bags (per unit)					
100% recycling	-0,361	Incineration	0,249	Landfill	0,248

It has been also analysed the environmental impact of different raw materials used for bag manufacturing (virgin and recycled PE and PELLD). This analysis has been performed for 1 kg of raw material. Results for assessment carried out with ReCiPe characterization method are represented in Figure 20. It can be seen that recycled materials have associated higher impact on ionizing radiation, freshwater eutrophication and land use, which is ascribed to electricity consumed for recycling. On the other hand, significant savings are obtained in the rest of indicators, especially in marine eutrophication and other indicators related with toxicity.

Figure 20. Environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for virgin and recycled plastic materials (per kg) used in the manufacturing of plastic bags.

When using CED characterization method (Table 18), savings achieved through recycling are significant. It can be seen that PE has slightly higher impact than PELLD both for virgin and recycled material. Savings achieved through recycling are in the order of 70-75 MJ per kg of material.

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Table 18. Cumulative Energy Demand for virgin and recycled plastic materials (per kg) used in the manufacturing of bags

Cumulative Energy Demand for ultralightweight plastic bags (per kg)			
Virgin PE	80,817	Recycled PE Mi-Plast	6,038
Virgin PELLD	75,804	Recycled PELLD Mi-Plast	5,464

5.3 Economic assessment

The different costs associated with the manufacturing of ultralightweight plastic bags has been considered for the LCC analysis. They are differentiated according to different categories such as raw materials, energy use, waste, maintenance (OPEX) and amortization of equipment (CAPEX).

As mentioned in deliverable D2.2, describing the methodology, labour cost has not been included because the innovations would not affect to them and there are high differences in labour costs among different countries. In this manner, results achieved when comparing impact of the innovations would have higher replicability across Europe. One year has been considered as temporary basis in order to avoid seasonal deviations.

In Figure 21 it is represented the contribution of different categories to overall cost of the product. Raw materials represents 73% of overall cost.

Figure 21. Contribution of different cost categories in manufacturing of ultralightweight plastic bags

On the other hand, it has been analysed the cost distribution for the recycling process. These results are represented in Figure 22 (for PE). It can be seen that main contribution is raw materials with 88% of cost.

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Figure 22. Contribution of different cost categories in recycling of plastic bags

Beside the environmental benefits already mentioned in section 5.2, the use of recycled raw materials has also economic benefits. In Table 19 it can be seen that cost for recycled materials is lower than virgin raw materials (around 15% lower), which is of importance in a raw materials intensive sector as plastic bags manufacturing. It lead to an increment in margins which has been estimated in 20% approximately.

Table 19. Comparison of raw material cost for virgin PE and recycled PE (per kg)

Raw materials cost (euro/kg)					
Virgin PE	1,30	Recycled PE	1,09	Recycled PELLD	1,17

Finally, it is worth to mention that other indicators such as NPV, IRR or ROI have not been calculated for the baseline because they only have sense when comparing baseline with potential innovations. Regarding the net added value, this indicator will be assessed as a part of the circularity framework.

5.4 Social assessment

Thick plastic bags (>50 microns) baseline, in terms of social indicators defined for CIRC-PACK methodology, is equal to thin plastic bags (<15 microns) value chain. Table 20 summarizes the reference point set for these value chains S-LCA. Related to the manufacturing process Mi-PLAST is the only stakeholder involved. Particularly, Mi-PLAST remarks that current bags composition is not exhibit due to painful truth. However, innovations will encourage to present recycled content on new bags. Moreover, no significant modifications on product format are expected due to 'the idea is that we create same products but with other materials.'

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Table 20. Thin plastic bags social reference point

Partner	MI-PLAST	CALAF ⁹	ECOEMBES
Task/ Role	Plastic bag manufacture	Disposal and recycling	Disposal and recycling
N° employees in the company	12	26	143
1. Equal opportunities/discrimination (gender issues)			
Male/female rates within workforce in the chain	Male: 45% Female: 55%	Male: 90% Female: 10%	Male: 50% Female: 50%
Preference for positions	Indifferent	Indifferent	Indifferent
2. Training and education			
Is workflow process modified by innovations?	Yes	No	No
Training for workers in the chain	240 hours/yr	80 hours/yr	30 hours/yr
Training programme	Yes	Yes	Yes
3. Workers' health and safety			
Do innovations involve or increase risks?	No	No	No
Average lost days per worker/year in the chain for health and safety reason	7 days/yr	0 days/yr	1 days/yr
Safety trainee	180 hours/yr	10 hours/yr	Unknown
Protective equipment availability in the chain	Yes. Gloves, respirators, ear-covers.	Yes. ¹⁰	Yes.
Severe accidents in the chain	0 accidents/yr	0 accidents/yr	0 accidents/yr
4. Consumers' health and safety			
Information/Signs available regarding features	No	Yes. Material certificates	N/A
Storage conditions	None	None	N/A
5. End-of-life responsibility			
Clear information on EOL options	No	Yes. User guide	N/A
Impact on domestic waste management	More difficult	Same	More difficult
6. Consumers' well being			
Quality expectation/ Performance and usability	Same	Better	N/A
User friendliness/ Convenience and acceptance	Better	Better	N/A
7. Community access to material resources			
Certified environmental management system	No	Yes, ISO 14001	Yes
Current materials origin in the chain	30 % Virgin 70 % Recycled	100 % Virgin	N/A
8. Safe and healthy living conditions			

⁹ Please note that Calaf's workflow is related to machine sensors development

¹⁰ Helmet, gloves, hearing protection devices (ear plugs and ear muffs), safety glasses, face shield, gas masks with different filters, safety shoes, gloves (leather, polyvinyl, polyethylene, textile, dielectric)

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Corporate social responsibility policy	Yes	No	Yes
Management effort to minimize use of hazardous substances	No hazardous substances use	No hazardous substances use	N/A
9. Local employment			
Workforce hired locally	100%	100%	100%
Local suppliers	70%	50%	100%
10. Community engagement			
Annual events/Workshops organized/participating locally	3 events/yr	1 events/yr	30 recycling initiative, programs/year in (schools and citizen organizations)
Impact in social media	No current participation	609 people reached/yr	10,000 people reached/yr
11. Technology development			
Previous involvement in technology transfer program or projects	Yes	Yes	No
Investment in technology development	100,000 €/yr	200,000 €/yr	25,000 €/yr
12. Suppliers relationships			
Seal of quality/Management system required for suppliers	Yes	Yes	Yes
Suppliers from countries with high estimated proportion of population in modern slavery	0%	0%	0%

5.5 Circularity assessment

Polyethylene thin plastic bags made by MIPLAST are half made of virgin PE and half made from recycled PE and LLDPE. As in other film recovery rates, it is assumed a low recovery from end user waste (9.7%). Investigations showed that these bags can carry up to 4 kg and they can be used several times but citizens are just using it once for an average load of 1 kg. Then, the utility for a bag unit is assumed to be 4 kg transported only 1 time, with a value of 1. The low recovery rate and utility are the two main issues of this value chain.

MIPLAST annual production of these type of bags is 70,000 kg per year, corresponding to more than 15.5 million bags (4.5 g/bag). The production line assets are shared with the production of thick bags (>50 microns), about 100,000 kg/year. Internal scrap takes place at the film extrusion process (1%) and at the bag welding and sealing (15%). This scrap is totally recovered and internally recycled.

The mass inventory for annual values in kg/yea and grams / unit is shown in the following table.

Table 21. Mass flow inventory for 15 micron plastic bag (MIPLAST)

material	g/unit	% respect to M
Virging material	2.7	59%
Product material	4.5	100%
User mat to recycle	0.4	10%

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Mfg mat to recycle	0.9	19%
Recycled mat for mfg	2.5	56%
Wastes from end user	4.1	90%
Wastes from mfg	0.0	0%
Wastes from rec/sorting	0.1	3%
Biodegradable wastes	0.0	0%
Compostable wastes	0.0	0%

Applying circularity metrics to the production of thin bags, the results show a large amount of waste that it is only partially compensated with the internal scrap recycling, and the use of recycled material in the production of new bags. The problem remains on the low life of the product and the low recovery rate from the user's side.

Table 22. Circularity assessment for 15 micron plastic bag (MIPLAST)

Indicator	units	relative /M
Virgin raw material	%	59
Product mass (w primary packaging)	%	100
Resource longevity	reuses	1
Value based Resource efficiency	%	41
Linear flow index	%	76
Material circularity index	%	31
End-of-life recycling input rates	%	94
Circular material use rate (CMU)	%	56
Degradation rate	%	0
Compostable rate	%	0
Wastes	%	94
Utility factor		0.90
Utility		1.00

Due to the low value of this product, resource efficiency and productivity are rather low, and the process of manufacturing, using and disposal are rather linear. The challenge of this product is to demonstrate the feasibility of producing biodegradable bags to close the process loop up to the biological restoration and avoid long term wastes.

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6 THICK PLASTIC BAGS VALUE CHAIN

6.1 Value chain description

Thick plastic bags are similar to ultralightweight plastic bags (same materials and manufacturing processes) already analysed in section 6. The only difference is the thickness of the plastic film (above 50 microns) in order to achieve higher mechanical properties, which allow reusability of the product.

For the EoL scenario, a **7% of recovery** has been considered (as in ultralightweight plastic bags) according to references [1]. For the rest of the materials, landfill and incineration have been evaluated for higher replicability of results across Europe.

Because of higher thickness, reusable bags have higher unitary weight. Therefore, the impact of one reusable plastic bag should be higher than the impact of one ultralightweight plastic bag because of the higher consumption of material and higher amount of waste generated. However, it should be taken into account that reusable bag can be used more than once and can transport higher amount of goods in its lifetime. In order to take into account this, the impact has been also calculated for kg of transported goods. For this calculation, it has been assumed 8 uses for the reusable bags and 12 kg of maximum carrying capacity for each use. In the case of ultralightweight plastic bags, the carrying capacity has been considered to be around 3 times lower due to the lower thickness, so 4 kg carrying capacity has been considered [16, 17].

As in the case of ultralightweight plastic bags, both virgin and recycled materials are currently used as raw materials. Recycled materials are obtained from internal scrap and external plastic wastes.

The flow-chart of this value chain is represented in Figure 23.

Figure 23. Flow chart of current state (baseline) for value chain of thick plastic bags (> 50 microns)

6.2 Environmental assessment

The environmental assessment has been performed using ReCiPe and CED characterization methods.

In a first assessment, the environmental impact of inputs/outputs associated to the manufacturing process has been evaluated. A unitary weight of 23 gr has been considered. As in the previous case, the proportion of recycled materials is 50% between recycled PELLD and PELD (this percentage will be increase during CIRC-PACK project). Regarding the EoL, a 7% collection rate is also considered. The other 93% is going to landfill. As in previous value chains, ReCiPe and CED methods have been used for comparison.

As it can be seen in Figure 24, results are very similar to those obtained for ultralightweight plastic bags (in terms of relative contribution). Virgin PE and inputs for manufacturing process (namely electricity) have the main contribution in most of the indicators.

Figure 24. Distribution of overall environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for different inputs/outputs of thick plastic bags (per unit)

When using CED indicator, main contribution is also ascribed to virgin PELD. In Table 23 it can be also seen the comparison with CED values for ultralightweight plastic bags. The energy consumption is significantly higher for thick plastic bags because of the higher consumption of raw materials and waste generated. The same occurs with absolute value indicators for ReCiPe methods.

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Table 23. Cumulative Energy Demand for different inputs/outputs of ultralightweight and thick plastic bags (per unit)

Cumulative Energy Demand for ultralightweight and thick plastic bags (per unit)			
Ultralightweight plastic bags		Thick plastic bags	
Virgin PELD	0,184	Virgin PELD	0,939
Recycled PELLD	0,002	Recycled PELLD	0,056
Recycled PE	0,011	Recycled PE	0,013
Manufacturing	0,096	Manufacturing	0,489
EoL	-0,045	EoL	-0,228

In a second analysis, the assessment has been performed taking the weight of transported goods as functional unit. In this manner, the use phase of the bag has been also considered. For reusable bags, 8 uses with capacity of 12 kg per use have been taking into account [16, 17]. For single-use bags, the capacity is around four times lower (4 kg of average transport capacity) and 1 use has been taken into account. Landfilling has been considered for the 93% of non recycled material.

With these assumptions, impacts associated to ReCiPe indicators for reusable bags is 85% lower than impact for single-use bags. Required energy (evaluated through CED method) for reusable bags is also in the range of 15% of the single use ones. Data for CED are summarized in Table 24. Since single-use bag can carry 4 kg once, the impact is the same per unit than extrapolated to kg of transported goods. For reusable bags, the high impact per unit is significantly reduced when calculated for kg of transported good.

Table 24. Cumulative Energy Demand for ultralightweight and thick plastic bags (per unit)

Cumulative Energy Demand for ultralightweight and thick plastic bags (per unit)			
Ultralightweight plastic bags		Thick plastic bags	
Per unit	0,248	Per unit	1,268
Per kg transported good	0,062	Per kg transported good	0,013

6.3 Economic assessment

The different costs associated with the manufacturing of thick plastic bags have been differentiated according to different categories such as raw materials, energy use, waste, maintenance (OPEX) and amortization of equipment (CAPEX).

As mentioned in deliverable D2.2, describing the methodology, labour cost has not been included because the innovations would not affect to them and there are high differences in labour costs among different countries. In this manner, results achieved when comparing impact of the innovations would have higher replicability across Europe. One year has been considered as temporary basis in order to avoid seasonal deviations.

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In Figure 25 it is represented the contribution of different categories to overall cost of the product. In this case, raw materials represents 84% of overall cost (for ultralightweight plastic bags it was lower). This contribution is higher because of the higher weight of reusable bags, which requires higher amount of material for manufacturing process.

Figure 25. Contribution of different cost categories in manufacturing of thick plastic bags

In both cases, the use of recycled material lead to higher benefits due to the lower cost in raw materials.

Finally, it is worth to mention that other indicators such as NPV, IRR or ROI have not been calculated for the baseline because they only have sense when comparing baseline with potential innovations. Regarding the net added value, this indicator will be assessed as a part of the circularity framework.

6.4 Social assessment

Thick plastic bags (>50 microns) baseline, in terms of social indicators defined for CIRC-PACK methodology, is equal to thin plastic bags (<15 microns) value chain. Please, for social reference point see Table 20.

6.5 Circularity assessment

The manufacturing process and hypothesis taken for thick bags value chain are the same as for thin bags from the previous chapter. In this case, the higher value added of this product results on a higher selling price In this case, thick bags are sold at a higher unitary

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price but a lower price per kg (2.5 €/kg for thin bags instead of 2 €/kg for thick bags). However, the manufacturing costs per kg, mainly raw materials, are the same, deriving in a lower net added value and lower resource efficiency per kg of the thick bag versus the thin bag (0.35 €/kg of added value for the thick product vs 0.71 €/kg of the thin product).

In terms of mass, the annual production reported by MIPLAST is 100,000 kg of 23 g bags, which represent 4.35 million bags. The mass inventory of the value chain is as follows.

Table 25. Mass flow inventory for 50 micron plastic bag (MIPLAST)

material	g/unit	% respect to M
Virgin material	14	59%
Product material	23	100%
User mat to recycle	2	10%
Mfg mat to recycle	4	19%
Recycled mat for mfg	13	56%
Wastes from end user	21	93%
Wastes from mfg	0	0%
Wastes from rec/sorting	1	3%
Biodegradable wastes	0	0%
Compostable wastes	0	0%

The main difference of this product is the longer life and utility. For the calculations, it is assumed that this type of bags can carry four times heavier load (12kg transported in a thick bag versus 4kg transported using an ultralight one) and can be reused up to 8 times. If the standard utility unit is the ultralight bag 4 kg – 1 time, this bag's utility is 24 times better. Although this does not reduce the amount of waste finally generated, it improves by three the material circularity index as shown in the table below.

Table 26. Circularity assessment for 50 micron plastic bag (MIPLAST)

Indicator	units	relative
Virgin raw material	%	59
Product mass (w primary packaging)	%	100
Resource longevity	reuses	8
Value based Resource efficiency	%	21
Linear flow index	%	76
Material circularity index	%	97
End-of-life recycling input rates	%	94
Circular material use rate (CMU)	%	56
Degradation rate	%	0
Compostable rate	%	0
Wastes	Kg/year	94
Utility factor		0.04
Utility		24.00

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The main improvements in this value chain for the future are a higher end user collection rate and the bio-degradability of the materials to reduce the long-term wastes reported in these metrics.

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7 FOOD PACKAGING (TRAYS AND MULTILAYER FILM) VALUE CHAIN

7.1 Value chain description

Packaging for meat products is usually based on a plastic tray, which is filled with an inert air atmosphere and sealed with a multilayer film comprising several polymers to obtain good barrier properties. The packaged product is chilled and storage for distribution.

For trays, a combination of different material can also be used to increase barrier properties, although is more likely to find monomaterials, as in the case of SADA which is using PET monomaterial trays. Film used for sealing, because of the lower thickness, is normally comprised several materials in order to achieved desired barrier properties. This is the current situation of SADA where tray is based on **100% virgin PET (monomaterial) and film is based on a multimaterial layer**. Both products will be substituted for bio-based polymers during innovations.

In this particular product, packaging can have a significant impact in the use phase. Due to the short shelf-life of some food products, around 87.6 million tonnes of food waste are generated in Europe. Around 46% of this waste is generated in household, a percentage which can increase up to 62% including distribution from factories to customers [19]. This percentage can be highly influenced by the packaging and their barrier properties and it is worth to include in the environmental assessment as an output of the use phase. For the evaluation, this data has been estimated from the expiring date of the product with the corresponding packaging material.

Regarding the EoL, both components (trays and film) are disposed in the packaging selection bin for sorting and recycling. Both materials are considered to be recycled after their sorting, avoiding the use of corresponding amount of raw materials. Nevertheless, a recycling rate of 40% can be considered for trays as representative recycling rate in Europe for plastic products [20]. In the case of films, a lower recycling rate (around 7%) has been reported [1]. For the non-recycled material, incineration and landfill can be considered depending on the European country.

The flow-chart of this value chain is represented in Figure 26. The packaging process comprise two steps: 1) vacuum and sealing in which the food is placed into the tray which is filled with inert atmosphere and sealed; 2) chilling and storage in which the product is cooled for proper storage.

Figure 26. Flow chart of current state (baseline) for value chain of packaged chicken products

7.2 Environmental assessment

All the inputs/outputs associated to packaging process of chicken products in GRUPO SADA facilities has been collected in the LCI. The environmental assessment has been performed using ReCiPe and CED characterization methods.

In the first analysis, it has been evaluated the contribution of different inputs associated to the packaged food product. As it can be seen in Figure 27, major contributions are associated with production of chicken and electricity for storage of raw materials and finished products. These results are in the same order of magnitude of other LCA studies where chicken production has been reported to have a non-negligible effect on the environmental impact which varies depending on the indicator selected [20, 21].

Figure 27. Distribution of overall environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for different inputs/outputs of packaged chicken products (per unit)

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Results using CED characterization method are shown in Table 27. As in evaluation through ReCiPe indicators, chicken and storage have the major contribution to CED.

Table 27. Cumulative Energy Demand for different inputs/outputs of packaged chicken products (per unit)

Cumulative Energy Demand for packaged chicken products (per unit)			
Chicken (kg)	20,030	Storage finished product	29,102
PET trays (kg)	1,129	Storage waste	0,000
Film (kg)	0,188	Recycling scrap chilling	-0,033
Vacuum - gas injection - sealing	0,492	Recycling scrap Vacuum - gas injection - sealing	-0,033
Chilling	0,029	EoL PET trays	-1,001
Storage raw materials	27,938	EoL film	-0,009
Internal transports	0,027	EoL chicken waste (expiring date)	0,269

A second analysis has been performed to evaluate the influence of the EoL of the packaging. For this analysis it has been only considered the raw materials for packaging (tray and film) and their EoL. A minimum of 40% of recycling rate has been considered for trays [20] and 7% for film (as typical recycling rates in Europe for these type of products [1]). Two different EoL scenarios have been considered for the other 60% of waste materials: landfill or incineration. Additionally, a hypothetical case of 100% recycling scenario has been established to estimate improvements that could be achieved by an efficient collection and recycling scheme. Results are represented in Figure 28.

On the one hand, as it can be seen, by comparing the two bars, incineration has higher impact in global warming potential, ozone depletion, ozone formation and human carcinogenic toxicity. On the other hand, landfill has higher impact in marine eutrophication and human non-carcinogenic toxicity. When comparing these scenarios with the hypothetical scenario of 100% recycling, significant savings can be achieved in most of the indicators. The one with lower savings is ionizing radiation because recycling process has significant contribution to this indicator attributed to electricity consumption.

Regarding CED characterization method (Table 28), incineration and landfill of the 60% non-collected material lead to significant consumption of energy. On the other hand, recycling lead to savings around 1,6 MJ per unit of packaged product. Results are aligned with other assessment reported in the literature where recycling lead to savings in energy demand and other indicators [11, 12].

Figure 28. Environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for packaging of chicken products (per unit) with different EoL scenarios: a) 100% recycling, b) 40% recycling for trays and 7% for film (incineration for no recycled materials), c) 40% recycling for trays and 7% for film (landfill for no recycled materials)

Table 28. Cumulative Energy Demand for different of packaging for chicken products (per unit) with different EoL scenarios

Cumulative Energy Demand for packaging of chicken products (per unit)	
Packaging (100% recycling)	-1,342
Packaging (40% recycling + 60% incineration)	0,312
Packaging (40% recycling + 60% landfill)	0,307

7.3 Economic assessment

Different costs associated with manufacturing of packaged food products are differentiated according to different categories such as raw materials, energy use, waste, maintenance (OPEX) and amortization of equipment (CAPEX).

As mentioned in deliverable D2.2, describing the methodology, labour cost has not been included because the innovations would not affect to them and there are high differences in labour costs among different countries. In this manner, results achieved when comparing impact of the innovations would have higher replicability across Europe. One year has been considered as temporary basis in order to avoid seasonal deviations.

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As it can be seen in Figure 29, most of the costs are associated with consumption of raw materials. Packaging components represents 3% of the overall cost, while chicken is the main contribution with 77% of the overall cost.

Figure 29. Contribution of different cost categories in manufacturing of packaged chicken products

Finally, it is worth to mention that other indicators such as NPV, IRR or ROI have not been calculated for the baseline because they only have sense when comparing baseline with potential innovations. Regarding the net added value, this indicator will be assessed as a part of the circularity framework.

7.4 Social assessment

Plastic trays and film for packaging of food products social reference point is presented in Table 29. Value chain stakeholders expect performance and convenience of food trays and multilayer films the same as non-bio-based, but predict easier domestic waste management. The profile of this value chain enables to target communication actions to end-consumers, providing composition information on the product and finding dissemination activities productive or very productive.

Table 29. Plastic trays and film for packaging of food products social reference point

Partner	TECNO	SADA	CALAF ¹¹	ECOEMBES
Task/ Role	Tray + multilayer film manufacture	Food packaging	Disposal and recycling	Disposal and recycling
N° employees in the company	23	1,687	26	143

¹¹ Please note that Calaf's workflow is related to machine sensors development

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1. Equal opportunities/discrimination (gender issues)				
Male/female rates within workforce in the chain	Male: 30% Female: 70%	Male: 25% Female: 75%	Male: 90% Female: 10%	Male: 50% Female: 50%
Preference for positions	Indifferent	Indifferent	Indifferent	Indifferent
2. Training and education				
Is workflow process modified by innovations?	Yes	No	No	No
Training for workers in the chain	24 hours/yr	Not stipulated	80 hours/yr	30 hours/yr
Training programme	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
3. Workers' health and safety				
Do innovations involve or increase risks?	No	No	No	No
Average lost days per worker/year in the chain for health and safety reason	0 days/yr	0 days/yr	0 days/yr	1 days/yr
Safety trainee	16 hours/yr	5 hours/yr 3 hours/yr ¹²	10 hours/yr	Unknown
Protective equipment availability in the chain	Yes. Gloves and safety shoes	No	Yes ¹³	Yes.
Severe accidents in the chain	0 accidents/yr	9 accidents/yr	0 accidents/yr	0 accidents/yr
4. Consumers' health and safety				
Information/Signs available regarding features	Yes. Resin identification code	Yes. Reports of apt to be in contact with food, technical specifications, homologation of materials	Yes. Material certificates	N/A
Storage conditions	None	Fresh and dry	None	N/A
5. End-of-life responsibility				
Clear information on EOL options	Yes. Resin identification code	Yes. Printed on the tray the consumer can know	Yes. User guide	N/A
Impact on domestic waste management	More difficult management (less impact on environment)	Easier	Same	More difficult
6. Consumers' well being				
Quality expectation/ Performance and usability	Same	Same	Better	N/A

¹² 5 hours/yr new workers. 3 hours/yr review

¹³ Helmet, gloves, hearing protection devices (ear plugs and ear muffs), safety glasses, face shield, gas masks with different filters, safety shoes, gloves (leather, polyvinyl, polyethylene, textile, dielectric)

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User friendliness/ Convenience and acceptance	Same	Same	Better	N/A
7. Community access to material resources				
Certified environmental management system	Yes, ISO 14001	Yes, ISO 1001 and ISO 14064	Yes, ISO 14001	Yes
Current materials origin in the chain	100 % Virgin	70 % Virgin 30 % Recycled	100 % Virgin	N/A
8. Safe and healthy living conditions				
Corporate social responsibility policy	No	Yes, it is in the values of the company from the Nutreco matrix	No	Yes
Management effort to minimize use of hazardous substances	No hazardous substances use	No hazardous substances use	No hazardous substances use	N/A
9. Local employment				
Workforce hired locally	100%	90%	100%	100%
Local suppliers	10%	100%	50%	100%
10. Community engagement				
Annual events/Workshops organized/participating locally	5 events/yr	1 events/yr Nutreco Community Day	1 event/yr	30 recycling initiative, programs/yr in (schools and citizen organizations)
Impact in social media	1,800 people reached/yr	No data available	609 people reached/yr	10,000 people reached/yr
11. Technology development				
Previous involvement in technology transfer program or projects	No	Yes	Yes	No
Investment in technology development	200,000 €/yr	500,000 €/yr	200,000 €/yr	25,000 €/yr
12. Suppliers relationships				
Seal of quality/Management system required for suppliers	Yes, ISO 9001	Yes, BRC for packaging companies	Yes	Yes
Suppliers from countries with high estimated proportion of population in modern slavery	0%	0%	0%	0%

7.5 Circularity assessment

This value chain addresses the organic-matter contaminated packaging from the food industry. The product chosen is an 800-g chicken tray, manufactured by SADA. The product

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contains a PET tray of 33.4 g, the wrapping PE film of 2gr and a bit more of 800 g of fresh chicken meat. The mass inventory per tray is depicted in the next table.

Table 30. Mass flow inventory for chicken trays (SADA)

material	Product kg/unit	Packaging kg/unit	% respect to M
Virging material	814	32.6	100.8%
Product material	808	31.7	100.0%
User mat to recycle	13	12.7	1.6%
Mfg mat to recycle	1	0.9	0.1%
Recycled mat for mfg	0	0.0	0.0%
Wastes from end user	19	19.0	2.4%
Wastes from mfg	6	0.4	0.7%
Wastes from rec/sorting	12	0.9	1.5%
Biodegradable wastes	0	0.0	0.0%
Compostable wastes	0	0.0	0.0%

The packaging weight is just 4% of the total product weight and only 0.45% of the manufacturing costs; most of it is related to the PET tray. No recycled material has been taken into account for new product manufacturing. All packaging wastes in the manufacturing process are taken for recycling by an external collector. A minimum amount of chicken meat is wasted and has been considered as biodegradable material. We consider no chicken wastes at the consumer's side and the packaging is recovered at 40% rate according to average European values. Sorting efficiency for film is 9.3% and for PET is 90.5%. No other intermediate packaging is included in the assessment. Trays are assumed to have a single use only.

With these hypothesis and data, the circularity indicator results for the baseline case are the following.

Table 31. Circularity assessment for chicken trays (SADA)

Indicator	units	relative
Virgin raw material	%	101
Product mass (w primary packaging)	%	100
Resource longevity	cycles	1.00
Value based Resource efficiency	%	5.7
Linear flow index	%	52.5
Material circularity index	%	53
End-of-life recycling input rates pack	%	0
Circular material use rate (CMU)	%	0
Degradation rate	kg/year	0.7
Compostable rate	%	0.0
Wastes	%	4.5
Utility factor		0.90

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Utility		1.00
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Net added value per kg of product is low, as it is usually the case in many agro food industries facing a high competition. The resource efficiency (5.7%) is also low for the same reason. Circularity index is affected by the moderate PET tray recovery rate and sorting efficiency, and to the high impact of the chicken meat weight in the total with no consumption wastes considered. In this case, it is worth analysing the flow rates of the packaging material only.

Table 32. Circularity assessment for chicken trays (SADA). Packaging only

Value chain 2, DC-A, Chicken Trays Packaging only		
Indicator	units	relative /M
Linear flow index (LFI)	%	91.5%
Material circularity index (MCI)	%	18%
End-of-life recycling input rates pack	%	0%
Circular material use rate (CMU)	%	0%
Degradation rate	%	0.0%
Wastes	%	4.5%

The packaging mass flow can be considered linear with little circularity. In this type of packaging material, it is hard to increase the consumer's reuse rate, and at manufacturing level there is little room for improvement. Higher collection rate is also hard to achieve although at film level, better rates would be advisable. The path forward targeted by CIRC-PACK to develop bio-based and biodegradable materials is a good solution to minimise environmental impact and reduce long-term degradable wastes to a minimum.

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8 PLASTIC AUTOMOTIVE COMPONENTS VALUE CHAIN

8.1 Value chain description

Some automotive components such as air ducts and bumpers are based on plastic materials comprising several additives such as fibres (e.g. natural fibres, carbon fibres or glass fibres) or mineral particles (e.g. talc). These components are produced by injection moulding from already prepared masterbatches of the plastic material with the corresponding reinforcement.

These automotive components are currently produced in CRF facilities with **100% virgin material**. During the manufacturing process in CRF (as in most of plastic converters) there are some scrap that is currently sold to an external customer. Since, the composition of this scrap is well known and it has similar characteristics than virgin material, it has high potential to be reused after recycling in the same application (automotive components) This is one of the objectives of CIRC-PACK project, since this recycled material is currently used for other applications.

Regarding the EoL destination, a limited amount of scrap can be transported per truck due to space limitations. This amount could be increased by carrying out a grinding process in CRF facilities. Depending on distances and increment in the amount of transported material, this scenario can be an interesting one, even if the material does not return to CRF in order to reduce transport costs and impacts.

Additionally, if CRF is **reusing the recycled material** in their production process, it could be even interesting to perform in-house the re-granulating process.

These alternative recycling scenarios (grinding in CRF facilities for improved logistic and grinding + regranulating in CRF facilities for reuse) are not be implemented within CIRC-PACK project, but their viability from environmental and economic point of view will be analysed to settle-down the basis for a future implementation during the innovation analysis phase. To this end, different analysis focused on the impact of using different raw materials (virgin vs recycled) and the different scenarios for the recycling process (including transport, as it is a key point in the comparison) will be studied during CIRC-PACK. At starting point, in this deliverable, only the current scenario (no recycled material is used as raw material and scrap is directly sent to recycler) has been analysed, evaluating savings achieved by this external recycling (for other applications). Other scenarios (internal grinding and recycling in CRF facilities and use of recycled materials in the manufacturing of car components) will be analysed in deliverable D2.5, which is focused on assessment of innovations.

This value chain is represented in Figure 30. Compounding and injection moulding processes are shadowed because they are out of the scope of the assessment. For the baseline amount of recycled PE is zero and grinding plus re-granulating processes are carried out externally.

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Figure 30. Flow chart of current state for value chain for management of automotive components scrap

8.2 Environmental assessment

Since bumpers and air ducts are based on same materials but they can have different weights depending on the component and the car model, the calculation has been performed taking weight unit (kg) as functional unit. In this manner, results are representative for these two automotive components (and others based in the same plastic materials).

As commented before, the assessment is focused on the management of scrap and failure components. Inputs included are those associated with internal transport in CRF facilities and transport to recycler.

Results are represented in Figure 31 below. As it can be seen in the graph, recycling has higher impact in some categories such as ionizing radiation or freshwater eutrophication due to electricity consumed during recycling process. However, there are significant savings in the other categories. Highest savings are obtained in global warming, fossil resource scarcity and toxicity related indicators. Savings are ascribed to the use of recycled plastic, which avoids production of virgin plastic material [3, 22].

Figure 31. Environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for car component (per kg) with different EoL scenarios

When using CED characterization method (Table 33), it can be seen that incineration and landfill has higher energy consumption. On the other hand, 54 MJ are being saving through recycling of the PP because of the avoided virgin material [3, 22].

Table 33. Cumulative Energy Demand for car components (per kg) with different EoL scenarios

Cumulative Energy Demand for EoL scenarios of car component (per kg)					
Incineration	75,718	Landfill	75,627	Recycling	19,874

8.3 Economic assessment

For the economic assessment, different costs associated with raw materials and scrap generation (including internal transports within CRF facilities and transport for waste management) has been considered. As it can be seen in Figure 32, cost ascribed to transport are negligible compared with consumption of raw materials. The cost associated to the raw materials for scrap represents 22% of the overall cost in raw materials. This data has been calculated taken into account that the company sells the scrap to an external compounder, getting back part of the cost associated with raw materials.

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Figure 32. Contribution of different cost categories associated to raw materials

Finally, it is worth to mention that other indicators such as NPV, IRR or ROI have not been calculated for the baseline because they only have sense when comparing baseline with potential innovations. Regarding the net added value, this indicator will be assessed as a part of the circularity framework.

8.4 Social assessment

Unlike the other CIRC-PACK value chains, CRF dissemination activities mainly target suppliers and does not rely on social media tools. Modifications in production lines are expected to demand two current skilled employees developing new tasks in new positions. Hence, specific training for these workers developing in new positions is planned (300 hours/year) and specific training for those whose task does not change (40 hours/year). On the other hand, air ducts and bumpers production lines that currently use 100% virgin raw materials, will test the inclusion of 10% of recycled materials from own process and 10% recycled from supplier. Table 34 summarizes current situation of corresponding social indicators defined in previous stages.

Table 34. Plastic automotive components social reference point

Partner	CRF	CRF
Task/ Role	Bumpers and ducts manufacturing	Bumpers and air ducts disposal and recycling
N° employees in the company	800	800
1. Equal opportunities/discrimination (gender issues)		
Male/female rates within workforce in the chain	Male: 80% Female: 20%	Male: 80% Female: 20%
Preference for positions	Indifferent	Indifferent
2. Training and education		
Is workflow process modified by innovations?	No	No
Training for workers in the chain	150 hours/yr	150 hours/yr

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Training programme	Yes	Yes
3. Workers' health and safety		
Do innovations involve or increase risks?	No	No
Average lost days per worker/year in the chain for health and safety reason	6 days/yr	6 days/yr
Safety trainee	40 hours/yr (Personal protective equipment use, fire)	40 hours/yr (Personal protective equipment use, fire)
Protective equipment availability in the chain	Yes	Yes
Severe accidents in the chain	0 accidents/yr	0 accidents/yr
4. Consumers' health and safety		
Information/Signs available regarding features	Yes	Yes
Storage conditions	Yes	Yes
5. End-of-life responsibility		
Clear information on EOL options	No. Shredder task	No. Disposal not performed today
Impact on waste management	Same	Same
6. Consumers' well being		
Quality expectation/ Performance and usability	Same	Same
User friendliness/ Convenience and acceptance	Better	Better
7. Community access to material resources		
Certified environmental management system	Yes	Yes
Current materials origin in the chain	100% Virgin 0% Recycled	100% Virgin 0% Recycled
8. Safe and healthy living conditions		
Corporate social responsibility policy	Yes	Yes
Management effort to minimize use of hazardous substances	No hazardous substances use	No hazardous substances use
9. Local employment		
Workforce hired locally	1	1
Local suppliers	1	1
10. Community engagement		
Annual events/Workshops organized/participating locally	50 events/yr	50 events/yr
Impact in social media	No participation	No participation
11. Technology development		
Previous involvement in technology transfer program or projects	Yes	Yes
Investment in technology development	15,000,000 €/yr	15,000,000 €/yr
12. Suppliers relationships		

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Seal of quality/Management system required for suppliers	No	No
Suppliers from countries with high estimated proportion of population in modern slavery	0%	0%

8.5 Circularity assessment

This value chain assesses the impact of using higher shares of recycled plastic materials for industrial applications, in particular car bumpers and air conditioning ducts by CRF. Plastic wastes come from plastic production scrap (76%) and from components failure in the assembly line (24%). In this value chain, CRF collects scrap and sells it to external compounders that grind down and re-granulate it to become new raw material. The amount of raw materials from recycled sources that is used in CRF's products is considered null, and hence, the process, as it is today, has a low level of circularity. The project innovation consists indeed in introducing growing amounts of recycled materials in the production of car bumpers and car air ducts.

The total annual material consumption is mainly virgin polypropylene. Rejection rate is estimated to be 28%. All of it is collected internally and sent to external recyclers. The assumption is that final product, which makes part of a vehicle, is not recovered and becomes end user waste. Recycling efficiency is not known and it is assumed 100%.

The net added value comes from the net sales of the plastic scrap to the recycler, at a price of 0.53 €/kg minus transport costs, resulting in a net benefit of 0.485 €/kg of scrap, or 0.14 €/kg of product sold. Handling costs are low since there is no specific equipment involved in the treatment of the scrap. For a future scenario, the company is analysing the possibility of purchasing grinding units to reduce the transport costs to external compounders, and even a re-granulating machine to be able to use the recycled plastic straight into the own production line, reducing the purchase of virgin material.

The circularity indicators of today's process show a full linearity, and a null circularity index. This later could be improved by feeding the production system with a percentage of pre-treated wastes.

Table 35. Circularity assessment for car plastic component recyclability (CRF)

Indicator	units	relative
Virgin raw material	%	128
Product mass (w primary packaging)	%	100
Resource longevity	time / cycles	1
Value based Resource efficiency	%	9
Linear flow index	%	114
Material circularity index	%	0
End-of-life recycling input rates	%	0
Circular material use rate (CMU)	%	0
Degradation rate	%	0
Compostable rate	%	0
Wastes	%	100.00

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Utility factor		0.90
Utility		1.00

If all the scrap was fed back into the process, the MCI would go up to 10% but the process would still be linear. Improvements on end-of-life recycling input rates and material use rate could also be expected (22%) Further circularity should be sought in the recycling of the end user wastes by sorting out the different materials of used vehicles at the end of life.

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9 COFFEE CAPSULES VALUE CHAIN

9.1 Value chain description

Different formats have been developed for coffee capsules and pods. From single-use coffee capsules to reusable coffee capsules which can reduce packaging consumption up to 85%. Both (single-use and reusable capsules) can be made of different materials such as plastic (namely PP), paper or steel. Therefore, two different factors are affecting the environmental impact of this packaging product. On one hand, the type of use (single-use vs reusable capsules); on the other hand, the material used for its manufacturing. Environmental impact of single-use coffee capsules based on different materials such as aluminium, fossil plastics and biodegradable plastics has been already been compared in the literature [23 - 26]. CIRC-PACK project is focused on the particular case of **single-use coffee capsules**, which are currently **based on fossil plastics** and will be based on biobased plastic (NOVAMONT) after implementing CIRC-PACK innovations. No recycling is considered in this case because the use of recycled material is limited in food contact applications.

Figure 33. Different packaging formats for coffee capsules packaging (extracted from [28])

Since the assessment is only focused on single-use coffee capsules, no inputs/outputs are associated with this phase for the environmental LCA.

Regarding the EoL, coffee capsules cannot be recycled with any of their streams obtained in packaging sorting facilities (neither with plastics nor with aluminium) because of their heterogeneous composition. Actually, most European countries do not include these products in their selective collection and sorting scheme for packaging wastes. As alternative, some private entities (mainly coffee capsules suppliers) promote their collection and recycling. According to companies, a collection rate up to 80-90% can be achieved for these products, and the aim is to get 100% in 2020 [29]. Therefore, a 100% collection has been considered for a better correlation between the type of packaging and the environmental impact.

The recycling process differs depending on the material. For plastic coffee capsules, mechanical recycling of plastic material is the most common procedure. Nevertheless, these multilayer materials are often not interesting for recycling due to their heterogeneity (polymers used for barrier properties such as EVOH and polyamide can affect to properties of recycled materials). For aluminium capsules, recycling process consists on energy

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valorization of organic components (plastic film and binder) and subsequent recovery of aluminium foil.

In any case, coffee must be washed and removed from the plastic or aluminium and it is usually used for compost. This fact can be considered as the main advantage of biobased and compostable coffee capsules to be implemented during CIRC-PACK project. Since these materials are compostable, the whole waste product (capsules with coffee) can be directly used for compost, avoiding the separation step, which increases economic cost and environmental impact.

The flow-chart of this value chain is represented in Figure 34. Targeted coffee capsules are based on plastic which are produced through injection moulding. After use, they are collected by companies and disposed correspondingly according to their composition.

Figure 34. Flow chart of current state (baseline) for value chain of coffee capsules

9.2 Environmental assessment

Different assessment have been performed using ReCiPe and CED characterization methods. The evaluations has been done for one unit of 1,5 g unitary weight comprising 6,7 gr of coffee. According to literature, a significant impact for single-serve coffee capsules is associated with coffee cultivation [30]. Significant impact are also related with use-phase, due to low efficiency of machines and overconsumption of coffee [25]. In order to have a more detailed comparison for different packaging types, efficiency of the machines has been left out of the scope. The LCA has been focused only on the manufacturing (including materials) of coffee capsules and their EoL (composting for coffee and mechanical recycling for plastic capsules).

In the first analysis, it has been compared the relative contribution of different inputs (raw materials, production process and EoL). For this analysis, landfill has been considered as EoL for both materials (coffee can capsule). As it can be seen in Figure 35, main contribution is ascribed to coffee production, whose EoL has also relevant impact in global warming indicator. The highest contribution for capsule is observed in human non-carcinogenic toxicity because of the landfilling of the capsule.

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Figure 35. Distribution of overall environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for different inputs/outputs of coffee capsules (per unit) considering landfill as EoL.

In a second analysis, it has been considered incineration as EoL for plastic capsule and coffee in order to evaluate the influence of the EoL. It can be seen that the contribution of coffee EoL to global warming and the contribution of capsule EoL to human non-carcinogenic toxicity are lower for incineration. These results are represented in

Figure 36.

Figure 36. Distribution of overall environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for different inputs/outputs of coffee capsules (per unit) considering landfill as EoL

Results using CED characterization method are shown in Table 36. As in the evaluation with ReCiPe indicators, production of coffee has the higher impact. Nevertheless, the capsule is the second input in this case, with 20% over the whole energy demand (including the production of PP and its processing to manufacture the capsule). As it was observed for ReCiPe indicators, incineration has lower environmental impact than landfill for CED indicators.

Table 36. Cumulative Energy Demand for different inputs/outputs of coffee capsule (per unit)

Cumulative Energy Demand for coffee capsule with coffee (per unit)			
Coffee production	0,599	Coffee to landfill	0,011
PP production	0,113	Capsule to landfill	0,0004
Capsule production	0,037	Coffee to incineration	0,002
		Capsule to incineration	0,0002

It has been also compared the effect of recycling the capsules, and compared with previous EoL scenarios (landfill and incineration). Results are represented in Figure 37 for comparison of different EoL (incineration, landfill and recycling). It can be seen that recycling of plastic capsule lead to savings in some indicators such as global warming, fossil resources scarcity and ozone formation/depletion.

Figure 37. Environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for capsules without coffee (per unit) with different EoL scenarios

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When using CED characterization method (Table 37), it can be seen that incineration and landfill has higher energy consumption. Savings around 0,1 MJ per unit are obtained through recycling of the capsules, mainly because of PP recycling and the avoided virgin materials [3, 22] .

Table 37. Cumulative Energy Demand for coffee capsules (per unit) with different EoL scenarios

Cumulative Energy Demand for EoL scenarios of car component (per kg)					
Incineration		Landfill		Recycling	
Capsule	0,154	Capsule	0,154	Capsule	0,052

9.3 Economic assessment

Due to confidentiality issues, the costs related to the manufacturing of coffee capsules could not be collected. In addition, as bibliography analysis revealed high variability of economic data, the estimation of theoretical cost was considered inaccurate. Therefore, this assessment was not applied to this value chain.

9.4 Social assessment

Currently, NOVAMONT does not manufacture coffee capsules. Hence, there is no workflow or process modified to become the reference point. Specific assessment will be needed among Task 2.4 in order to evaluate social commitment. Table 38 collects available data related to stakeholders involved in this value chain.

Table 38. Coffee capsules social reference point

Partner	NOVAMONT	NOVAMONT
Task/ Role	Coffee capsule manufacture	Coffee packaging
N° employees in the company	273	273
1. Equal opportunities/discrimination (gender issues)		
Male/female rates within workforce in the chain	Male: 0% Female: 0%	Male: 0% Female: 0%
Preference for positions	N/A	N/A
2. Training and education		
Is workflow process modified by innovations?	N/A	N/A
Training for workers in the chain	N/A	N/A
Training programme	Yes	Yes
3. Workers' health and safety		
Do innovations involve or increase risks?	N/A	N/A
Average lost days per worker/year in the chain for health and safety reason	N/A	N/A
Safety trainee	N/A	N/A

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Protective equipment availability in the chain	N/A	N/A
Severe accidents in the chain	N/A	N/A
4. Consumers' health and safety		
Information/Signs available regarding features	No	No
Storage conditions	Yes. Store Mater-Bi® in a cool and dry warehouse, sealed in its original packaging, away from heat and light. Novamont recommends to convert Mater-Bi® within 6 (six) months from the delivery date.	N/A
5. End-of-life responsibility		
Clear information on EOL options	Yes. EOL disposal info is reported for the end product	Yes. EOL disposal info is reported for the end product
Impact on domestic waste management	Easier	Easier
6. Consumers' well being		
Quality expectation/ Performance and usability	Better	Better
User friendliness/ Convenience and acceptance	Better	Better
7. Community access to material resources		
Certified environmental management system	Yes. ISCC Plus, eLabel	Yes. ISCC Plus, eLabel
Current materials origin in the chain	N/A	N/A
8. Safe and healthy living conditions		
Corporate social responsibility policy	Yes	Yes
Management effort to minimize use of hazardous substances	N/A	N/A
9. Local employment		
Workforce hired locally	N/A	N/A
Local suppliers	N/A	N/A
10. Community engagement		
Annual events/Workshops organized/participating locally	4-5 events (Ecomondo, K 2016, Novara Jazz and Fa' La Cosa Giusta)	4-5 events (Ecomondo, K 2016, Novara Jazz and Fa' La Cosa Giusta)
Impact in social media	528,352 views on Twitter, 1,798 likes on Facebook	528,352 views on Twitter, 1,798 likes on Facebook
11. Technology development		
Previous involvement in technology transfer program or projects	Yes	Yes
Investment in technology development	7% turnover	7% turnover
12. Suppliers relationships		

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Seal of quality/Management system required for suppliers	Yes. (ISCC- renewable raw materials)	Yes. (ISCC- renewable raw materials)
Suppliers from countries with high estimated proportion of population in modern slavery	N/A	N/A

9.5 Circularity assessment

The use of coffee capsules is becoming increasingly popular nowadays due to simplicity and convenience of this clean and fast coffee making system. However, it is highly pollutant due to the material wastes that it generates, aggravated by the fact that there is not a waste recovery system for this kind of materials.

The circularity assessment is made over one single coffee capsule that is made up of 6.7 grams of grinded coffee and 1.5 grams of PP plastic capsule. 3 grams of printed non-recycled cardboard is assigned to every capsule that goes in the box. The total capsule weight is assumed to be 11.2 g, and the capsule itself is 8.2 g. No recycled materials are used for the manufacturing of each capsule. In all cases, it is assumed a 90% collection rate for the cardboard box, which is sorted out with a 96% efficiency. For different capsule collection rates we assume that coffee is both biodegradable and compostable and the PP capsule is theoretically recyclable but, de facto, they not due to techno-economic constraints. No capsule reuse is considered although this is a possibility just replacing the coffee and the sealing of the used capsule.

We consider several capsule collection rate scenarios, starting from 0%, actual case, up to a 100% hypothetical best case, to check how much progress can be obtained from an increasing collection effort. In all cases, cardboard box recycling rate is 86.4%, from end user. The mass inventory in grams per capsule for the different recovery rates is available in the following table.

Table 39. Coffee capsules mass inventory for different recovery rates.

Value chain 1, DC-A, coffee capsules for different recovery rates				
material in gr /unit	0%	25%	50%	100%
Virgin material	11.2	11.2	11.2	11.2
Product material	11.2	11.2	11.2	11.2
User mat to recycle	2.7	4.3	6.8	10.9
Mfg mat to recycle	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Recycled mat for mfg	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Wastes from end user	8.5	6.9	4.4	0.3
Wastes from mfg	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Wastes from rec/sorting	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11
Biodegradable wastes	0.0	1.3	3.4	6.7
Compostable wastes	0.0	1.3	3.4	6.7

For each scenario, the main circularity indicators are calculated in the table below.

Table 40. Coffee capsules circularity assessment for different recovery rates.

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Value chain 1, DC-A, coffee capsules (NOVAMONT) for different recovery rates				
indicator	0%	25%	50%	100%
Linear flow index (LFI)	88.0%	80.7%	69.7%	51.5%
Material circularity index (MCI)	20.8%	27.4%	37.3%	53.7%
End-of-life recycling input rates	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Circular material use rate (CMU)	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Degradation rate	0.0%	12.0%	29.9%	59.8%
Compostable rate	0.0%	12.0%	29.9%	59.8%
Wastes vs virgin materials	76.4%	61.7%	39.8%	3.2%

Higher circularity rates could be attained by using recycled materials. In the case of capsules manufactured with biodegradable materials, degradation rates will increase regardless of the recovery rate scenario, which seems a clearer and simpler path forward for the wastes generated in this value chain, as it would turn the full product (except a share of the cardboard box) into biodegradable and, maybe, compostable.

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10 ABSORBENT HYGIENE PRODUCTS (AHPs) VALUE CHAIN

10.1 Value chain description

Absorbent Hygiene Products (AHP products) are normally composed of different materials. The absorbent part is based on a Super-Absorbent Polymer (SAP), which is encapsulated by a non-woven or cellulose material. This piece is attached to a backing layer where are placed the fixtures (in case there are). This backing layer and fixtures are based on different plastic materials such as PP or PE. All these components are produced separately and assembled in the manufacturing line. Afterwards, they are packaged for distribution. Since, CIRC-PACK innovations are focused on materials for packaging, LCA assessment has been focused on in these packaging items, leaving out of the scope the manufacturing of the AHP. These materials are being currently manufactured using viring plastic materials (PE film, PP boxes) or wood (mini-pallets). After innovations, these items will be based either on bio-based polymers (PE film) or recycled plastic materials (PP boxes and PP mini-pallets).

The flow chart of the AHPs value chain is represented in Figure 38, from raw materials to EoL.

Figure 38. Flow chart of AHPs value chain

CIRC-PACK innovations will be focused on three different packaging products:

- **Secondary packaging of AHPs:** current PE film will be substituted by bio-based and biodegradable plastic bag.
- **Plastic boxes used as tertiary packaging of diapers:** they are currently based on virgin PP that be substituted by recycled plastic materials.
- **Mini-pallets for product distribution:** they are currently based on wood and they will be substituted by mini-pallets manufactured with recycled plastic materials.

For the baseline, it will be evaluated the environmental impact of current packaging formats depending on their EoL scenario (recycling vs landfill vs incineration).

On the other hand, FATER is currently recycling waste of post-consumer AHP waste. Three different fractions are obtained as output of the process: cellulose, SAP and plastic.

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Cellulose will be used during innovations as raw material for biobased polymers manufactured by NOVAMONT. On the other hand, recyclability of plastic fraction for different applications will be investigated by AITIP.

Recycling process has associated several inputs such as electricity, steam...that should be compensated by the use of the recycled fraction in different applications (avoiding therefore consumption of other materials). The use of recycled materials will be developed within innovations and will be analysed in task 2.4. Therefore, different EoL scenarios of post-consumer AHP waste will be analysed in task 2.4. In this task (T2.3), it has been analysed relative contribution of different inputs/outputs of the recycling process carried out by FATER.

Figure 39 shows the flow chart of the recycling process.

Figure 39. Flow chart of AHP wastes recycling process

10.2 Environmental assessment

In a first analysis, the impact of different EoL for PE film used as tertiary packaging of AHPs has been evaluated.

Results obtained by using ReCiPe characterization method are represented in Figure 40 for a PE film of 3,2 gr unitary weight. As it can be seen in the graph, recycling leads to lower environmental impact in most of the indicators but some of them such as ionizing radiation, stratospheric ozone depletion or freshwater eutrophication have higher impact due to the consumption of electricity during recycling process.

Figure 40. Environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for PE film used as secondary packaging for AHPs (per unit) with different EoL scenarios

When using CED characterization method (Table 41), savings close to 0,5 MJ per unit of tertiary packaging can be achieved by recycling. This is due to the avoided virgin material [3, 22].

Table 41. Cumulative Energy Demand for PE film used as secondary packaging for AHPs (per unit) with different EoL scenarios

Cumulative Energy Demand for EoL scenarios of AHPs tertiary packaging (per unit)					
Incineration	0,294	Landfill	0,293	Recycling	0,069

In a second analysis, different EoL scenarios have been evaluated for plastic boxes used as tertiary packaging of diapers. Results obtained with ReCiPe characterization are represented in Figure 41 for one box of 2 kg unitary weight. It can be seen in the graph that recycling lead to significant savings in many different indicators. Especially in those related with fossil resources scarcity, global warming and toxicity related indicators. On the other hand, recycling has higher impact in freshwater eutrophication, ionizing radiation and stratospheric ozone depletion because of the consumption of energy (electricity) for recycling.

Figure 41. Environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for plastic box used as tertiary packaging for diapers (per unit) with different EoL scenarios

When using CED characterization method (Table 42), savings around 288 MJ per box can be obtained through recycling [3, 22]. Savings are significantly higher than those obtained per unit of PE film packaging because of weight (2 kg per box compared with 3,2 gr per film unit). If we compared savings per gram of material, they are similar in both cases (around 0,15 MJ).

Table 42. Cumulative Energy Demand for plastic box used as tertiary packaging for diapers (per unit) with different EoL scenarios

Cumulative Energy Demand for EoL scenarios of a plastic box used as tertiary packaging of diapers (per unit)					
Incineration	205,140	Landfill	205,149	Recycling	69,350

A similar analysis has been carried out for mini-pallets used for distribution of AHPs. In this case, recycling of wood has not been considered as EoL since wood cannot be recycled as plastic materials. Results are represented in Figure 42 for one mini-pallet of 0,75 kg unitary weight. As it can see in the graph, there is higher impact for landfilling in global warming, marine and freshwater ecotoxicity, human non-carcinogenic ecotoxicity and in marine eutrophication (having the latter the highest difference). On the rest of indicators, incineration has higher environmental impact in ozone depletion and ozone formation. In the rest of indicators there are minor differences between two scenarios.

Figure 42. Environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for mini-pallets used for distribution of AHPs (per unit) with different EoL scenarios

When using CED characterization method, overall required energy is similar for both scenarios as it can be seen in Table 43.

Table 43. Cumulative Energy Demand for mini-pallets used for distribution of AHPs (per unit) with different EoL scenarios

Cumulative Energy Demand for EoL scenarios of a mini-pallet used for distribution of AHPs (per unit)			
Incineration	21,834	Landfill	21,952

As it has been commented before, an additional analysis has been made to evaluate relative impacts of different inputs/outputs associated with the recycling process of AHP wastes. Main inputs are electricity, fuel for boiler and steam. Regarding the outputs, wastewater is generated as an output of the process.

Results are represented in Figure 43. It can be seen that energy (fuel and electricity) has the highest contribution with more than 80% in most of the indicators. Fuel has higher contribution in ozone depletion and formation, terrestrial acidification, particle formation, fossil resource scarcity and mineral resource scarcity. On the other hand, electricity has major contribution in ionizing radiation and toxicity related indicators. Wastewater has negative impact in water consumption because of the release of water. However, this water is contaminated and has significant impact in marine eutrophication.

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Figure 43. Distribution of overall environmental impact (ReCiPe indicators) for different inputs/outputs of AHP wastes recycling process (per kg)

Results using CED characterization method are shown in Table 44. The highest contribution to CED is related to fuel consumption in boiler, with around 70%.

Table 44. Cumulative Energy Demand for different inputs/outputs of AHP wastes recycling process (per kg)

Cumulative Energy Demand for different inputs/outputs of AHP wastes recycling process (per kg)			
Electricity	4,857	Fuel	17,672
Steam	2,992	Wastewater	0,020

10.3 Economic assessment

Information has been collected about different costs in packaging of AHPs to analyse their contribution. It has been distinguished among CAPEX and OPEX. A similar assessment has been done for the AHP waste recycling process.

In Figure 44 it can be seen the yearly consumption (weight) and the yearly cost for different packaging items (PE film, plastic box and mini-pallets). It can be seen that the highest consumed weight correspond for plastic boxes (with 4 kg unitary weight), then for mini-pallets (0,75 kg unitary weight) and finally for PE film (3,2 gr unitary weight). On the other

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hand, PE film has similar contribution to cost than wood mini-pallets, which much lower weight consumption because of the higher price.

Figure 44. Yearly cost for different packaging items in FATER facilities

Regarding the recycling process, it can be seen in Figure 45, that main contribution is attributed to OPEX with 85% of overall cost.

Figure 45. Contribution of different cost categories for AHP wastes recycling process

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Finally, it is worth to mention that other indicators such as NPV, IRR or ROI have not been calculated for the baseline because they only have sense when comparing baseline with potential innovations. Regarding the net added value, this indicator will be assessed as a part of the circularity framework.

10.4 Social assessment

Although AHP value chain's results are presented on the same table (Table 45), different types of packaging belong to diverse product typologies and so, results may not be aggregated. In addition, in this particular case, although FATER applies innovations to its products, packaging is developed by subcontractors and suppliers. In addition, innovative activity will take place in a pilot plant.

Table 45. Absorbent Hygiene Products social reference point

Partner	MI-PLAST	FATER	FATER	FATER
Task/ Role	Film manufacturing	Film (Feminine AHP packaging)	Box (Pampers secondary packaging)	Mini-pallet (Tertiary packaging)
N° employees in the company	12	1,600	1,600	1,600
1. Equal opportunities/discrimination (gender issues)				
Male/female rates within workforce in the chain	Male: 45% Female: 55%	Supplier ¹⁴	Supplier	Supplier
Preference for positions	Indifferent	Supplier	Supplier	Supplier
2. Training and education				
Is workflow process modified by innovations?	Yes	Supplier	Supplier	Supplier
Training for workers in the chain	240 hours/yr	Supplier	Supplier	Supplier
Training programme	Yes	Supplier	Supplier	Supplier
3. Workers' health and safety				
Do innovations involve or increase risks?	No	No	No	No
Average lost days per worker/yr in the chain for health and safety reason	7 days/yr	Supplier	Supplier	Supplier
Safety trainee	180 hours/yr	Supplier	Supplier	Supplier
Protective equipment availability in the chain	Yes. Gloves, respirators, ear-covers.	Yes	Yes	Yes

¹⁴ See MI-PLAST column

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Severe accidents in the chain	0 accidents/yr	Supplier	Supplier	Supplier
4. Consumers' health and safety				
Information/Signs available regarding features	No	Yes. Specific labelling for EOL	Yes. Specific labelling for EOL	No
Storage conditions	None	Yes. Humidity	No	Yes. Mechanical resistance
5. End-of-life responsibility				
Clear information on EOL options	No	Yes. Specific labelling for EOL	Yes. Specific labelling for EOL	No
Impact on domestic waste management	More difficult	Easier	Same	Easier
6. Consumers' well being				
Quality expectation/ Performance and usability	Same	Better	Better	Better
User friendliness/ Convenience and acceptance	Better	Same	Same	Better
7. Community access to material resources				
Certified environmental management system	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Current materials origin in the chain	30 % Virgin 70 % Recycled	100% virgin	100% virgin	100% virgin
8. Safe and healthy living conditions				
Corporate social responsibility policy	Yes	No	No	No
Management effort to minimize use of hazardous substances	No hazardous substances use	No hazardous substances use	No hazardous substances use	No hazardous substances use
9. Local employment				
Workforce hired locally	100%	Supplier	Supplier	Supplier
Local suppliers	70%	Supplier	Supplier	Supplier
10. Community engagement				
Annual events/Workshops organized/ participating locally	3 events/yr	>20 events/yr	>20 events/yr	>20 events/yr
Impact in social media	No current participation	Depends on campaign	Depends on campaign	Depends on campaign
11. Technology development				
Previous involvement in technology transfer program or projects	Yes	Supplier	Supplier	Supplier
Investment in technology development	100,000 €/yr	Supplier	Supplier	Supplier

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12. Suppliers relationships				
Seal of quality/Management system required for suppliers	Yes	N/A	N/A	N/A
Suppliers from countries with high estimated proportion of population in modern slavery	0%	Supplier	Supplier	Supplier

10.5 Circularity assessment

The value chain of highly impacting everyday multi-material products is represented by the feminine absorbent pads manufactured by FATER. Only the mass flows are calculated for this product, whose estimated annual production is 7 million units per year, each unit consisting on a PE bag 40 micron thick, enclosing 10 absorbent pads. PE bags involve the use of a certain amount of PE, half of which, comes from recycled sources following the same manufacturing process described for the 50 micron thick MIPLAST's bags. The film collection rate is just 9.7%, and the sorting efficiency of the collected film is 72.3%.

FATER has an innovative line that is capable to recycle 10,000 tons of AHP products per year, separating the components and obtaining 15% of recycled cellulose, 7.5% of recycled SAP and 7.5% of recycled plastic. The total share of recycled materials is 30% over the overall AHP waste. Specific collection campaigns are made involving hospitals, kindergartens, geriatric centres, etc. to obtain 1.1% of the estimated AHP wastes in Italy. Applying this collection rate to the Petalo Blu line 1.1% of feminine pads could be recycled at FATER's facilities.

The relative mass inventory of this product line is in the table below.

Table 46. Mass flow inventory for feminin AH pads in bags (FATER)

material	Product g/unit	Packaging g/unit	% of product mass with respect to M	% of packaging with respect to of M
Virging material	201.60	1.60	99%	50%
Product material	203.20	3.20	100%	100%
User mat to recycle	2.53	0.31	1%	10%
Mfg mat to recycle	0.00	0.00	0%	0%
Recycled mat for mfg	1.60	1.60	1%	50%
Wastes from end user	200.67	2.89	99%	90%
Wastes from mfg	0.00	0.00	0%	0%
Wastes from rec/sorting	1.64	0.09	1%	3%
Biodegradable wastes	0.00	0.00	0%	0%
Compostable wastes	0.00	0.00	0%	0%

Applying these values to the circularity metric calculation, the results are as follows.

Table 47. Circularity assessment for feminin AH pads in bags (FATER)

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Indicator	units	relative /M
Virgin raw material	%	99
Product mass (w primary packaging)	%	100
Resource longevity	time / cycles	1
Value based Resource efficiency recycling line	%	
Linear flow index	%	99
Material circularity index	%	11
End-of-life recycling input rates	%	100
Circular material use rate (CMU)	%	50
Degradation rate	%	0.0
Compostable rate	%	0.0
Wastes	%	99.2
Utility factor		0.90
Utility		1.00

The utility is one. Despite of the AHP recycling line, the recovery rate is very low to have a significant impact on the linearity of this product line, as it is just a pilot case in Italy, and there is not a real waste recovery channel in place for end users to dispose this type of products. In addition, the material recovered is just 30% and not fed back yet in the AHP production line. Only the bags use recycled materials for production, but in terms of mass is just a 1% of the full product. Using the recycled cellulose in other CIRC-Pack value chain will also help to improve the circularity indexes of the chain where the recycled material is reused. Improvements can also be obtained by means of bio-based plastic materials that would allow considering the full AHP waste as biodegradable.

Having a close look to the packaging flow only (PE bags), the results look better due to the use of recycling PE for the bag manufacturing. The weak point is the low recovery of films from end users.

Table 48. Circularity assessment for feminine AH pads in bags (FATER). Packaging only

Value chain 8, DC-A, feminine AH pads. Packaging only	
Indicator	value
Linear flow index	71.3%
Material circularity index	36%
End-of-life recycling input rates	100%
Circular material use rate (CMU)	50%

Besides PE bags, FATER also use PP plastic boxes (2 kg/box), and wooden mini pallets (0.75 kg/pallet) as diaper packaging. Although the diaper product line is not analysed, these two pieces of packaging make part of the CIRC-Pack innovation solutions and the baseline scenario for this packaging only is assessed in terms of circularity. The ambition is to replace

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the materials by new plastic boxes made of 60% recycled PP and 40% recycled PE. In addition, these packaging are occasionally reused, either as domestic bins or as foundation support for supermarket box display on shelves. We consider a utility 20% higher than the minimum average packaging utility, which is one single use. Boxes are made of virgin PP and the end-user recovery rate is 40%. Wood is considered biodegradable in a medium term, but not recyclable. Manufacturing materials are all virgin materials. The material mass inventory is in the next table.

Table 49. Mass flow inventory for diaper packaging items (FATER)

material	kg/unit
Virging material	1.23
Product material	1.23
User mat to recycle	0.21
Mfg mat to recycle	0.25
Recycled mat for mfg	0.00
Wastes from end user	0.74
Wastes from mfg	0.00
Wastes from rec/sorting	0.06
Biodegradable wastes	0.37
Compostable wastes	0.00

The circularity metric results are shown in the next table.

Table 50. Circularity assessment for diaper packaging items (FATER)

Indicator	units	relative
Virgin raw material	%	100
Product mass (w primary packaging)	%	100
Resource longevity	time / cycles	1.20
Linear flow index	%	80
Material circularity index	%	40
End-of-life recycling input rates	%	0
Circular material use rate (CMU)	%	0
Degradation rate	%	30
Compostable rate	%	0
Wastes	%	62.28
Utility factor		0.75
Utility		1.20

Since 30% of the material is wood, degradation rate is 30%. Due to the higher utility (1.2) and the final sorting of 30% of the PP used, wastes reduce to 62% of the total material usage. This increase the material circularity index to 40%, but the overall linearity is rather high due to a

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lack of recycling materials in the manufacturing process. This is precisely the shortcoming addressed by the CIRC-Pack innovation.

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11 SOCIAL NEEDS AND EXPECTATIONS

Until date, most innovation projects are mainly focused on assessing technical and environmental viability of their proposals. However, CIRC-PACK project intends to include citizen consultations along different stages of the project to ensure final project outcomes have a real chance of success when being introduced on the market. With such activities, social involvement has started at the very beginning of the CIRC-PACK project, instead of just giving end-of-pipe feedback.

To ensure the market acceptance of innovative proposals arising within CIRC-PACK project, we need to count on citizen point of view. As a matter of fact, consumers will decide which proposals will succeed throughout their purchasing choices. Therefore, it is crucial to gather the perception and expectations of consumer opinions, about plastics and plastic packaging, during the baseline exercise. As well as collecting practical information to be considered in the design of the new products during project demo cases, in order to assure the development of not only sustainable but also usable alternatives.

In this sense, a first citizen survey was carried out in six countries (Italy, Belgium, Portugal, Spain, Croatia and Kartal, district of Istanbul, representative region of Turkey with 500.000 inhabitants) to investigate current habits regarding product packaging and when purchasing or segregating domestic waste. Additionally, the survey intended to measure awareness and level of information regarding environmental policies or impact of plastics and plastic packaging. As plastic bags are a hot topic in most of involved countries, a special section of the survey was dedicated on material preferences, current habits and problems, as well as potential acceptance of biodegradable or bio-based alternatives.

Finally, consumers' potential behaviour regarding new plastic materials, such as biobased, recycled or biodegradable packaging materials has been introduced. Acceptance, pricing and information on demo-case products has been investigated as well.

Data allow comparisons across countries, for certain socio-demographic segments within a single country, or related to the demo-cases products within a single country.

The survey concludes that CIRC-PACK innovations can help to address consumers' sustainability needs. Most people agree that current production, use and waste of plastic for domestic use cause pollution problems. Plastic for domestic use is considered a problem for the planet in all countries and it is also considered to use a lot of natural resources. Additionally, environmental aspects exert a moderate influence on the decision of buying everyday products such as food, detergents or hygiene products. Besides, environment is a relevant aspect of packaging that citizens value in all countries, but Croatia and Kartal. Therefore, a more sustainable plastic packaging can be part of a more sustainable consumption.

Since new plastic materials have a very limited market share and there is little available information about their properties, it is understandable that **most of respondents do not consider new plastic materials as a first option when buying most demo-case products**, except in Italia where biodegradable alternatives are the prevalent option. In other countries more than 50% of respondents would prefer conventional options or do not have a clear preference when being asked about the type of packaging they would choose. Information about properties and advantages becomes key for success of these initiatives towards a more sustainable consumption.

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Citizens would clearly **prefer biodegradable options** over bio-based products. The best acceptance for a biodegradable packaging product relates to coffee capsules. There is a willingness to pay a little bit more for these new packaging options, although a significant share of respondents would pay no single amount. The average amount varies across countries but not significantly between products, except for coffee capsules for which people would pay slightly less extra.

The sorting of biodegradable **plastic with bio-waste is not perceived to have a negative impact on the domestic waste management** for most respondents. There is a good level of waste sorting (including plastic fraction) in Belgium, Italy, Portugal and Spain. In Croatia and Kartal sorting scores significantly lower. Main constraints are the inconvenience to have so many waste bins at home and the distance to the bring-points. However, a different sorting for biodegradable packaging does not seem a barrier.

Information has a key role to play but finding trust-inspiring information channels is equally important. Most citizens consider they are not at all or not well informed about new plastic materials, whereas a third of them would like to be informed. Respondents do not trust in information given by manufacturers, supermarkets or media and they have more confidence in environmental and consumer organizations. Public authorities score fairly, especially in Portugal and Kartal. Information needs to be reinforced in order to move citizens into action. Most respondents find it very important having a good ecological behaviour but many of them do not take a lot of actions to put this into practice.

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12 WASTE LEAKAGE AND MARINE IMPLICATIONS

Europe has a coastline of 68000 km and it is encircled by the Mediterranean, Black and Baltic Seas, and the North Atlantic Ocean which also includes the North Sea [31]. Europe's seas has an extensive variety of marine and coastal ecosystems. It varies from the stable environment of the deep ocean to very dynamic coastal waters. Every sea is shared by countless individuals, institutions, cultures and activities. They are also hosting many species of marine plants and animals [32].

Unfortunately, marine litter is a global problem that affects all of the oceans. Every year, millions of tons of garbage leak into the ocean around the world, causing environmental, economic, health and aesthetic problems. Main sources of marine litter are given in Table 51 [33].

Table 51. Main sources of Marine litter (adapted from [33])

Land-based sources	Sea-based sources
Land-fills	Fishing and aquaculture
Rivers and floodwaters	Shipping (e.g. transport, tourism)
Industrial outfalls	Offshore mining and extraction
Discharge from storm water drains	Illegal dumping at sea
Untreated municipal sewerage	
Littering of beaches, coastal areas (tourism)	

On average in the EU, 31.5 kg of plastic packaging waste is generated by a person in a year. In total, EU produces 15.8 million tonnes of plastic packaging waste per year [34]. By using Eurostat data tables and plastic waste leakage rates, which were calculated in D2.2, amounts of municipal waste, generated plastic packaging waste, plastic packaging goes to marine, automotive component waste in marine and generated paper/cardboard waste are listed in Table 52.

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Table 52. Amounts of plastic waste types in marine

EU Countries	2016 Municipal Waste (kg per capita)	Plastic packaging waste generated (kg per capita)	Min. plastic packaging goes to marine (kg per capita)	Max. plastic packaging goes to marine (kg per capita)	Min. automotive component waste in marine (kg per capita)	Max. automotive component waste in marine (kg per capita)	Paper/ cardboard waste generated (kg per capita)
Austria	564	28.6	0.152	0.515	0.008	0.026	61.8
Belgium	420	29.4	0.156	0.529	0.008	0.026	63.5
Bulgaria	404	10.4	0.055	0.188	0.003	0.009	22.5
Croatia	403	12	0.052	0.176	0.003	0.009	21.1
Cyprus	640	16.4	0.087	0.294	0.004	0.015	35.3
Czech Republic	339	19.6	0.104	0.352	0.005	0.018	42.3
Denmark	777	29.4	0.156	0.529	0.008	0.026	63.4
Estonia	376	32.7	0.173	0.588	0.009	0.029	70.5
Finland	504	24.7	0.131	0.445	0.007	0.022	53.3
France	511	35.5	0.188	0.639	0.009	0.032	76.6
Germany	627	42.0	0.222	0.755	0.011	0.038	90.6
Greece	498	13.1	0.069	0.235	0.003	0.012	28.2
Hungary	379	22.4	0.119	0.403	0.006	0.020	48.3
Ireland	-	60	0.210	0.712	0.010	0.036	85.3
Italy	497	38.6	0.204	0.694	0.010	0.035	83.2
Latvia	410	22.5	0.119	0.405	0.006	0.020	48.6
Lithuania	444	23.1	0.122	0.416	0.006	0.021	49.9
Luxembourg	614	39.8	0.211	0.716	0.011	0.036	85.9
Malta	621	24.5	0.130	0.441	0.006	0.022	52.9

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Netherlands	520	33.2	0.176	0.597	0.009	0.030	71.6
Poland	307	25.4	0.135	0.458	0.007	0.023	54.9
Portugal	461	29.1	0.154	0.524	0.008	0.026	62.9
Romania	261	12.0	0.063	0.215	0.003	0.011	25.8
Slovakia	348	17.3	0.092	0.311	0.005	0.016	37.3
Slovenia	466	19.9	0.105	0.358	0.005	0.018	42.9
Spain	443	29.3	0.155	0.527	0.008	0.026	63.2
Sweden	443	21.4	0.114	0.386	0.006	0.019	46.2
United Kingdom	483	33.3	0.177	0.600	0.009	0.030	72.0
EU28	12,760	31.5	0.167	0.567	0.008	0.028	68.0

A relation between value chains and amounts of marine litter types is tried to establish. But specific rates for coffee capsules, bottles and food trays cannot be reached. Plastic packaging waste includes all of them. And also data for biodegradable plastics and absorbent hygienic product waste in marine cannot be reached.

According to Table 52, Germany has the maximum plastic packaging leakage into the marine with maximum 0.755 kg per capita and Croatia has the minimum plastic packaging leakage into the marine with 0.176 kg per capita.

Since high amounts of plastic waste leaks into the ocean, marine life is affected hazardously. Hazards of plastic waste to marine life can be analyzed in three groups, environmental damage, economic costs, wildlife entanglement and ingestion [35].

For environmental damage, Scottish Government said that "As a result of the existence of marine litter, there are a wide variety of short and long term adverse environmental effects on individual organisms, species and ecosystems as a whole. Marine litter damages benthic environments, causes biodiversity loss, and causes a reduction in overall ecosystem function[36]."

For economic costs, marine litter is a serious non-point source pollution problem that is pervasive, and impacts users of the marine in several ways. Of these, the direct impacts are the most obvious, from local authorities responsible for clean-up activities, the loss of tourism expenditure or shifts in tourism activity, and the loss of vessel activity as a result of propeller fouling or bringing up litter in fishing nets. Indirect impacts can also be substantial and occur from a decline in the environmental quality of the coast that can cause losses in amenity and resulting losses in property values, opportunity costs and civic pride [36].

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Entanglement by items such as fishing nets and line, lures, light sticks, crab/lobster/fish traps, plastic bags, strapping bands and four/six pack yokes pose a significant risk to marine organisms. These items are responsible for an estimated 62% of all entanglements and can reduce movement, cause injury and in some cases death from starvation, drowning or suffocation [35].

An estimated 136 species of marine vertebrate and 8 invertebrate species have been reported entangled in marine litter including six turtle species, 11 cetacean species, 19 pinniped species, 51 seabird species and 34 fish species and entanglement along with other ecological impacts of marine litter hinder conservation efforts, accounting for a high proportion of mortality rates in endangered species [35].

Ingestion is one of the main impacts on marine wildlife. It is estimated that 177 marine species have ingested litter items which include whole plastic bags, gallon drums and balloons, mistakenly identified as food by mammal, turtle and shark species. Resin pellets, convenience food packaging and plastic bags are among some of the litter ingested by birds, marine mammals and sea turtles which are particularly susceptible to floating plastic bags, mistaking them for jellyfish [35].

13 RESULTS INTERPRETATION AND INDICATORS RANKING

13.1 Ranking Approach

As an important part of sustainable value chain creation and monitoring, the CIRC-PACK Project aims to deliver a framework for ranking and prioritization of indicators spanning environmental, economic and social themes. Currently the CEIS of CIRC-PACK includes (i) 19 life cycle impact indicators, (ii) 9 life cycle inventory indicators, (iii) 8 economic indicators, (iv) 7 circularity indicators, and (v) 29 social indicators under 12 sub-categories. In the case of trade-offs concerning indicators of the same theme or cross-themes, it is an asset to provide the decision makers and other involved stakeholders a means to prioritize the indicator data. For this purpose, as reported in *D2.2: Methodology for CIRC-PACK Value Chain Evaluations*, Analytical Hierarchy Process (ANP), which is a Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) tool, is being utilized to evaluate the significance/importance of indicators for value chain stakeholders.

The ANP method relies on the identification of dependencies between goals, criteria and alternatives in a network structure (Figure 46) and pair-wise comparison of alternatives between each other according to the set of criteria and the dependencies among them. The pair-wise comparisons are made according to a pre-set scheme shown in

Table 53.

Figure 46. Hierarchy and network structure under ANP (Adapted from [36])

Table 53. Scales of relative importance in AH process *¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..*

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Intensity of importance	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	Two activities contribute equally to the objectives
3	Weak importance	Experience and judgement slightly favor one alternative above the other
5	Essential or strong importance	Experience and judgement strongly favor one activity over another
7	Demonstrated importance	An activity is strongly favoured and its dominance demonstrated in practice
9	Absolute importance	The evidence favouring one activity over another is the highest possible order of affirmation
2,4,6,8	Intermediate values between the two adjacent judgements	Where compromise is needed
Reciprocals of the non-zero	Each score above assigned to activity i in comparison to activity j has a reciprocal value for activity j when compared to activity i.	

As earlier applications demonstrate, ANP offers ability to support selection, prioritization and aggregation of indicators based on different criteria and stakeholder preferences. Integration of ANP with indicators allows CEIS to offer a methodological approach for implementation on various value chains, improving its added-value and replicability. The proposed framework is presented in Figure 47, already shown in D2.2: Methodology for CIRC-PACK Value Chain Evaluations,

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Figure 47. The methodological approach for implementation of CEIS

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The proposed framework has two main outcomes;

- 1) Determination to headline indicators
- 2) Weighing of indicators in order to reach single scores – optional at this time for CIRC-PACK

The process is initiated with selection of generic list of indicators as done in *D2.2: Methodology for CIRC-PACK Value Chain Evaluations*. Next the evaluation criteria is selected as follows:

- o *Social indicators:*
Evaluation is done through the social indicators survey (Please see D2.2 for details).
 - o Influence on stakeholders' perceptions of the product
 - o Significance for the business
- o *Environmental indicators:*
Evaluation is done using the partners' survey on environmental indicators as well as RACER evaluation of them.
 - o Significance for the business
 - o Significance for society
 - o Effect on consumer perception of the product
 - o Competitive advantage
 - o Potential for benchmarking
 - o Ease of communication with stakeholders
 - o RACER: Relevant – Attainable – Credible – Easy – Robust
- o *Economic indicators:*
Evaluation is done using partners' survey on economic indicators
 - o Significance for taking an investment decision
 - o Importance for setting the price of a product
 - o Usefulness for indicating benefits as well as costs
 - o Potential for benchmarking
- o *Life cycle indicators:*
The basis for evaluating the life cycle indicators are determined as
 - o Inclusion of life cycle indicators in the Product Category Rules (PCR) documents and
 - o Monetization of life cycle impacts per unit.

Following selection of the criteria, it is possible to set different significance levels for each criterion. For the purpose of CIRC-PACK analyses, all criteria is assumed to have same significance.

Next stage is the pair-wise comparison of indicators according the set criteria above in order to establish priority indicators i.e. headline indicators for each value chain. For social indicator set, the survey is applied to all value chain stakeholders. For environmental indicator set, representative surveys were obtained from three stakeholder groups (i) manufacturers (represented by Bumaga), (ii) end-of-life operators (represented by Ecoembes), and (iii) consumers (represented by KARTAL MUN). The latter is valid for economic indicators. The RACER evaluations and PCR content check for life cycle impact indicators originate from the literature.

In order to create the ANP networks and carry out the ranking analysis, Super Decisions Software was utilized **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..** The conceptual

network for social indicators with regards to biodegradable polymers and the network created on Super Decisions software are shown in Figure 48.

Figure 48 Conceptual (a) and software (b) ANP networks for biodegradable polymers value chain

Upon creation of the network it is necessary to provide the pair-wise comparisons as an input for analysis. Figure 49 shows an example of social indicator comparisons for biopolymer value chain. The qualitative survey results on social indicators, seen in the upper part of the chart, is converted to quantitative values in Super Decisions software by assigning values for qualitative levels of “low”, “medium” and “high” used in the survey. The quantification is carried out according to the comparison system presented in

Table 53 and

Table 54 (social indicators). During this process, the inconsistency ratio was kept below 0.1.

The results of the ANP analysis includes the **ranking of the indicators** in the light of prioritization criteria as well as **weights that can be assigned to each alternative** if obtaining a single score is desired. As a rule of thumb, a combination of ranking and weighing is used for selection of headline indicator set for each theme. For social indicators, top five ranking indicator sub-categories are deemed to have the highest relevance for each value chain. Among the bottom ranking indicator sub-groups, the ones with weights lower than 5% are categorized as indicators with low relevance for the value chains.

An optional aspect of this framework is its ability to compare the importance of environmental, economic, social and circularity themes with each other in the eyes of stakeholders or on the basis of different value chains. If a value chain is associated with unfair labor for instance or consumption of highly polluting chemicals, social and environmental scores respectively, can be more critical piece of information for the stakeholders.

The final step is to obtain a single CEIS score for the value chains. Under this single score, the importance of indicators, indicator values (results) and dominance of themes are all factored in so as to reach a single normalized value solely to be used for comparison and benchmarking purposes. This single score is only aimed to communicate CEIS results in a simple and concise way to different stakeholder groups.

Figure 49 The conversion of social indicator survey results into ANP pair-wise comparisons

Table 54 Quantification of qualitative social, environmental and economic indicator survey results (with consistency index < 0.1)

	Low	Medium	High
Low	1	+5	+9
Medium	-5	1	-5
High	-9	-5	1

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Table 55 Quantification of RACER evaluation results (with consistency index < 0.1)

	Criterion not fulfilled	Criterion partially fulfilled	Criterion completely fulfilled
Criterion not fulfilled	1	+5	+9
Criterion partially fulfilled	-5	1	-5
Criterion completely fulfilled	-9	-5	1

13.2 Evaluation of social indicators

In Table 56, the results of the ANP analyses for social indicators are shown. In this table, the headline indicators are presented in green with their ranks from 1 – 5. Furthermore, indicator sub-groups with low relevance are indicated with grey shading.

Overall assessment of results suggest that **end-of-life responsibility, consumers' health and safety** and **technology development** are considered to be highly significant by the value chain stakeholders. In fact, end-of-life responsibility is found to be most relevant indicator group from the perspective of significance for business as well as influence on stakeholder perceptions in five out of eight value chain covered by this assessment. For two value chains, this group has ranked the second most important indicator group. The only exception is the automotive components value chain. Consumer health and safety, which can easily be combined with consumer well-being, also ranked high in seven out of eight value chains although they did not rank as high as end-of-life responsibility in the order of ranking. Finally, technology development is found to be highly relevant food trays, automobile components and biodegradable polymers value chains and also placed among headline indicators for four additional value chains.

Next to these three indicator groups, it is observed that safe and healthy living conditions and workers' health and safety are considered to be worth considering within the headline indicator sets. Other indicators, which has ranked high enough to be included in the headline indicator set for some value chains, are community access to materials, local employment and supplier relations. Although, considered to be a headline indicator by the automotive components value chain stakeholders, training and education of workers usually ranked lower than previously mentioned indicator sub-groups. Similarly, community access to materials scored low in terms of weights in all value chains except in ones that it scored high enough to be placed in the headline lists. Among the social indicator sub-groups that did not make it in the headline indicator lists and considered to have low importance for a number of value chains include equal opportunities (gender issues) and community engagement.

Detailed results of the ranking and weighing analyses can be found in ANNEX B.

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Table 56 Results of the ANP ranking for social indicators (Headline indicators are presented in green with their ranks, indicators marked with grey have much lower significance)

Indicator sub-groups	Indicator sub-groups											
	Equal opportunities/ discrimination	Training and education	Workers' health and safety	Consumers' health and safety	End-Of-Life responsibility	Consumers' well being	Community access to material resources	Safe and healthy living conditions	Local employment	Community engagement	Technology developments	Suppliers relationships
Value chains												
Biodegradable polymers			4	3	1			5			2	
Multi-material packaging			5	1	2		3		4			
Plastic packaging (bottles)				3	1	2			4		5	
Plastic bags			5	2	1			4			3	
Food trays (tray & multi-material film)				4	2	3					1	5
Automotive components		1	1	1		1		1	1		1	1
Coffee capsules			5	2	1			4			3	
Absorbent Hygienic Products					1		2	4			5	3

13.3 Evaluation of environmental indicators

For the evaluation of environmental indicators, two main activities were carried out. First one is the literature review on the existing RACER analyses of environmental indicators carried out by field experts previously. Second evaluation was done internally by conducting representative surveys within the CIRC-PACK Project consortium. The Cardboard-based multimaterial packaging for powder detergent was selected as the pilot value chain. BUMAGA BV (representing manufacturing of cardboard and packaging), SAPONIA D.D.

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(representing the packaging operations), BUMAGA BV and ECOEMBES (representing End-of-Life operations), and KARTAL MUN (representing the product end-users) has provided the survey results.

The findings for RACER evaluation from the policy reports and previous projects are provided in Table 57. Especially from the resource efficiency point of view, all topics covered with CIRC-PACK environmental indicators are considered to be relevant. In terms of acceptability, credibility and robustness, some indicators were not found to be fully compliant with the criteria. The ease of reporting and quantification is reported to be low for use of recycled material content, which corresponds to secondary raw material consumption among CIRC-PACK indicators, expected recyclable content and fossil depletion. Greenhouse gas emission quantities as reported in CO₂-eq for example, has scored medium in acceptable, credible, easy and robust categories. One indicator that yield no RACER evaluation results was "marine litter", which is a key issue for plastic value chains.

Table 57 RACER evaluation for environmental indicators (References: "Development of a System of Indicators for a Resource efficient Europe" report, "Assessment of resource efficiency indicators and targets", "Material-efficiency Ecodesign Report and Module to the Methodology for the Ecodesign of Energy-related Products (MEErP)")

INDICATOR	R	A	C	E	R
Use of virgin material (primary raw material use) (%)	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Green
Use of recycled material content (Secondary raw material use) (%)	Green	Yellow	Green	Red	Green
Amount of waste generation (%) (MSW)	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Yellow
Amount of waste generation (%) (No MSW)	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green
Expected recyclable content (%)	Green	Yellow	Green	Red	Green
Efficiency of recycling (%)	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Green
Marine litter (%)	White	White	White	White	White
Water consumption (m ³ /kg)	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow
Fossil depletion (MJ/unit product)	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow
Energy consumption (MJ/unit product) (Gross Inland Energy Consumption)	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Green
Greenhouse gas emissions (t CO ₂ -eq/unit product)	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow

Legend:

Green: Fully compatible with the criteria
 Yellow: Partially compatible with the criteria
 Red: Not compatible with the criteria

These results were used as an input for the ANP model of environmental indicator evaluation with qualitative assessment converted into the quantitative framework according to Table 55. According to ANP analysis results summarized in Table 58, waste generation, energy consumption, efficiency of recycling, municipal solid waste generation and water consumption have the highest ranking among the environmental indicators in terms of RACER evaluation. Except for relevancy, credibility and ease criteria respectively, waste generation, energy consumption and efficiency of recycling was determined to be fully compatible with RACER criteria. These indicators turned out to be partially compatible with respective criteria. Municipal solid waste and water consumption has received medium

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scores for partially being compatible with not only a single criteria but two. The bottom scoring indicators in the ranking has at least one case of non-compliance with the criteria of “easy”. Unfortunately, due to absence of data, marine litter is listed as the lowest ranking indicator. It is generally observed that RACER evaluations are biased towards more established indicators. In this sense, marine litter is not mature enough to get high scores in a RACER evaluation even if the RACER results were available.

Table 58 Ranking of environmental indicators according to the RACER evaluation

Indicators	Normal	Ranking
Waste generation from production processes	0.1442	1
Energy consumption	0.1338	2
Efficiency of recycling	0.1263	3
Municipal solid waste generation	0.1145	4
Water consumption	0.1005	5
Secondary raw material consumption	0.0927	6
Expected recyclable content	0.0904	7
Primary raw material consumption	0.0737	8
GHG emissions	0.0514	9
Fossil depletion	0.0422	10
Marine litter	0.0303	11

The second part of the evaluation of environmental indicators involved stakeholder surveys collected from BUMAGA BV, ECOEMBES, SAPONIA DD and KARTAL MUN as representatives of different value chain actors, namely manufacturers of packaging material and packaging itself, users, and parties involved in disposal and recycling. Based on the survey results presented in

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ANNEX C: SURVEY RESULTS FOR ENVIRONMENTAL INDICATORS, different value chain actors have different priorities.

Secondary raw material consumption is one of the top priority environmental indicators for ECOEMBES, KARTAL MUN and SAPONIA DD while it is a mid-ranking indicator for Bumaga (Table 59). On the other hand, fossil depletion and marine litter scored lowest among the stakeholders. Based on survey results from Bumaga, water consumption, GHG emissions and energy consumption has higher importance. For ECOEMBES, primary and secondary raw material consumption as well as expected recyclable content has higher priority. According to KARTAL MUN, the users give expected recyclable content, waste generation from production processes, and primary raw material consumption higher priority. Finally, Saponia survey suggests secondary raw material, waste generation from production processes and primary raw material consumption are more significant.

The outcome of the overall analysis presented in Table 60 indicate that **(i) secondary raw material consumption, (ii) waste generation from production processes, (iii) primary raw material consumption, (iv) expected recyclable content, (v) efficiency of recycling** can be listed as headline indicators. None of the indicators received a weight less than 5% therefore no indicators were identified to have low relevance.

Table 59 Stakeholder priorities of environmental indicators

Indicators	Bumaga	Ecoembes	Kartal	Saponia
Waste generation from production processes	4	4	5	2
Energy consumption	3	8	3	7
Efficiency of recycling	7	6	7	4
Water consumption	1	10	10	8
Secondary raw material consumption	5	1	2	1
Expected recyclable content	10	3	1	6
Primary raw material consumption	6	2	4	3
GHG emissions	2	7	6	9
Fossil depletion	9	9	9	5
Marine litter	8	5	8	10

Table 60 Ranking of environmental indicators according to the surveys

Alternatives	Normal	Ranking	Ranking according to RACER evaluation
Secondary raw material consumption	0.1784	1	6
Waste generation from production processes	0.1357	2	1
Primary raw material consumption	0.1273	3	8

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Expected recyclable content	0.1203	4	7
Efficiency of recycling	0.089	5	3
Water consumption	0.0827	6	5
Energy consumption	0.0812	7	2
GHG emissions	0.0735	8	9
Marine litter	0.0566	9	11
Fossil depletion	0.0555	10	10

13.4 Evaluation of economic indicators

The second part of surveys extended to the project consortium was related to the economic indicators. The indicators included conventional economic indicators such as OPEX, CAPEX or NPV as well as more inclusive indicators like environmental externalities and life cycle cost. BUMAGA BV, SAPONIA DD, ECOEMBES and KARTAL MUN provided responses to the survey, which yielded to the results given in Table 61.

Table 61 ANP results for economic indicators

Alternatives	Normal	Ideal	Ranking
Return of investment (ROI)	0.1937	1	1
Capital expenses (CAPEX)	0.1698	0.8766	2
Operational expenses (OPEX)	0.1552	0.8014	3
Net added value	0.1294	0.6683	4
Internal rate of return (IRR)	0.0984	0.5079	5
Net present value (NPV)	0.0947	0.4892	6
Externalities (environmental cost)	0.0879	0.4541	7
Life cycle cost (LCC)	0.0709	0.3659	8

Based on the information on Table 61, **return of investment, CAPEX and OPEX** are the highest scoring economic indicators. More inclusive economic indicators scored the lowest in the overall rating. Table 62 indicates for industrial stakeholders CAPEX and OPEX are highly significant. Return on investment is highly important for all respondents. Different from the rest, according to KARTAL MUN, return on investment, internal rate of return and net added value is ranking highest. It can be observed from the results that external environmental costs and life cycle costs has not gained much acceptance from the value chain actors despite the fact that these two indicators are inclusive of NPV, CAPEX, OPEX and for the case of LCC, the environmental externalities.

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Table 62 Stakeholder preferences of economic indicators

Alternatives	BUMAGA BV	ECOEMBES	KARTAL MUN	SAPONIA DD
CAPEX	2	1	6	8
Externalities	6	6	4	5
IRR	5	4	3	4
LCC	8	8	8	7
Net added value	4	7	2	6
NPV	3	5	7	3
OPEX	7	2	5	1
ROI	1	3	1	2

13.5 Life cycle indicators

The assessment of life cycle indicators were carried out through literature review instead of surveys and RACER analysis. This is due to the fact that life cycle indicators are still under development and some categories are still under development in terms of scientific methodology. This may cause these categories to score low on the RACER criteria. Furthermore, it is observed that value chain actors have difficulty on interpreting mid-point indicators. Therefore, stakeholder surveys would not yield to identification of relevant life cycle indicators. During Task 2.4, headline set of life cycle indicators are proposed through screening of the impact categories used in environmental product declaration (EPD) studies. Life cycle assessment (LCA) under EPD Projects are carried out on the basis of Product Category Rules (PCRs) related to a specific group of product that are collections of specific rules to conduct LCA including which impact categories to cover.

Besides life cycle inventory indicators covered under environmental indicators section, **GHG emissions, emissions of acidifying gases, eutrophication, and photochemical ozone creation** stand out to be the most significant impact categories that are handled through LCA.

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Table 63 Relevant life cycle impact categories for plastic packaging products based on related PCRs

Product category	CIRC-PACK Value Chain	Indicators	PCR
Plastics in primary forms	Conventional plastics (baseline)	Use of resources renewable and non-renewable, energy, water and materials primary and secondary	[39]
		Waste production <i>Emission of GHGs</i> <i>Emission of acidifying gases</i> <i>Emission of substances to water contributing to eutrophication</i> <i>Emission of gases that contribute to photochemical oxygen creation potential</i>	
Food Contactable Plastic Containers	Food trays	Energy use	[40]
		Resource use Recyclable and secondary materials (optional) Waste generation <i>Global warming</i> <i>Acidification</i> <i>Photochemical oxidant formation</i> <i>Eutrophication</i> <i>Ozone depletion</i>	
Plastic Containers and Packaging	Multiple VCs	<i>GHG emissions</i>	[41]
Cartons, Boxes, Cases, Record Sleeves and Other Packing Containers (Except Bags) of Paper	Multimaterial packaging	Use of resources renewable and non-renewable, energy, water and materials electricity	[42]
		<i>Emissions of GHGs</i> <i>Emissions of ozone-depleting gases</i>	

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- Emissions of acidification gases*
- Emissions of gases that contribute to creation of ground level ozone*
- Emissions of substance to water contributing to oxygen depletion*
- Use of resources
 - renewable and non-renewable,
 - energy, water and materials
 - primary and secondary
- Waste production
- Emission of GHGs* [43]
- Emission of acidifying gases*
- Emission of substances to water contributing to eutrophication*
- Emission of gases that contribute to photochemical oxygen creation potential*

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14 CONCLUSIONS

Deliverable D2.3 (State of play of the demo case using the CEIS) is prepared under the CIRC-PACK project as main output of Task 2.3 on “Baseline definition and preliminary assessment of the CIRC-PACK value chains”. The objective of this deliverable has been analysing the starting point of the CIRC-PACK value chain in order to establish the reference for the evaluation of innovations developed during the project.

The main conclusions for each of the value chains also considered as the public able summary can be described as follows.

- **For packaged products** such as powder detergent, liquid soap, chicken and coffee, main contribution to environmental impact is due to the product itself. In particular, the contribution of packaging to environmental impact is very low for chicken or coffee where The highest contribution is observed for powder detergent, where it can reach up to 40% in some indicators. In these products, recycling leads to savings in all the environmental indicators for all these products, showing the best performance in global warming, fine particulate formation, eutrophication and fossil resource scarcity. Packaged chicken also shows very low contribution of packaging to overall cost (lower than 5%). The highest contribution is observed in liquid soap with almost 70% of the overall manufacturing cost. The group of stakeholders involved in packaged products value chains is very heterogeneous from a social perspective. Among all, same and/or better performance and convenience is expected and communication activities towards intermediate and end-users engagement is frequent.

The economic value added of the value chain varies greatly from low for the food value chain to high for the soap and detergent products. In general, this product packaging is characterised by the low amount of recycled materials used in manufacturing (exception made for the recycled cardboard boxes), the low utility of the packaging (single use only) and the moderate collection rate from the end user side. All the above results in very linear flows and low material circularity index for the starting baseline.

- **For bags**, main contribution to environmental impact is ascribed to raw materials and electricity used during manufacturing process. It has been observed that the use of recycled material reduces the impact in two different ways: a) plastic waste is used to manufacture the recycled material, b) no virgin polymers are used for the manufacturing of bags. According to EC reports the recovery rate for bags in Europe is very low. It has been seen in the assessment that non-collected bags, has significant contribution to ecotoxicity indicators where landfilled. Regarding the cost analysis, main contribution is attributed to the consumption of raw materials. The percentual contribution depend on the weight of the bag, but is not lower than 75% of the overall cost. From a social point of view, changes on bag manufacturing are not expected to involve or increase risks, although they may hinder domestic waste management.

In terms of value added, thick bags show higher score despite of the low selling price, due to the relatively lower production and materials cost. Circularity is positively affected by the recycled material share used in the production process (near to 50%), and

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negatively affected by the low end-user collection and recovery rates of films in general. In spite of that, the product is rather linear (LFI =76%). Thick bags have three times better material circularity index due to the higher utility rate due to an estimated longer life expectancy (8 reuses vs 1) and heavier carried load (4 kg vs 1 kg).

- **For automotive components**, it has been compared different EoL and the impact of recycling is lower than incineration and landfill in most of the indicators. Some of them (such as ozone depletion, ionizing radiation and eutrophication) show higher impact for recycling because of electricity used for recycling process. The opportunity to recycle materials from automotive components may demand new skilled positions and hence, tailored training will be developed.

Despite the high waste recovery rate at the production line, circularity metrics are heavily impacted by the high level of virgin raw materials used, and the high rejection rate in the plastic part production and the assembly line. No material recovery has been taken from the end user viewpoint.

- **For packaging of Absorbent Hygiene Products (AHP)**, environmental assessment revealed that recycling lead to savings in most of the indicators, especially in toxicity related indicators, fossil resource scarcity and global warming. Regarding the recycling process for AHP wastes, it was observed that almost all the impact is associated with energy consumption (either by electricity, fuel or steam). Only in marine eutrophication indicators there is an important contribution of the wastewater generated in the process. In the same manner, the operation cost represents a 85% of the process. According to social impacts assessment, packaging suppliers would be the main involved stakeholders regarding workers health and safety. Due to changes on materials, it is expected a better communication of EOL options through specific labelling on products.

AHP circularity is defined by the low utility of the product, and the null use of recycled materials in the manufacturing of both product and packaging (expectation of the PE bag). Some remarkable process improvements implemented by the manufacturer, such as the AHP recycling line and the partial reuse of the diapers' boxes and minipallets, entail small improvements in the circularity metrics because of the low waste collection rate nation-wide and the predominant use of virgin materials in production.

As a part of the activities under Task 2.3, the assessment of indicators through stakeholder surveys, RACER criteria and lieterature revealed following indicators to be highly relevant as seen in Table 64.

Table 64 Summary of indicator assessment

Theme	Indicators
Environmental (life cycle inventory)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Secondary raw material consumption 2) Waste generation form production processes 3) Primary material consumption 4) Expected recyclable content

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	5) Efficiency of recycling
Life cycle assessment	<p>Resource consumption</p> <p>Waste generation</p> <p>Emission of GHGs</p> <p>Emission of acidifying gases</p> <p>Eutrophication</p> <p>Ozone depletion</p> <p>Photochemical oxidant formation</p>
Economic	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Return on investment 2) CAPEX 3) OPEX 4) Net added value 5) Internal rate of return
Social (indicator sub-categories)	<p>Varies on the value chain but most important indicators include</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) End-of-life responsibility 2) Consumer's health and safety 3) Technology development 4) Safe and healthy living conditions 5) Workers' health and safety

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ANNEXES

ANNEX A: CITIZEN SURVEY: QUESTIONNAIRES AND RESULTS

The Citizen survey “*Your experience with Plastic packaging*” was carried out simultaneously in Belgium, Italy, Portugal and Spain through a self-administered paper questionnaire distributed in November-December 2017. The same survey was carried out in Croatia and Kartal through a Computer assisted personal interview method (CAPI), face-to-face using tablet software, in January-February 2018.

The questionnaire was developed with respect to CIRCPACK context and aims, complemented with literature & desk research and environmental experts’ inputs from the partner organisations. The layout and scripting of the questionnaires in all national languages were harmonized as much as possible. (See QUESTIONNAIRE in English in this Annex).

Sampling: at least 1000 valid responses were required, as representative as possible of the general population by gender, age (18-74 y.o.) and geographic/residence area distribution according to the national/local statistics indicators. After the survey questionnaire’s production process (printing-routing etc.), the fieldwork follow-up included paper questionnaire collection, pre-data-entry control and individual numbering of all questionnaires, full data-entry process with data-entry control, second independent data-entry control and rough database delivery to the statistical survey analysis coordinator.

Data were weighted by gender, age, educational level and geographical distribution, as to ensure representative trends for the national populations, or in the case of Kartal, district of Istanbul, for the sub-regional population.

Overview of Citizen survey

	Belgium	Italy	Portugal	Spain	Croatia	Kartal
Questionnaires	Paper	Paper	Paper	Paper	Online	Online
Fieldwork	Nov 2017	Nov 2017	Nov 2017	Nov 2017	Jan 2018	Jan 2018
Survey distribution	Postal quota sampling	Postal quota sampling	Postal quota sampling	Postal quota sampling	Door-to- door sampling	Door-to- door sampling

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Questionnaires completed	2.101	2.607	1.925	1.219	1.001	1.014
Age sample	18-74	18-74	18-74	18-74	18-74	18-74

As a general rule, respondents answered all or nearly all questions. A slight exception concerns Kartal respondents in relation to coffee capsule. This product is not widely available neither popular in Turkey, which was a constraint acknowledged from the beginning by the partner country.

YOUR EXPERIENCE WITH PLASTIC PACKAGING

Everyone can answer this questionnaire, no matter how frequently buying plastic packaged products or using plastic bags. You should only answer the questions/sections that are applicable to your own experience.

Your profile

1. According to you, how important is it having a good ecological behavior (separating waste, reducing energy use, saving water, using public transportations, eating organic food, etc.)?

1= not important at all 3= somewhat important
2= not very important 4= very important

2. To what extent do you take action to put in practice a good ecological behavior?

1= I don't take any specific actions
2= I take some actions
3= I take a lot of actions

3. To what extent do you think domestic waste has a real impact on the environment?

1= no single impact 3= some impact
2= very minor impact 4= great impact

4. In general, how well do you feel informed about the following issues? [Answer from 1 to 10.]

- | | |
|---|--------------------------|
| National environmental policies and legislation | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| EU environmental policies and legislation | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Environmental impact of pollution in general | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Environmental impact of plastic waste | <input type="checkbox"/> |

5. How much of an influence does each of the following aspects have on your decision when buying an everyday product such as food, detergents, hygiene products, etc.? [Answer from 1 to 10.]

- | | |
|---|--------------------------|
| The price | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| The quality | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| The composition | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| The origin | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| The brand (reputation) | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Features / characteristics of the product | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| The look / design | <input type="checkbox"/> |

- | | |
|--|--------------------------|
| The packaging | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| User friendliness / convenience | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Promotions / offers | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Environmental aspects (eg. pollutants, organic food) | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Product packaging

6. Do you avoid buying / using products with plastic content / plastic packaging?

1= never
2= yes, sometimes
3= always

- | | |
|---------------------------------|--------------------------|
| Products with plastic content | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Products with plastic packaging | <input type="checkbox"/> |

i When answering the following question, please note: Bio-based plastic is created from renewable sources (fermentation of cereals, potatoes, maize...). It can be biodegradable or not. Biodegradable means that it decomposes as organic / food waste and can be composted.

7. Which type of packaging would you choose when buying the following products? [Please select one option for each product]

- Coffee capsule
 - 1= conventional plastic capsule
 - 2= bio-based plastic capsule (non biodegradable)
 - 3= biodegradable plastic capsule
 - 4= aluminum capsule
 - 5= no preference

- Fresh meat (eg. chicken)
 - 1= conventional plastic tray (eg. polystyrene)
 - 2= bio-based plastic tray (non biodegradable)
 - 3= biodegradable plastic tray
 - 4= non-plastic packaging (eg. paper)
 - 5= no preference

- Prepared food (eg. salad lunch)
 - 1= conventional plastic container (eg. polystyrene)
 - 2= bio-based plastic container (non biodegradable)
 - 3= biodegradable plastic container
 - 4= non-plastic container (eg. cardboard)
 - 5= no preference

• **Washing machine detergent in powder**

- 1= conventional plastic bag / box
- 2= bio-based plastic bag / box (non biodegradable)
- 3= biodegradable plastic bag / box
- 4= conventional cardboard box
- 5= no preference

• **Shower gel / shampoo**

- 1= conventional plastic flask
- 2= bio-based plastic flask (non biodegradable)
- 3= non-plastic flask (eg. glass)
- 4= no preference

8. Which of the following aspects in packaging do you value most for the following products?

(Indicate only one aspect by type of product.)

- 1= material(s), composition
- 2= size, weight or volume
- 3= design (appearance, colour)
- 4= shape (easy to seize or use the whole content)
- 5= convenience (handling of the product, transportation, pouring spout, stopper, etc.)
- 6= product protection
- 7= environmental aspects (eg. suited for re-fill, fully recyclable, non polluting material...)

Coffee capsule	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fresh meat	<input type="checkbox"/>
Prepared food	<input type="checkbox"/>
Washing machine detergent in powder	<input type="checkbox"/>
Shampoo / shower gel	<input type="checkbox"/>

9. How frequently do you perceive the following situations when buying everyday products with plastic packaging?

- 1= never
- 2= few times
- 3= sometimes
- 4= most of the time
- 5= always

Packaging unnecessary because the product is sufficient to itself	<input type="checkbox"/>
Packaging too large considering the size of the product	<input type="checkbox"/>
Packaging too heavy considering the weight of the product itself	<input type="checkbox"/>
Packaging not handy or not well-fit to the product	<input type="checkbox"/>
Packaging that gives an impression of luxury or higher quality than what it is	<input type="checkbox"/>
Packaging that is not easy to compress and be disposed of	<input type="checkbox"/>
Packaging that doesn't protect/preserve the product properly	<input type="checkbox"/>
Packaging for single-use / not fit for reuse or refill	<input type="checkbox"/>

Plastic bags

10. Regarding shopping bags, how do you usually proceed when shopping for groceries in supermarkets?

- 1= I mainly bring bags from home (re-use them from previous purchases, or use a textile bag)
- 2= I mainly buy (new) bags at the supermarket
- 3= I both bring bags from home and buy them at the supermarket
- 4= I don't use bags (e.g. carry the products by hand, in a shopping trolley or use cardboard/plastic boxes) [answer '4' and go to Question 15]

! When answering the following question, please note:

Bio-based plastic is created from renewable sources (fermentation of cereals, potatoes, maize...). It can be biodegradable or not. Biodegradable means that it decomposes as organic / food waste and can be composted.

11. From the following list of bag materials, which one would you prefer when shopping for groceries?

- 1= conventional plastic
- 2= bio-based plastic (non biodegradable)
- 3= biodegradable plastic
- 4= paper
- 5= textile
- 6= synthetic fiber (eg. polyester)
- 7= other (specify):
- 8= no preference

12. How satisfied are you with the plastic bags you buy in the supermarket regarding the following aspects? (Answer from 1 to 10.)

Size	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ease of use	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Price	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Resistance	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall satisfaction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

13. How often do you experience the following situations when shopping for groceries?

- 1= never
- 2= few times
- 3= sometimes
- 4= most of the time
- 5= always

Trying to fit the purchases in the smallest possible number of bags	<input type="checkbox"/>
Asking for a more resistant or bigger bag, which is more expensive	<input type="checkbox"/>
Being proposed a more resistant or bigger bag, which is more expensive	<input type="checkbox"/>
Asking for a more resistant or reusable bag, and it is not available	<input type="checkbox"/>

- Being proposed to choose between light weight or long-life reusable bags
- Being proposed to use bio-based bags (non biodegradable)
- Being proposed to use bio-degradable bags

i When answering the following question, please note: Bio-based plastic is created from renewable sources (fermentation of cereals, potatoes, maize...). It can be biodegradable or not. Biodegradable means that it decomposes as organic / food waste and can be composted.

14. How much would you be willing to pay for a plastic bag when shopping for groceries?

- 1= no single amount
- 2= no more than 5 cents per bag
- 3= 6 to 10 cents per bag
- 4= 11 to 15 cents per bag
- 5= 16 to 20 cents per bag
- 6= more than 20 cents per bag

- Bio-based plastic bag (non biodegradable)
- Biodegradable bag

Plastic waste recycling

15. How well informed do you feel about waste separation (which materials are to be recycled, recycling bin/bag colours, waste treatment, final destination of recovery materials, recycling rates etc.) according to your municipality rules? [Answer from 1 to 10.]

16. Does your household separate the following waste? [Please answer for each type of waste, whichever the municipal waste collection system]

- 1= no
- 2= yes, but not very accurately
- 3= yes, very accurately

- Metal
- Plastic
- Drink packaging / Tetrapak
- Glass
- Paper/cardboard
- Clothes
- Bio-waste (eg. garden, kitchen and food waste)
- Cooking oil / vegetable oil
- Medicines
- Batteries
- Other hazardous waste (eg. paint, light bulb, electronics or any waste that includes toxic components)

If you answered '3' in the previous question for all types of waste, continue with question 18.

17. What prevents you from separating (more accurately) your waste? [Tick.]

- All (types of) waste bring-points are too far away from my house
- Some (types of) waste bring-points (e.g. for glass) are too far away from my house
- There is no door-to-door collection of separated waste
- Waste separation is too expensive (cost of the bins, specific collection bags, etc.)
- It's not convenient / practical to have so many waste bins/bags at home
- I don't know how to do it (lack of information)
- It's time consuming / it gives too much work
- I don't feel motivated to do it because the garbage I produce will not make the difference
- Other [specify]:

18. How much do you agree with the following statements regarding the environmental impact of plastic for domestic use?

- 1= strongly disagree
- 2= rather disagree
- 3= neither agree nor disagree
- 4= rather agree
- 5= strongly agree

- Plastic for domestic use is a problem for the planet
- Plastic for domestic use consumes a lot of natural resources
- Once discarded, plastic for domestic use is a waste that cannot be re-used
- Plastic for domestic use generates food safety risks
- Plastic for domestic use generates health risks
- The production/use/waste of plastic for domestic use is one of the most important causes of pollution

19. How often do you keep and reuse the packaging below?

- 1= never
- 2= few times
- 3= sometimes
- 4= most of the time
- 5= always

- Fresh meat plastic tray
- Fruit / vegetable plastic tray
- Prepared food plastic container
- Water plastic bottle
- Detergent / shampoo plastic flasks
- Plastic bag

New plastic materials

f When answering the following questions, please note: Bio-based plastic is created from renewable sources (fermentation of cereals, potatoes, maize...). It can be biodegradable or not. Biodegradable means that it decomposes as organic / food waste and can be composted.

20. When buying a product, would you give preference to products packaged with the following new materials?

- 1= no single preference
- 2= yes depending on the products
- 3= yes in any case

Bio-based plastic (non biodegradable) (118)

Biodegradable plastic (119)

Recycled plastic (121)

21. How much more extra would you be willing to pay for the following products using bio-based / biodegradable packaging ?

- 1= no single amount
- 2= no more than 5 cents
- 3= 6 to 10 cents
- 4= 11 to 15 cents
- 5= 16 to 20 cents
- 6= more than 20 cents

Coffee capsule (122)

Fresh meat (123)

Prepared food (124)

Washing machine detergent in powder (125)

Shampoo / shower gel (126)

22. The waste from biodegradable plastic requires to be sorted with bio-waste (eg. waste from food/kitchen, garden, etc). What would be the impact of this on your domestic waste management?

- 1= It would make it more difficult
- 2= It would be about the same as now
- 3= It would make it easier

23. To what extent are you informed about new plastic materials (bio-based / biodegradable)?

- 1= not at all and I don't care
- 2= not at all but I would like to be informed
- 3= a bit informed
- 4= well informed

24. How much do you trust information on new plastic material provided by the following sources? [Answer from 1 to 10.]

Manufacturer (eg. product packaging, brand website) (128) (129)

Supermarket (130) (131)

Public authorities (eg. by country) (132) (133)

Independent certification institutions (eg. label OK Compost, EcoLabel) (134) (135)

Media (136) (137)

Environmental organisations (eg. Greenpeace) (138) (139)

Consumer organisation (eg. by country) (140) (141)

For finishing...

25. Your gender:

- 1= female
- 2= male

 (142)

26. Your age:

 (143) (144) years old

27. Your educational level: [Indicate the level that you fully completed (until now)]

- 1= ???
- 2= ???
- 3= ???
- 4= ???

 (145)

28. Your household composition:

Nr. of adults (including yourself) (146)

Nr. of persons 12-17 years old (147)

Nr. of persons 4-11 years old (148)

Nr. of persons < 4 years old (149)

29. Your financial situation:

- 1= very difficult
- 2= difficult
- 3= sufficient to make ends meet
- 4= comfortable
- 5= very comfortable

 (150)

30. The type of area where you live:

- 1= urban / in a city
- 2= semi-urban / city suburb
- 3= rural / small town or village

 (151)

31. Your postal code/province:

 (152) (153) (154) (155)

THANK YOU VERY MUCH FOR YOUR COLLABORATION!

Country code 2 (156)

VOTRE EXPÉRIENCE CONCERNANT LES EMBALLAGES EN PLASTIQUE

Tout le monde peut répondre à ce questionnaire, peu importe la fréquence à laquelle vous achetez des produits emballés dans du plastique ou utilisez des sacs en plastique. Vous devez uniquement répondre aux questions/sections qui s'appliquent à votre expérience personnelle.

Votre profil

1. Dans quelle mesure trouvez-vous important d'adopter un bon comportement écologique (en triant les déchets, réduisant sa consommation d'énergie, utilisant les transports en commun, mangeant des aliments bio, etc.) ?

1= pas du tout important 3= relativement important
2= pas très important 4= très important

2. Jusqu'à quel point prenez-vous des mesures pour mettre en pratique un bon comportement écologique ?

1= Je ne prends aucune mesure particulière
2= Je prends certaines mesures
3= Je prends de nombreuses mesures

3. Dans quelle mesure pensez-vous que les déchets ménagers ont un réel impact sur l'environnement ?

1= aucun impact 3= un certain impact
2= un impact très mineur 4= un impact important

4. En général, dans quelle mesure pensez-vous être bien informé(e) sur les questions suivantes ?

[Répondez de 1 à 10.]

Les lois et politiques belges en matière d'environnement

Les lois et politiques européennes en matière d'environnement

L'impact environnemental de la pollution en général

L'impact environnemental des déchets de plastique

5. Dans quelle mesure chacun des aspects suivants a-t-il une influence sur votre décision lorsque vous achetez un produit courant tel que des aliments, détergents, produits d'hygiène, etc. ?

[Répondez de 1 à 10.]

Le prix

La qualité

La composition

L'origine

La marque (réputation)

Les spécificités/caractéristiques du produit

L'aspect / design

L'emballage

La facilité d'utilisation / le côté pratique

Les offres/promotions

Les aspects environnementaux (ex. polluants, aliment bio)

L'emballage des produits

6. Évitez-vous d'acheter / d'utiliser des produits contenant / emballés dans du plastique ?

1= Jamais
2= oui, parfois
3= toujours

Produits contenant du plastique

Produits dans un emballage en plastique

! Au moment de répondre à la prochaine question, veuillez prendre note de l'information suivante :

Le plastique biosourcé est fabriqué à partir de sources renouvelables (fermentation de céréales, pommes de terre, maïs, ...). Il peut être biodégradable ou non. Biodégradable signifie qu'il se décompose comme les déchets organiques / alimentaires et peut être composté.

7. Quel type d'emballage choisiriez-vous lorsque vous achetez les produits suivants ? [Sélectionnez une seule option pour chaque produit.]

• Capsule de café

1= capsule en plastique classique
2= capsule en plastique biosourcé (non biodégradable)
3= capsule en plastique biodégradable
4= capsule en aluminium
5= aucune préférence

• Viande fraîche (ex. poulet)

1= barquette en plastique classique (ex. en polystyrène)
2= barquette en plastique biosourcé (non biodégradable)
3= barquette en plastique biodégradable
4= emballage non plastique (ex. en papier)
5= aucune préférence

Aliments préparés (ex. salade-repas)

- 1= contenant en plastique classique (ex. en polystyrène)
- 2= contenant en plastique biosourcé (non biodégradable)
- 3= contenant en plastique biodégradable
- 4= contenant non plastique (ex. en carton)
- 5= aucune préférence

Détergent à lessive en poudre

- 1= boîte / sac en plastique classique
- 2= boîte / sac en plastique biosourcé (non biodégradable)
- 3= boîte / sac en plastique biodégradable
- 4= boîte en carton classique
- 5= aucune préférence

Shampooing / gel douche

- 1= flacon en plastique classique
- 2= flacon en plastique biosourcé (non biodégradable)
- 3= flacon non plastique (ex. en verre)
- 4= aucune préférence

8. Lequel des aspects suivants de l'emballage valorise-vous le plus pour les produits suivants ?

[N'indiquez qu'un seul aspect par type de produit.]

- 1= matière(s), composition
- 2= taille, poids ou volume
- 3= design (apparence, couleur)
- 4= forme (facile à prendre ou utiliser la totalité du contenu)
- 5= côté pratique (manement du produit, transport, bec verseur, bouchon, etc.)
- 6= protection / conservation du produit
- 7= aspects environnementaux (ex. matière non polluante, entièrement recyclable, convenant au remplissage, ...)

- Capsule de café
- Viande fraîche
- Aliments préparés
- Détergent à lessive en poudre
- Shampooing / gel douche

9. À quelle fréquence avez-vous la perception suivante lorsque vous achetez des produits courants en emballage en plastique ?

- 1= jamais
- 2= rarement
- 3= parfois
- 4= la plupart du temps
- 5= toujours

- Emballage inutile car le produit se suffit à lui-même
- Emballage trop grand compte tenu de la taille du produit
- Emballage trop lourd compte tenu du poids du produit lui-même
- Emballage pas pratique ou mal adapté au produit
- Emballage qui donne l'impression d'un produit de luxe ou de meilleure qualité qu'il ne l'est
- Emballage difficile à compacter et à éliminer
- Emballage qui ne protège / conserve pas bien le produit
- Emballage à usage unique / ne convenant pas à la réutilisation ou remplissage

Les sacs en plastique

10. Pour ce qui est des sacs à provisions, comment procédez-vous généralement lorsque vous faites vos courses au supermarché ?

- 1= J'apporte principalement des sacs de chez moi (Je réutilise ceux de mes précédents achats, ou utilise des sacs réutilisables)
- 2= J'achète principalement des (nouveaux) sacs au supermarché
- 3= J'apporte des sacs de chez moi et en achète aussi au supermarché
- 4= Je n'utilise pas de sacs (ex. transport des produits à la main, dans un caddie sur roulettes ou utilise des boîtes en carton / bacs en plastique) [répondez '4' et passez à la question 15]

! Au moment de répondre à la prochaine question, veuillez prendre note de l'information suivante :

Le plastique biosourcé est fabriqué à partir de sources renouvelables (fermentation de céréales, pommes de terre, maïs, ...). Il peut être biodégradable ou non. Biodégradable signifie qu'il se décompose comme les déchets organiques / alimentaires et peut être composté.

11. Parmi les matériaux pour sacs d'emballage dans la liste suivante, lequel préféreriez-vous utiliser pour faire vos courses ?

- 1= plastique classique
- 2= plastique biosourcé (non biodégradable)
- 3= plastique biodégradable
- 4= papier
- 5= textile
- 6= fibre synthétique (ex. polyester)
- 7= autre [précisez]:
- 8= aucune préférence

12. Dans quelle mesure êtes-vous satisfait(e) des sacs en plastique que vous achetez au supermarché pour ce qui est des aspects suivants ?

[Répondez de 1 à 10.]

- Taille
- Facilité d'utilisation
- Prix
- Résistance
- Satisfaction générale

13. À quelle fréquence vous trouvez-vous dans les situations suivantes lorsque vous faites vos courses au supermarché ?

- 1= jamais
- 2= rarement
- 3= parfois
- 4= la plupart du temps
- 5= toujours

- Essayer de rassembler vos achats dans le moins de sacs possible
- Demander à avoir un sac plus grand ou plus solide, qui est plus cher

Se voir proposer un sac plus grand ou plus solide, qui est plus cher

Demander à avoir un sac plus solide ou réutilisable, et qu'il n'y en ait pas

1 Au moment de répondre à la prochaine question, veuillez prendre note de l'information suivante :

Le plastique biosourcé est fabriqué à partir de sources renouvelables (fermentation de céréales, pommes de terre, maïs, ...). Il peut être biodégradable ou non. Biodégradable signifie qu'il se décompose comme les déchets organiques / alimentaires et peut être composté.

14. A terme il est prévu que les sacs ultra-légers pour le self-service de fruits et légumes au supermarché soient biodégradables et compostables. Combien seriez-vous disposé(e) à payer pour ce nouveau type de sac ?

- | | |
|--------------------------------|-----------------------------|
| 1= aucun montant | 4= 6 à 10 cents par sac |
| 2= pas plus de 2 cents par sac | 5= plus de 10 cents par sac |
| 3= 3 à 5 cents par sac | |

Le recyclage des déchets de plastique

15. Dans quelle mesure pensez-vous être bien informé(e) de la réglementation relative à la collecte sélective des déchets dans votre commune (matériaux à trier, sacs spécifiques, etc.) ? [Répondez de 1 à 10.]

16. Votre ménage trie-t-il les déchets suivants ?

[Répondez pour chaque type de déchets, quel que soit le système de collecte des déchets de votre commune.]

- | | |
|----------------------------|-------------------|
| 1= non | 3= oui, très bien |
| 2= oui, mais pas très bien | |

- Métal
- Plastique
- Emballages de boisson / Tetra Pak
- Verre
- Papier/carton
- Vêtements
- Déchets organiques et déchets verts (ex. déchets de jardin et déchets alimentaires)
- Huile de friture / huile végétale
- Médicaments
- Piles
- Autres déchets dangereux (ex. peinture, ampoules, produits électroniques ou autres déchets contenant des composants toxiques)

Si vous avez répondu '3' à la question précédente pour tous les types de déchets, passez à la question 18.

17. Qu'est-ce qui vous empêche de (mieux) trier vos déchets ? [Cochez.]

- Tous les (types de) centres de collecte des déchets sont situés trop loin de chez moi
- Certains (types de) centres de collecte des déchets (ex. pour le verre) sont situés trop loin de chez moi
- Il n'existe pas de système de collecte séparée des déchets à domicile
- Le tri des déchets est trop coûteux (coût des bacs, sacs de collecte spécifiques, etc.)
- Ce n'est pas commode/pratique d'avoir autant de sacs/bacs à déchets à la maison
- J'ignore comment faire (manque d'information)
- Cela prend trop temps / cela demande trop de travail
- Je ne me sens pas motivé(e) à le faire car la quantité de déchets que je produis ne fera pas de différence
- Autre [précisez]:

18. Dans quelle mesure êtes-vous d'accord avec les énoncés suivants concernant l'impact environnemental du plastique à usage domestique ?

- | | |
|---------------------------------|-------------------------|
| 1= pas du tout d'accord | 4= plutôt d'accord |
| 2= plutôt pas d'accord | 5= tout à fait d'accord |
| 3= ni d'accord, ni pas d'accord | |

- Le plastique à usage domestique est un problème pour la planète
- Le plastique à usage domestique consomme beaucoup de ressources naturelles
- Une fois jeté, le plastique à usage domestique est un déchet qui ne peut pas être réutilisé
- Le plastique à usage domestique comporte des risques pour la sécurité alimentaire
- Le plastique à usage domestique comporte des risques pour la santé
- La production / l'utilisation / les déchets de plastique à usage domestique sont l'une des principales causes de pollution

19. À quelle fréquence gardez-vous et réutilisez-vous les emballages ci-dessous ?

- | | |
|-------------|------------------------|
| 1= jamais | 4= la plupart du temps |
| 2= rarement | 5= toujours |
| 3= parfois | |

- Barquette de viande fraîche en plastique
- Barquette de fruits/légumes en plastique
- Contenant d'aliments préparés en plastique
- Bouteille d'eau en plastique

Flacons de détergent/shampooing en plastique (118)

Sacs en plastique (119)

Les nouvelles matières plastiques

! Au moment de répondre aux prochaines questions, veuillez prendre note de l'information suivante :

Le plastique biosourcé est fabriqué à partir de sources renouvelables (fermentation de céréales, pommes de terre, maïs, ...). Il peut être biodégradable ou non. Biodégradable signifie qu'il se décompose comme les déchets organiques / alimentaires et peut être composté.

20. Lors de l'achat d'un produit, donneriez-vous la préférence aux produits emballés dans les nouvelles matières suivantes ?

- 1= aucune préférence
- 2= oui, dépendant des produits
- 3= oui dans tous les cas

Plastique biosourcé (non biodégradable) (120)

Plastique biodégradable (121)

Plastique recyclé (122)

21. Combien seriez-vous disposé(e) à payer en plus pour les produits suivants utilisant un emballage en plastique biosourcé / biodégradable ?

- 1= aucun montant
- 2= pas plus de 5 cents
- 3= 6 à 10 cents
- 4= 11 à 15 cents
- 5= 16 à 20 cents
- 6= plus de 20 cents

Capsule de café (123)

Viande fraîche (124)

Aliments préparés (125)

Détergent à lessive en poudre (126)

Shampooing / gel douche (127)

22. Les déchets de matières plastiques biodégradables nécessitent d'être triés avec les déchets organiques (ex. les déchets de jardin, déchets alimentaires, ...). Quel impact cela aurait-il sur la gestion de vos déchets ménagers?

- 1= cela compliquerait la gestion
- 2= la gestion serait sensiblement la même que maintenant
- 3= cela simplifierait la gestion

23. Dans quelle mesure êtes-vous informé(e) au sujet des nouvelles matières plastiques (biosourcées / biodégradables) ?

- 1= pas du tout et je m'en soucie pas
- 2= pas du tout, mais j'aimerais être informé(e)
- 3= un peu informé(e)
- 4= bien informé(e)

24. Dans quelle mesure vous fiez-vous aux informations au sujet des nouvelles matières plastiques provenant des sources suivantes ?

[Répondez de 1 à 10.]

très peu confiance très grande confiance

Fabricant (ex. Fost Plus, emballage des produits, site des marques) (128) (129)

Supermarchés (130) (131)

Autorités publiques (ex. Office wallon des déchets, Agence Bruxelles Propreté) (132) (133)

Organismes de certification indépendants (ex. Vinçotte, label OK Compost, Ecolabel) (134) (135)

Médias (136) (137)

Organisations environnementales (ex. Greenpeace, Ecoconso) (138) (139)

Organisation de consommateurs (ex. Test-Achats) (140) (141)

Pour mieux vous connaître...

25. Vous êtes...

- 1= une femme
- 2= un homme

(142)

26. Quel âge avez-vous ?

ans (143) (144)

27. Quel est votre niveau d'éducation ?

- 1= enseignement primaire ou secondaire inférieur
- 2= enseignement secondaire supérieur
- 3= enseignement supérieur ou universitaire

(145)

28. Quelle est la composition de votre ménage ?

Nombre total d'adultes (vous y compris) (146)

Nombre de personnes de 12 à 17 ans (147)

Nombre de personnes de 4 à 11 ans (148)

Nombre de personnes < 4 ans (149)

29. Comment décririez-vous votre situation financière ?

- 1= très difficile
- 2= difficile
- 3= suffisante pour joindre les deux bouts
- 4= confortable
- 5= très confortable

(150)

30. Dans quel environnement habitez-vous ?

- 1= urbain / en ville
- 2= semi-urbain / banlieue
- 3= rural / village

(151)

31. Dans quelle région habitez-vous ?

- 1= Région de Bruxelles-Capitale
- 2= Région flamande
- 3= Région wallonne

(152)

MERCI POUR VOTRE COLLABORATION!

Code du pays 2 (153)

UW ERVARINGEN MET PLASTIC VERPAKKINGEN

Iedereen kan deze vragenlijst invullen. Hoe vaak u in plastic verpakte producten koopt of plastic draagtassen gebruikt, doet er dus niet toe. Beantwoord wel enkel die vragen/hoofdstukken die op uw eigen situatie van toepassing zijn.

Uw profiel

1. Hoe belangrijk is verantwoord ecologisch gedrag volgens u (afval scheiden, minder energie verbruiken, het openbaar vervoer nemen, biologisch voedsel eten, enz.)?

- 1= totaal niet belangrijk 3= ietwat belangrijk
2= niet erg belangrijk 4= zeer belangrijk

2. In welke mate doet u zelf iets om werk te maken van verantwoord ecologisch gedrag?

- 1= ik doe niets speciaals
2= ik doe wel een en ander
3= ik doe veel

3. In welke mate heeft huishoudelijk afval volgens u echt een impact op het milieu?

- 1= geen enkele impact 3= enige impact
2= een zeer geringe impact 4= een grote impact

4. Hoe goed bent u globaal op de hoogte van de volgende kwesties? [Antwoord van 1 tot 10.]

Belgisch milieubeleid en Belgische milieuwetgeving

Milieubeleid en milieuwetgeving op niveau van de EU

Milieu-impact van vervuiling in het algemeen

Milieu-impact van plastic afval

5. Hoeveel invloed heeft elk van de volgende aspecten op uw beslissing bij het aankopen van doordeweekse producten zoals voeding, (vaat) was- en schoonmaakmiddelen, producten voor persoonlijke hygiëne, enz.? [Antwoord van 1 tot 10.]

Prijs

Kwaliteit

Samenstelling

Herkomst

(Reputatie van het) merk

Kenmerken/eigenschappen van het product

Look / design

Verpakking

Gebruiksvriendelijkheid/-gemak

Promoties / speciale aanbiedingen

Milieuaspecten (bv. milieuverontreinigende stoffen, biologisch voedsel)

Productverpakkingen

6. Vermijdt u de aankoop / het gebruik van producten die plastic bevatten of in plastic verpakt zijn?

- 1= nooit
2= soms
3= altijd

Producten die plastic bevatten

Producten die in plastic verpakt zijn

Houd bij het beantwoorden van deze vraag het volgende voor ogen:

Biobased plastic, ook wel genoemd plastic van biologisch oorsprong, wordt gemaakt van hernieuwbare grondstoffen (vergisting van granen, aardappelen, mais...). Soms is het biologisch afbreekbaar, soms niet. Biologisch afbreekbaar betekent dat het materiaal ontbindt zoals organisch afval of keukenafval en dat het composteerbaar is.

7. Aan wat voor verpakking zou u de voorkeur geven bij het kopen van volgende producten?

[Duid bij elk product slechts één optie aan.]

• Koffiecapsule

- 1= capsule uit gewoon plastic
2= capsule uit biobased plastic (niet biologisch afbreekbaar)
3= capsule uit biologisch afbreekbaar plastic
4= capsule uit aluminium
5= geen voorkeur

• Vers vlees (bv. kip)

- 1= schaalpje uit gewoon plastic (bv. polystyreen)
2= schaalpje uit biobased plastic (niet biologisch afbreekbaar)
3= schaalpje uit biologisch afbreekbaar plastic
4= verpakking uit ander materiaal dan plastic (bv. papier)
5= geen voorkeur

• Bereide maaltijd (bv. lunchslaaije)

- 1= doosje uit gewoon plastic (bv. polystyreen)
2= doosje uit biobased plastic (niet biologisch afbreekbaar)
3= doosje uit biologisch afbreekbaar plastic
4= doosje uit ander materiaal dan plastic (bv. karton)
5= geen voorkeur

• **Waspoeder**

- 1= zak/doos uit gewoon plastic
- 2= zak/doos uit biobased plastic (niet biologisch afbreekbaar)
- 3= zak/doos uit biologisch afbreekbaar plastic
- 4= doos uit gewoon karton
- 5= geen voorkeur

• **Shampoo / douchegel**

- 1= flacon uit gewoon plastic
- 2= flacon uit biobased plastic (niet biologisch afbreekbaar)
- 3= flacon uit ander materiaal dan plastic (bv. glas)
- 4= geen voorkeur

8. Aan welke van de volgende aspecten van een verpakking hecht u het meest belang bij de volgende producten? [Duid bij elk product slechts één aspect aan.]

- 1= materia(a)l(en), samenstelling
- 2= afmetingen, gewicht of volume
- 3= design (aanblik, kleur)
- 4= vorm (makkelijk om vast te grijpen of om de inhoud volledig op te gebruiken)
- 5= gebruiksgemak (hanteerbaarheid van het product, vervoer, gietuit, gietstop, enz.)
- 6= bescherming van het product
- 7= milieuaspecten (bv. navulbaar, volledig recyclebaar, geen verontreinigende stoffen...)

Koffiecapsule

Vers vlees

Bereide maaltijd

Waspoeder

Shampoo/douchegel

9. Hoe vaak stelt u de volgende situaties vast bij het kopen van doordeweekse producten in een plastic verpakking?

- 1= nooit
- 2= zelden
- 3= soms
- 4= meestal
- 5= altijd

Verpakking is overbodig omdat het product op zich volstaat

Verpakking is te groot gelet op de afmetingen van het product

Verpakking is te zwaar gelet op het gewicht van het product

Verpakking is niet handig of niet aangepast aan het product

Verpakking wekt een indruk van luxe of van een hogere kwaliteit dan werkelijk het geval is

Verpakking valt niet makkelijk samen te drukken of weg te gooien

Verpakking beschermt/bewaart het product niet naar behoren

Verpakking is voor eenmalig gebruik / niet herbruikbaar of navulbaar

Plastic draagtassen

10. Nu even over draagtassen voor boodschappen. Hoe gaat u gewoonlijk te werk wanneer u boodschappen doet in de supermarkt?

- 1= ik breng meestal draagtassen mee van thuis (ik hergebruik de draagtassen van vorige aankopen of ik gebruik een herbruikbare draagtas)
- 2= ik koop meestal (nieuwe) draagtassen in de supermarkt
- 3= nu eens breng ik draagtassen mee van thuis, dan weer koop ik er in de supermarkt
- 4= ik gebruik geen draagtassen (bv. ik draag mijn aankopen in mijn handen, ik stop ze in een caddie of ik gebruik dozen in karton/plastic) (Antwoord '4' en ga dan verder met vraag 15)

! *Houd bij het beantwoorden van deze vraag het volgende voor ogen:*

Biobased plastic, ook wel genoemd plastic van biologisch oorsprong, wordt gemaakt van hernieuwbare grondstoffen (vergisting van granen, aardappelen, mais...). Soms is het biologisch afbreekbaar, soms niet. Biologisch afbreekbaar betekent dat het materiaal ontbindt zoals organisch afval of keukenafval en dat het composteerbaar is.

11. Hieronder een lijst met materialen voor draagtassen. Aan welk materiaal zou u de voorkeur geven bij het boodschappen doen?

- 1= gewoon plastic
- 2= biobased plastic (niet biologisch afbreekbaar)
- 3= biologisch afbreekbaar plastic
- 4= papier
- 5= textiel
- 6= synthetische vezels (bv. polyester)
- 7= ander materiaal [omschrijf]:
- 8= geen voorkeur

12. Hoe tevreden bent u over de volgende aspecten van de draagtassen die u koopt in de supermarkt? [Antwoord van 1 tot 10.]

Afmetingen

Gebruiksgemak

Prijs

Stevigheid

Globale tevredenheid

13. Hoe vaak maakt u de volgende situaties mee wanneer u boodschappen doet in de supermarkt?

- 1= nooit
- 2= zelden
- 3= soms
- 4= meestal
- 5= altijd

Ik probeer mijn aankopen in zo weinig mogelijk draagtassen te stoppen

- Ik vraag een stevigere of grotere draagtas, die duurder is
- Men stelt mij een stevigere of grotere draagtas voor, die duurder is
- Ik vraag een stevigere of herbruikbare draagtas, maar die blijkt niet voorhanden
- Ik krijg de keuze tussen lichtgewicht draagtassen en herbruikbare draagtassen die lang meegaan

i Houd bij het beantwoorden van deze vraag het volgende voor ogen:

Biobased plastic, ook wel genoemd plastic van biologisch oorsprong, wordt gemaakt van hernieuwbare grondstoffen (vergisting van granen, aardappelen, mais...). Soms is het biologisch afbreekbaar, soms niet. Biologisch afbreekbaar betekent dat het materiaal ontbindt zoals organisch afval of keukenafval en dat het composteerbaar is.

- 14. Op termijn is het voorzien dat dunne plastic zakjes (flodderzakjes) voor zelfbediening van groenten en fruit in de supermarkt biologisch afbreekbaar en composteerbaar worden. Hoeveel zou u bereid zijn te betalen voor dit nieuwe soort zakjes?**

- 1= helemaal niets 4= 6 tot 10 cent per zakje
2= hooguit 2 cent per zakje 5= meer dan 10 cent per zakje
3= 3 tot 5 cent per zakje

Recycling van plastic afval

- 15. Hoe goed bent u op de hoogte van de afvalscheiding volgens de reglementering in uw gemeente (welke materialen moeten worden gerecycled, specifieke recyclingzakken, enz.)?**
- [Antwoord van 1 tot 10.]

- 16. Wordt het volgende afval in uw huishouden gescheiden?** (Geef een antwoord voor elk type afval, ongeacht het afvalinzamelsysteem in uw gemeente.)

- 1= neen
2= ja, maar niet erg zorgvuldig
3= ja, zeer zorgvuldig

- Metaal
- Plastic
- Drankverpakkingen/tetrapakken
- Glas
- Papier/karton
- Kleding
- Biologisch afval (bv. tuinafval, keukenafval, groente- en fruitafval)
- Frituurolie / plantaardige olie
- Geneesmiddelen

- Batterijen
- Ander gevaarlijk afval (bv. verf, lampen, elektronica of afval dat giftige componenten bevat)

Indien u in de vorige vraag bij elk type afval "3" hebt geantwoord, gaat u meteen verder met vraag 18.

- 17. Wat belet u om uw afval (zorgvuldiger) te scheiden?** (Kruis aan.)

- De inzamelpunten van alle types afval bevinden zich te ver van bij mij thuis
- De inzamelpunten van sommige types afval (bv. glas) bevinden zich te ver van bij mij thuis
- Gescheiden afval wordt niet aan huis opgehaald
- Afvalscheiding is te duur (kostprijs van de bakken, speciale inzamelzakken, enz.)
- Het is niet handig/praktisch om thuis zoveel afvalbakken/-zakken te hebben
- Ik weet niet hoe ik dat moet doen (gebrek aan informatie)
- Het is tijdrovend / het vergt te veel moeite
- Ik voel mij niet gemotiveerd omdat het afval dat ik produceer geen verschil zal maken
- Andere reden [Welke?]:

- 18. In welke mate bent u het eens met de volgende stellingen over de milieu-impact van plastic voor huishoudelijk gebruik?**

- 1= volkomen oneens
2= eerder oneens
3= noch eens noch oneens
4= eerder eens
5= volkomen eens

- Plastic voor huishoudelijk gebruik is een probleem voor de planeet
- Voor plastic voor huishoudelijk gebruik zijn veel natuurlijke grondstoffen nodig
- Enmaal afgedankt vormt plastic voor huishoudelijk gebruik afval dat niet kan worden hergebruikt
- Plastic voor huishoudelijk gebruik veroorzaakt risico's voor de voedselveiligheid
- Plastic voor huishoudelijk gebruik veroorzaakt gezondheidsrisico's
- De productie / het gebruik / het weggooien van plastic voor huishoudelijk gebruik is een van de belangrijkste oorzaken van vervuiling

- 19. Hoe vaak bewaart en hergebruikt u de volgende verpakkingen?**

- 1= nooit 4= meestal
2= zelden 5= altijd
3= soms

- Plastic schaalpje van vers vlees
- Plastic schaalpje van fruit/groenten

Plastic doosje van een bereide maaltijd

Plastic waterfles

Plastic flacon van schoonmaakmiddel/shampoo

Plastic draagtas

Nieuwe plasticsoorten

i Houd bij het beantwoorden van deze vragen het volgende voor ogen:

Biobased plastic, ook wel genoemd plastic van biologische oorsprong, wordt gemaakt van hernieuwbare grondstoffen (vergisting van granen, aardappelen, mais...). Soms is het biologisch afbreekbaar, soms niet. Biologisch afbreekbaar betekent dat het materiaal ontbindt zoals organisch afval of keukenafval en dat het composteerbaar is.

20. Zou u bij uw aankopen de voorkeur geven aan producten verpakt in de volgende nieuwe materialen?

- 1= neen
2= ja, maar het hangt van het product af
3= ja, sowieso

Biobased plastic (niet biologisch afbreekbaar)

Biologisch afbreekbaar plastic

Gerecycled plastic

21. Hoeveel zou u bereid zijn extra te betalen voor de volgende producten indien die in een biobased / biologisch afbreekbare verpakking zouden zitten?

- 1= helemaal niets
2= hooguit 5 cent
3= 6 tot 10 cent
4= 11 tot 15 cent
5= 16 tot 20 cent
6= meer dan 20 cent

Koffiecapsule

Vers vlees

Bereide maaltijd

Waspoeder

Shampoo/douchegel

22. Afval van biologisch afbreekbaar plastic moet worden gesorteerd bij het biologische afval (bv. tuinafval, keukenafval, groente- en fruitafval, enz.). Welke impact zou dit hebben op het afvalbeheer bij u thuis?

- 1= dat zou het moeilijker maken
2= dat zou nagenoeg niets veranderen
3= dat zou het makkelijker maken

23. In welke mate bent u op de hoogte van nieuwe plasticsoorten (biobased plastic / biologisch afbreekbaar plastic)?

- 1= totaal niet en het interesseert me ook niet
2= totaal niet, maar ik zou er graag meer over weten
3= een beetje op de hoogte
4= zeer goed op de hoogte

24. Hoeveel vertrouwen hebt u in de informatie over nieuwe plasticsoorten die wordt verstrekt door de volgende bronnen? [Antwoord van 1 tot 10.]

Fabrikant (bv. Fost Plus, op de verpakking van het product, op de website van het merk)

Supermarkt

Overheid (bv. Net Brussel, OVAM)

Onafhankelijke certificerende Instanties (bv. Vinçotte, label OK Compost, Ecolabel)

Media

Milieuorganisaties (bv. Greenpeace, Netwerk Bewust Verbruiken)

Verbruikersorganisatie (bv. Test-Aankoop)

Tot slot...

25. U bent een...

- 1= vrouw
2= man

26. Hoe oud bent u?

jaar

27. Wat is uw opleidingsniveau?

- 1= lager onderwijs of lager secundair onderwijs
2= hoger secundair onderwijs
3= hoger onderwijs of universitair onderwijs

28. Uit hoeveel personen bestaat uw huisgezin?

Totaal aantal volwassenen (uzelf meegerekend)

Totaal aantal personen van 12 à 17 Jaar

Totaal aantal personen van 4 à 11 Jaar

Totaal aantal personen < 4 Jaar

29. Hoe zou u uw financiële situatie omschrijven?

- 1= zeer moeilijk
2= moeilijk
3= voldoende om rond te komen
4= comfortabel
5= zeer comfortabel

30. Hoe zou u uw woonomgeving omschrijven?

- 1= stedelijk (stad)
2= voorstedelijk (stadsrand)
3= eerder landelijk (klein dorp)

31. In welke regio woont u?

- 1= Brussels Hoofdstedelijk Gewest
2= Vlaams Gewest
3= Waals Gewest

VAN HARTE DANK VOOR UW MEDEWERKING!

VAŠA ISKUSTVA S PLASTIČNIM AMBALAŽAMA

Bilo tko može ispuniti ovaj upitnik, neovisno o tome koliko često kupuje proizvode u plastičnoj ambalaži ili koristi plastične vrećice. Molimo vas da odgovarate samo na pitanja koja se odnose na vaše prilike.

VAŠ PROFIL

1. Prema Vašem mišljenju, koliko je važno obzirno ponašanje prema okolišu (odvajanje otpada, ušteda potrošnje energije, upotreba javnog prijevoza, konzumiranje organske hrane, itd.)?

- 1= nije mi uopće važno 3= važno mi je
2= nije mi jako važno 4= jako mi je važno

2. U kojoj mjeri provodite obzirno ponašanje prema okolišu?

- 1= ne poduzimam posebne aktivnosti
2= poduzimam neke aktivnosti
3= poduzimam mnogo aktivnosti

3. Prema Vašem mišljenju, ima li kućanski otpad stvarni utjecaj na okoliš?

- 1= nema nikakvog utjecaja 3= ponešto utječe
2= slabog je utjecaja 4= jakog je utjecaja

4. Iopćenito, koliko ste informirani o sljedećim pitanjima? [Ocjenite ocjenama od 1 do 10.]

Nacionalna politika, zakoni i ostali propisi o okolišu

EU politika i propisi o okolišu

Utjecaj onečišćenja na okoliš općenito

Utjecaj plastičnog otpada na okoliš

5. Koliki utjecaj imaju sljedeći čimbenici na Vašu odluku o kupnji svakodnevnih proizvoda, kao što su hrana, deterdženti, higijenski proizvodi, itd.? [Ocjenite ocjenama od 1 do 10.]

Cijena

Kvaliteta

Sastav

Porijeklo

Marka proizvođača

Značajke proizvoda

Dizajn proizvoda

Pakiranje

Lakoća korištenja

Posebna ponuda

Ekološke značajke (npr. zagađivači, organsko porijeklo)

PAKIRANJE PROIZVODA

6. Koliko često izbjegavate kupnju/upotrebu proizvoda s plastičnim sadržajem ili u plastičnoj ambalaži?

- 1= nikad
2= ponekad
3= uvijek

Proizvodi s plastičnim sadržajem

Proizvodi u plastičnoj ambalaži

i Pri odgovaranju na ovo pitanje, molimo obratite pozornost na:

Bioplastika ili plastika bio-porijekla proizvodi se iz obnovljivih izvora (fermentacijom žitarica, krumpira, kukuruza...). Može biti razgradiva ili ne. Razgradiva znači da se razlaže na organski/prehrambeni otpad i može se kompostirati.

7. Koju vrstu ambalaže biste odabrali pri kupnji sljedećih proizvoda? [Odaberite jednu opciju za svaki proizvod.]

• Kapsule za kavu

- 1= uobičajene plastične kapsule
2= plastične kapsule bio-porijekla (nerazgradive)
3= plastične kapsule bio-porijekla i biorazgradive
4= aluminijske kapsule
5= nemam preferencija

• Svježe meso (npr. piletina)

- 1= uobičajena plastična tacna (npr. polistiren)
2= plastična tacna bio-porijekla (nerazgradiva)
3= plastična tacna bio-porijekla i razgradiva
4= bez plastičnog pakovanja (npr u papiru)
5= nemam preferencija

• Pripremljena hrana (npr. obročna salata)

- 1= uobičajena plastična posuda (npr polistiren)
2= plastična posuda bio-porijekla (nerazgradiva)
3= plastična posuda bio-porijekla i razgradiva
4= ambalaža koja nije od plastike (npr. kartonska)
5= nemam preferencija

• Prašak za pranje rublja

- 1= uobičajena plastična vreća/kutija
 2= plastična vreća/kutija bio-porijekla (nerazgradiva)
 3= plastična vreća/kutija bio-porijekla i razgradiva
 4= uobičajena kartonska kutija
 5= nemam preferencija

• Gel za tuširanje / šampon

- 1= uobičajena plastična boca
 2= plastična boca bio-porijekla (nerazgradiva)
 3= ambalaža koja nije od plastike (npr staklena)
 4= nemam preferencija

8. Koje od sljedećih značajki pakiranja najviše cijenite na sljedećim proizvodima? [Označite jednu značajku po proizvodu.]

- 1= materijal, sastav
 2= veličina, težina i volumen
 3= dizajn (izgled, boja)
 4= oblik (lako obuhvatiti ili iskoristiti cijeli proizvod)
 5= praktičnost (npr. rukovanje proizvodom, transport, lijevak za točenje, zatvarač...)
 6= zaštita proizvoda
 7= ekološke značajke (npr. mogućnost ponovnog punjenja, recikliranje u potpunosti, materijal koji ne onečišćuje...)

Kapsule za kavu

Svježe meso

Pripremljena hrana

Deterdžent za pranje

Gel za tuširanje / Šampon

9. Koliko često zapažate sljedeće značajke pri kupnji svakodnevnih proizvoda sa plastičnom ambalažom?

- 1= nikad
 2= nekoliko puta
 3= ponekad
 4= uglavnom
 5= uvijek

Nepotrebno pakiranje jer je proizvod samodostatan

Preveliko pakiranje obzirom na količinu sadržaja

Pakiranje preteško obzirom na težinu proizvoda

Pakiranje nije spremno za rukovanje niti pristaje proizvodu

Pakiranje koje pruža dojam luksuznijeg proizvoda ili bolje kvalitete nego što jest

Pakiranje koje nije lako zgužvati za posudu za otpatke

Pakiranje koje ne štiti proizvod na pravilan način

Jednokratno pakiranje/ne može se ponovno koristiti ili napuniti

PLASTIČNE VREĆICE

10. Kada se radi o vrećicama za kupnju, kako obično postupate kada kupujete namirnice u supermarketima?

- 1= obično nosim vrećicu od doma (ponovno ih koristim nakon kupnje, ili koristim platnenu vrećicu)
 2= uglavnom kupujem novu vrećicu pri kupnji
 3= nosim vrećice od doma i kupujem nove
 4= ne koristim vrećice (npr. nosim proizvode u rukama, kolicima, kartonskim ili plastičnim kutijama) (ako je odgovor „4“, idite na pitanje 15)

i Pri odgovaranju na ovo pitanje, molimo obratite pozornost na:

Bioplastika ili plastika bio-porijekla proizvodi se iz obnovljivih izvora (fermentacijom žitarica, krumpira, kukuruza...). Može biti razgradiva ili ne. Razgradiva znači da se razlaže na organski/prehrambeni otpad i može se kompostirati.

11. Iz sljedećeg popisa materijala za vrećice, odaberite koji bi Vam najbolje odgovarao za kupnju namirnica?

- 1= obična plastika
 2= bioplastika (nerazgradiva)
 3= biorazgradiva plastika
 4= papir
 5= tekstil
 6= sintetička vlakna (npr. poliester)
 7= ostalo:
 8= nemam preferencija

12. Ocijenite svoje zadovoljstvo plastičnim vrećicama iz supermarketa ili trgovina obzirom na sljedeće značajke? [Ocjente ocjenama od 1 do 10.]

Veličina

Praktičnost

Cijena

Čvrstoća

Sveukupna ocjena

13. Koliko često doživite sljedeću situaciju kupujući namirnice?

- 1= nikad
 2= nekoliko puta
 3= ponekad
 4= uglavnom
 5= uvijek

Pokušavam smjestiti namirnice u što manje vrećica

Tražim čvršću ili veću vrećicu koja je skuplja

Nudi mi se čvršća ili veću vrećicu koja je skuplja

Tražim čvršću ili vrećicu koja se može ponovno koristiti, ali nije u ponudi

Nudi mi se izbor između lagane vrećice ili dugotrajne

Nudi mi se vrećica bio-porijekla (nerazgradiva)

Nudi mi se biorazgradiva vrećica

! Pri odgovaranju na ovo pitanje, molimo obratite pozornost na:

Bioplastika ili plastika bio-porijekla proizvodi se iz obnovljivih izvora (fermentacijom žitarica, krumpira, kukuruza...). Može biti razgradiva ili ne. Razgradiva znači da se razlaže na organski/prehrambeni otpad i može se kompostirati.

14. Koliko novaca biste bili voljni izdvojiti za plastičnu vrećicu bio-porijekla kada kupujete namirnice?

- 1= ništa
- 2= do 50 lipa po vrećici
- 3= 50 do 70 lipa po vrećici
- 4= 70 lipa do 1 kuna po vrećici
- 5= 1 kuna do 1.50 kuna po vrećici
- 6= više od 1.50 kuna po vrećici

Plastična vrećica bio-porijekla (nerazgradiva)

Biorazgradiva plastična vrećica

RECIKLIRANJE PLASTIČNOG OTPADA

15. Smatrate li da ste dovoljno informirani o lokalnim pravilima odvajanja otpada (koji materijali se mogu reciklirati, bojama kanti za otpatke, obradi otpada, krajnjem odredištu recikliranih materijala, cijenama reciklaže, itd.)?

[Ocjenite ocjenama od 1 do 10.]

16. Da li se u vašem kućanstvu odvaja sljedeći otpad?

[Molimo odgovorite za svaku vrstu otpada, bez obzira na lokalni sustav prikupljanja otpada.]

- 1= ne
- 2= da, ali ne u potpunosti
- 3= da, u potpunosti

Metal

Plastika

Tekuća pakiranja/tetrapak

Staklo

Papir/karton

Odjeća

Bio-otpud (npr. vrtni otpud, kuhinjski)

Ulje za kuhanje/biljno ulje/Medicinali

Lijekovi

Baterije

Ostali opasni materijali (npr. boja, žarulje, električni uređaji ili drugi koji sadrže toksične dijelove)

Ako ste odgovorili '3' za sve vrste otpada, nastavite na pitanju 18.

17. Što Vas onemogućava u potpunom odvajanju otpada?

[Označiti kvačicom.]

Sve posude za odvajanje otpada se nalaze podalje od moga doma

Neke vrste posuda za odvajanje otpada se nalaze podalje od moga doma

Odvojeni otpad se ne prikuplja po sistemu od vrata – do vrata

Odvajanje otpada je preskupo (cijena posuda, posebne vrećice za prikupljanje, itd.)

Nije praktično smjestiti toliko posuda/vreća za otpad u domu

Ne znam kako (nedovoljno informacija)

Oduzima previše vremena/previše posla

Nisam motiviran/a jer ne proizvodim toliko otpada da bi činio razliku

Drugo (obrazložite):

18. U kojoj mjeri se slažete sa sljedećim tvrdnjama o utjecaju plastike iz kućanstava na okoliš?

- 1= uopće se ne slažem
- 2= uglavnom se ne slažem
- 3= niti se slažem niti se ne slažem
- 4= uglavnom se slažem
- 5= u potpunosti se slažem

Plastika iz kućanstava je problem za planet

Plastika iz kućanstava troši mnogo prirodnih resursa

Jednom odbačena plastika je otpad koji se ne može ponovno koristiti

Plastika iz kućanstava proizvodi rizike za sigurnost hrane

Plastika iz kućanstava proizvodi rizik za zdravlje

Proizvoda/upotreba/plastični otpad iz kućanstava je jedan od bitnijih uzroka zagađenja

19. Koliko često sačuvate i ponovno koristite sljedeća pakiranja?

- 1= nikad
- 2= nekoliko puta
- 3= ponekad
- 4= uglavnom
- 5= uvijek

Plastičnu tacnu od svježeg mesa

Plastičnu tacnu od svježeg voća/povrća

Plastičnu posudu od gotovih jela

Plastičnu bocu za vodu

Plastične posude deterđženata/šampona

Plastičnu vrećicu

NOVI PLASTIČNI MATERIJALI

i Pri odgovaranju na ovo pitanje, molimo obratite pozornost na:

Bioplastika ili plastika bio-porijekla proizvodi se iz obnovljivih izvora (fermentacijom žitarica, krumpira, kukuruza...). Može biti razgradiva ili ne.

Razgradiva znači da se razlaže na organski/prehrambeni otpad i može se kompostirati.

20. Pri kupnji, da li biste dali prednost proizvodima pakiranima od u sljedećim novim materijala?

- 1= nemam preferencija
2= da, ovisno o proizvodima
3= da u svakom slučaju

Plastika bio-porijekla (nerazgradiva) (118)

Biorazgradiva plastika (119)

Reciklirana plastika (120)

21. Koji biste dodatni iznos bili spremni izdvojiti za kupnju navedenih proizvoda u biorazgradivoj ambalaži?

- 1= ništa
2= najviše 50 lipa
3= 50 do 70 lipa
4= 70 lipa do 1 kune
5= 1 kune do 1.50 kuna
6= više od 1.50 kuna

Kapsule za kavu (121)

Svježe meso (122)

Pripremljena hrana (123)

Deterdžent za pranje (124)

Gel za tuširanje / Šampon (125)

22. Otpad s biorazgradivom plastikom treba se odvajati s bio-otpadom. Kakav bi učinak navedeno imalo na vaše navike odvajanja otpada?

- 1= otežalo bi ih
2= bilo bi jednako kao i sada
3= olakšalo bi ih

23. Koliko smatrate da ste informirani o novim plastičnim materijalima (bioplastici/ biorazgradivoj plastici)? (126)

- 1= nisam previše, ne zanima me
2= nisam previše, ali želim se informirati
3= ponešto sam informiran/a
4= dobro sam informiran/a

24. Koliko povjerenja imate u informacije o novim plastičnim materijalima kada se informirate iz sljedećih izvora? [Ocijenite ocjenama od 1 do 10.]

Proizvođač (npr. navodi na pakiranju, web proizvođača) (127)

Supermarket (128)

Javna uprava (npr. prema državi) (129)

Certifikati neovisnih ustanova (npr. Ok compost, Ecolabel) (130)

Mediji (131)

Ekološke udruge (npr. Greenpeace) (132)

Udruge potrošača (npr. u državi) (133)

ZA KRAJ...

25. Spol: (134)

1= žensko

2= muško

26. Dob: (135) godina starosti

27. Obrazovanje: [Razina koju ste postigli (dosad.)] (136)

- 1= osnovna škola
2= srednja škola
3= fakultet
4= magisterij/doktorat
5= ostalo

28. Članovi Vašega kućanstva:

Br. osoba (uključujući Vas) (137)

Br. osoba 12-17 godina starosti (138)

Br. osoba 4-11 godina starosti (139)

Br. osoba < 4 godina starosti (140)

29. Vaša financijska situacija: (141)

- 1= veoma teška
2= teška
3= dovoljna za osnovne potrebe
4= zadovoljavajuća
5= vrlo zadovoljavajuća

30. Mjesto stanovanja: (142)

- 1= urbano/grad
2= djelomično urbano/predgrađe
3= ruralno/manji grad ili selo

31. Poštanski broj: (143)

ZAHVALJUJEMO NA SURADNJI!

Country code (144)

LA SUA ESPERIENZA CON LE CONFEZIONI DI PLASTICA

Questo questionario può essere compilato da chiunque, a prescindere dalla frequenza con cui utilizza prodotti confezionati o sacchetti di plastica. La preghiamo di rispondere solo alle domande che si applicano alla sua situazione, seguendo le Istruzioni Indicate.

Il suo profilo personale

1. Secondo lei, quanto è importante avere un comportamento amico dell'ambiente (separare i rifiuti, ridurre l'uso di elettricità e acqua, utilizzare il trasporto pubblico, ecc.)?

1= per nulla importante 3= abbastanza importante
2= poco importante 4= molto importante

2. Fa delle azioni specifiche per avere un comportamento rispettoso dell'ambiente?

1= nessuna azione specifica
2= qualche azione specifica
3= molte azioni specifiche

3. Fino a che punto ritiene che la produzione di rifiuti dentro le mura domestiche abbia un impatto significativo sull'ambiente?

1= nessun impatto 3= qualche impatto
2= poco impatto 4= forte impatto

4. In genere, quanto ritiene di essere bene informata/o riguardo ai seguenti temi? [Risponda da 1 a 10.]

Politiche e leggi nazionali di salvaguardia dell'ambiente

Politiche e leggi europee di salvaguardia dell'ambiente

Impatto che l'inquinamento ha sull'ambiente

Impatto che i rifiuti in plastica hanno sull'ambiente

5. Quando compra oggetti di uso quotidiano (cibo, prodotti per la casa, cosmetici, ecc.), quanto influisce ciascuno dei seguenti aspetti, sulla scelta del prodotto da acquistare? [Risponda da 1 a 10.]

Il prezzo

La qualità

La composizione, le materie prime

L'origine

La marca

Le caratteristiche del prodotto

L'aspetto/ Il design del prodotto

La confezione

La facilità d'uso / Praticità

Promozioni e offerte

Sostenibilità ambientale (privo di inquinanti, pesticidi, ecc.)

Le confezioni dei prodotti

6. Le capita di evitare di acquistare/utilizzare un prodotto perchè contiene parti in plastica o perchè la confezione è di plastica?

1= no, mai
2= sì, a volte
3= sì, sempre

Prodotti con parti in plastica

Prodotti con confezione di plastica

! Nel rispondere, faccia riferimento alle seguenti definizioni:

La **BIOPLASTICA** è un materiale del tutto simile nell'aspetto alla plastica tradizionale, ma che è ottenuto da materie prime vegetali (cereali, amido, mais,...). Può essere o meno biodegradabile. Un materiale è **BIODEGRADABILE** se si degrada come i rifiuti organici e può essere avviato a compostaggio.

7. Che tipo di confezione sceglierebbe, se dovesse acquistare uno dei seguenti prodotti? [Selezioni una opzione per ciascun prodotto.]

• **Caffè in capsule**

1= capsule in plastica tradizionale
2= capsule in bioplastica (non biodegradabili)
3= capsule biodegradabili
4= capsule di alluminio
5= nessuna preferenza

• **Carne confezionata**

1= vaschetta tradizionale (in polistirene)
2= vaschetta in bioplastica (non biodegradabile)
3= vaschetta biodegradabile
4= vaschetta in altro materiale (es. carta)
5= nessuna preferenza

• **Cibo pronto confezionato**

1= vaschetta in plastica tradizionale
2= vaschetta in bioplastica (non biodegradabile)
3= vaschetta biodegradabile
4= vaschetta in altro materiale (non plastica)
5= nessuna preferenza

• **Detersivo per lavatrice in polvere**

- 1= scatola/sacco in plastica tradizionale
- 2= scatola/sacco in bioplastica (non biodegradabile)
- 3= scatola/sacco biodegradabile
- 4= scatola in cartone
- 5= nessuna preferenza

• **Shampoo / Docciaschiuma**

- 1= flacone in plastica tradizionale
- 2= flacone in bioplastica (non biodegradabile)
- 3= flacone in altro materiale (es. vetro)
- 4= nessuna preferenza

8. Quale aspetto ritiene più importante, nella scelta dei seguenti prodotti? [Selezioni un aspetto per ciascun prodotto.]

- 1= composizione/ materie prime
- 2= dimensioni, peso, volume
- 3= design (estetica, colore)
- 4= forma (facile da prendere, giusta quantità di prodotto, ecc.)
- 5= praticità d'uso (facile da maneggiare e da trasportare, provvisto di beccuccio antigoccia, ecc.)
- 6= protezione dell'integrità del prodotto
- 7= sostenibilità ambientale (riutilizzabile, riciclabile, privo di componenti tossici, ecc.)

Capsule da caffè	<input type="checkbox"/>
Carne confezionata	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cibo pronto confezionato	<input type="checkbox"/>
Detersivo per lavatrice in polvere	<input type="checkbox"/>
Shampoo / Docciaschiuma	<input type="checkbox"/>

9. Quanto spesso le è capitata ciascuna delle seguenti situazioni, con prodotti di uso quotidiano confezionati in plastica?

- 1= mai
- 2= raramente
- 3= di tanto in tanto
- 4= la maggior parte delle volte
- 5= sempre

La confezione non è necessaria perché il prodotto si potrebbe acquistare sciolto	<input type="checkbox"/>
La confezione è troppo grande rispetto alle dimensioni del prodotto	<input type="checkbox"/>
La confezione è troppo pesante rispetto al peso del prodotto in sé	<input type="checkbox"/>
La confezione non è maneggevole o adatta al prodotto	<input type="checkbox"/>
La confezione dà l'impressione che il prodotto sia di migliore qualità di quello che è	<input type="checkbox"/>
La confezione non è semplice da appiattire e buttare via	<input type="checkbox"/>
La confezione non è adatta a conservare correttamente il prodotto	<input type="checkbox"/>
La confezione è usa e getta, non è riutilizzabile	<input type="checkbox"/>

Sacchetti di plastica

10. Quando si reca al supermercato, quale delle seguenti situazioni si verifica più spesso?

- 1= porto sacchetti da casa (riutilizzando sacchetti di un acquisto precedente o portando borse di stoffa)
- 2= acquisto i sacchetti del supermercato
- 3= utilizzo sia i sacchetti del supermercato che quelli che porto da casa
- 4= non utilizzo sacchetti (porto le cose a mano, in scatole di cartone, nel trolley per la spesa, ecc.) [scriva '4' e vada alla domanda 15]

11. Quale tipo di sacchetti preferisce utilizzare, quando fa la spesa al supermercato?

- 1= sacchetti di plastica tradizionale
- 2= sacchetti biodegradabili
- 3= sacchetti di carta
- 4= sacchetti di stoffa
- 5= sacchetti in fibra sintetica (ad es. poliestere)
- 6= altro [specificare]:
- 7= nessuna preferenza

12. Quanto è soddisfatta/o dei seguenti aspetti dei sacchetti di plastica dei supermercati? [Risponda da 1 a 10.]

Dimensioni	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Praticità d'uso	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Prezzo	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Resistenza	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Soddisfazione complessiva	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

13. Quanto spesso le capita di trovarsi in ciascuna delle seguenti situazioni, quando fa la spesa al supermercato?

- 1= mai
- 2= raramente
- 3= di tanto in tanto
- 4= la maggior parte delle volte
- 5= sempre

Cerco di far entrare la spesa nel minor numero di sacchetti possibile	<input type="checkbox"/>
Chiedo un sacchetto più grande o più resistente, che costa di più di quello standard	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mi propongono di acquistare un sacchetto più grande o più resistente, che costa di più di quello standard	<input type="checkbox"/>
Chiedo un sacchetto più resistente o riutilizzabile (ad es. di stoffa) ma non è disponibile	<input type="checkbox"/>

14. Da gennaio 2018 anche i sacchetti per il self-service della frutta e verdura al supermercato saranno biodegradabili. Quanto sarebbe disposta/o a pagare in più, per utilizzare questo nuovo tipo di sacchetti?

- 1= nulla
- 2= non più di 2 centesimi a sacchetto
- 3= tra 3 e 5 centesimi a sacchetto
- 4= tra 6 e 10 centesimi a sacchetto
- 5= più di 10 centesimi a sacchetto

Il riciclo della plastica

15. Quanto ritiene di essere bene informata/o riguardo alle regole sul riciclo dei rifiuti del suo comune (quali materiali sono riciclabili e quali no, come vanno smaltiti, ecc.)? [Risponda da 1 a 10.]

16. In casa sua, fa la raccolta differenziata dei seguenti rifiuti? [Risponda per ciascun materiale, anche nel caso in cui non fosse prevista la raccolta differenziata nel suo comune.]

- 1= no
- 2= sì, ma non in modo accurato
- 3= sì, in modo accurato

Metalli	<input type="checkbox"/>
Plastica	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cartone per bibite	<input type="checkbox"/>
Vetro	<input type="checkbox"/>
Carta	<input type="checkbox"/>
Abiti	<input type="checkbox"/>
Organico	<input type="checkbox"/>
Olio alimentare esausto	<input type="checkbox"/>
Medicinali	<input type="checkbox"/>
Batterie	<input type="checkbox"/>
Altro rifiuto pericoloso (ad es. elettronica, vernice, ecc)	<input type="checkbox"/>

Se ha risposto '3' per tutti i tipi di rifiuto, vada direttamente alla domanda 18.

17. Per quale motivo non separa (in modo accurato) i rifiuti? [Selezioni tutte le opzioni che si applicano al suo caso.]

Tutti i contenitori per la differenziata sono troppo lontani da casa mia

Alcuni contenitori per la differenziata sono troppo lontani da casa mia

Non c'è la raccolta porta a porta della differenziata

Fare la raccolta differenziata costa troppo (costo dei bidoni, dei sacchetti, ecc.)

È scomodo avere tanti contenitori diversi a casa

Mancanza di informazioni

È complicato, perdo troppo tempo

Mancanza di motivazione, in quanto i rifiuti che io produco non faranno certo la differenza

Altro [specificare]:

18. Quanto è d'accordo con ciascuna delle seguenti affermazioni, riguardo all'impatto ambientale dei rifiuti in plastica prodotti in casa?

- 1= completamente in disaccordo
- 2= abbastanza in disaccordo
- 3= né d'accordo né in disaccordo
- 4= abbastanza d'accordo
- 5= completamente d'accordo

I rifiuti in plastica prodotti in casa sono un problema per il pianeta

La produzione di imballaggi/confezioni in plastica consuma troppe risorse naturali

Gli imballaggi/confezioni in plastica sono usa e getta (non possono essere riutilizzati più volte)

Gli imballaggi/confezioni in plastica non sono sicuri per il contatto con gli alimenti

Gli imballaggi/confezioni in plastica rappresentano un rischio per la salute

I rifiuti in plastica prodotti in casa sono una delle maggiori fonti di inquinamento

19. Quanto spesso le capita di riutilizzare i seguenti tipi di confezioni di plastica?

- 1= mai
- 2= raramente
- 3= a volte
- 4= la maggior parte delle volte
- 5= sempre

Vaschette in plastica della carne

Vaschette in plastica di frutta e verdura

Contenitori di plastica di cibo pronto confezionato

Bottiglie di acqua

Flaconi di detersivo/shampoo

Sacchetti di plastica

Materiali innovativi in plastica

I Nel rispondere, faccia riferimento alle seguenti definizioni:
 La **BIOPLASTICA** è un materiale del tutto simile nell'aspetto alla plastica tradizionale, ma che è ottenuto da materie prime vegetali (cereali, amido, mais,...). Può essere o meno biodegradabile.
 Un materiale è **BIODEGRADABILE** se si degrada come i rifiuti organici e può essere avviato a compostaggio.

20. Preferirebbe acquistare un prodotto la cui confezione fosse fatta di...?

- 1= nessuna preferenza
 2= sì, ma dipende dal prodotto
 3= sì, a prescindere dal prodotto

Bioplastica (non biodegradabile)

Bioplastica biodegradabile

Plastica riciclata

21. Quanto sarebbe disposta/o a pagare in più per acquistare un prodotto la cui confezione fosse fatta di bioplastica (non biodegradabile) o di bioplastica biodegradabile?

- 1= nulla
 2= non più di 5 centesimi
 3= tra 6 e 10 centesimi
 4= tra 11 e 15 centesimi
 5= tra 16 e 20 centesimi
 6= più di 20 centesimi

Capsule da caffè

Carne confezionata

Cibo pronto confezionato

Detersivo per lavatrice in polvere

Shampoo / Docciaschiuma

22. I rifiuti in bioplastica biodegradabile devono essere smaltiti assieme ai rifiuti organici (ad es. residui di cibo, scarti di potatura, ecc.). Che impatto avrebbe sulla sua gestione dei rifiuti domestici?

- 1= renderebbe la gestione dei rifiuti domestici più difficoltosa
 2= non cambierebbe di molto
 3= renderebbe la gestione dei rifiuti domestici più semplice

23. Fino a che punto ritiene di essere informata/o riguardo ai materiali innovativi in plastica (bioplastica/ biodegradabile)?

- 1= per nulla e non mi interessa
 2= per nulla, ma mi piacerebbe saperne di più
 3= poco informata/o
 4= bene informata/o

24. Quanta fiducia ha nelle informazioni sui nuovi prodotti in plastica, che le forniscono le seguenti fonti di informazione? [Risponda da 1 a 10.]

Il produttore (ad es. sulla confezione del prodotto, nel sito web del produttore)

Il commerciante (ad es. sugli scaffali dei supermercati)

Il Ministero dell'Ambiente

Istituti di certificazione ambientale (ad es. EcoLabel, OK Compost)

I media

Organizzazioni ambientaliste (ad es. Legambiente, Greenpeace)

Associazioni di difesa dei consumatori

E per finire...

25. Sesso:

- 1= femmina 2= maschio

26. Età:

anni

27. Quale titolo di studio ha conseguito:

- 1= nessuno/licenza elementare
 2= licenza di scuola media inferiore (o licenza di avviamento professionale)
 3= licenza di scuola media superiore
 4= laurea (o superiore)

28. Da quante persone è composto il suo nucleo familiare?

Numero di adulti (lei inclusa/o)

Numero di persone di 12-17 anni

Numero di persone di 4-11 anni

Numero di persone minori di 4 anni

29. Qual è la sua situazione economica/finanziaria?

- 1= molto difficile
 2= difficile
 3= sufficiente a far quadrare i conti
 4= agevole
 5= molto agevole

30. Come descriverebbe la zona in cui abita?

- 1= urbana (città)
 2= semi-urbana (periferia, sobborgo, ecc.)
 3= semi-rurale / rurale (campagna, montagna, ecc.)

31. In che regione abita?

- 1= Abruzzo
 2= Basilicata
 3= Calabria
 4= Campania
 5= Emilia-Romagna
 6= Friuli-Venezia Giulia
 7= Lazio
 8= Liguria
 9= Lombardia
 10= Marche
 11= Molise
 12= Piemonte
 13= Puglia
 14= Sardegna
 15= Sicilia
 16= Toscana
 17= Trentino-Alto Adige
 18= Umbria
 19= Valle d'Aosta
 20= Veneto

GRAZIE PER LA COLLABORAZIONE!

Codice nazionale

A SUA EXPERIÊNCIA COM EMBALAGENS DE PLÁSTICO

Este questionário pode ser respondido por qualquer pessoa, independentemente da frequência com que compra produtos com embalagens de plástico ou utiliza sacos de plástico. Basta responder às questões ou secções que se aplicam à sua experiência.

0 seu perfil

1. Até que ponto considera importante ter um bom desempenho ambiental (separar o lixo, reduzir o consumo de energia e de água, utilizar transportes públicos, preferir alimentos oriundos de agricultura sustentável, etc.)?

1= nada importante 3= algo importante
2= não muito importante 4= muito importante

2. Até que ponto toma a iniciativa de pôr em prática um bom desempenho ambiental?

1= não tomo nenhuma iniciativa em particular
2= tomo algumas iniciativas
3= tomo muitas iniciativas

3. Até que ponto considera que os resíduos domésticos têm um impacto importante no meio ambiente?

1= não têm qualquer impacto 3= têm algum impacto
2= têm um pequeno impacto 4= têm um grande impacto

4. No geral, até que ponto se sente informado/a sobre os seguintes aspetos? [Responda de 1 a 10.]

Políticas e legislação ambientais nacionais

Políticas e legislação ambientais da União Europeia

Impacto da poluição em geral no meio ambiente

Impacto dos resíduos plásticos no meio ambiente

5. Que influência tem cada um dos seguintes aspetos na sua decisão de compra de produtos de uso corrente, como alimentação, detergentes, produtos de higiene, etc.? [Responda de 1 a 10.]

Preço

Qualidade

Composição

Origem

Marca (reputação)

Características do produto

Aspetto / design

Embalagem

Facilidade de utilização

Promoções/ofertas

Aspetos ambientais (por ex. ingredientes com reduzido impacto ambiental, alimentos provenientes de agricultura sustentável)

Embalagens

6. Evita comprar/utilizar produtos com plástico ou com embalagem de plástico?

1= não, nunca
2= sim, algumas vezes
3= sim, sempre

Produtos com plástico

Produtos embalados em plástico

i Quando responder à pergunta seguinte, tenha em atenção as seguintes definições:

O plástico de origem biológica é feito a partir de recursos renováveis (cereais fermentados, batatas, milho,...). Pode ser biodegradável ou não.

Biodegradável significa que se decompõe em matéria orgânica, podendo esta ser usada como composto, um fertilizante natural.

7. Que tipo de embalagem escolheria ao comprar os seguintes produtos? (Indique uma opção para cada produto.)

• Cápsulas de café

1= cápsulas de plástico convencional
2= cápsulas em plástico de origem biológica não biodegradável
3= cápsulas em plástico biodegradável
4= cápsulas de alumínio
5= sem preferência

• Carne fresca (por ex. frango)

1= tabuleiro de plástico convencional (por ex. esferovite)
2= tabuleiro em plástico de origem biológica não biodegradável
3= tabuleiro em plástico biodegradável
4= embalagem sem plástico (por ex. cartão)
5= sem preferência

• Comida preparada (por ex. refeição de salada)

- 1= embalagem de plástico convencional
- 2= embalagem de plástico de origem biológica não biodegradável
- 3= embalagem de plástico biodegradável
- 4= embalagem sem ser de plástico (por ex. cartão)
- 5= sem preferência

• Detergente em pó para a máquina de lavar roupa

- 1= saco de plástico convencional
- 2= saco de plástico de origem biológica não biodegradável
- 3= saco de plástico biodegradável
- 4= caixa de cartão / saco de papel
- 5= sem preferência

• Champô / gel de banho

- 1= frasco de plástico convencional
- 2= frasco em plástico de origem biológica não biodegradável
- 3= frasco sem ser de plástico (por ex. vidro)
- 4= sem preferência

8. Quais dos seguintes aspetos relativos à embalagem mais valoriza em cada um dos produtos listados em baixo? [Indique apenas um aspeto por tipo de produto.]

- 1= tipo de material
- 2= tamanho, peso ou volume
- 3= design (aspeto, cor)
- 4= forma (facilidade em se adaptar ao produto e utilizar todo o seu conteúdo)
- 5= facilidade de utilização (transporte, manuseamento da embalagem, acesso ou doseamento do produto, etc.)
- 6= protecção do produto
- 7= aspetos ambientais (por ex. pode ser recarregado, totalmente reciclável, material com reduzido impacto ambiental,...)

Cápsulas de café

Came fresca

Comida preparada

Detergente em pó para a máquina de lavar roupa

Champô / gel de banho

9. Com que frequência se depara com as seguintes situações quando compra produtos de uso corrente embalados em plástico?

- 1= nunca
- 2= poucas vezes
- 3= algumas vezes
- 4= a maior parte das vezes
- 5= sempre

Embalagem desnecessária (o produto não precisa de embalagem)

Embalagem demasiado grande para o tamanho do produto

Embalagem muito pesada, dado o peso do produto

Embalagem difícil de manusear ou mal adaptada ao produto

Embalagem que transmite uma imagem luxuosa do produto ou de maior qualidade do que na verdade é

Embalagem difícil de comprimir para ocupar menos espaço no caixote do lixo ou da reciclagem

Embalagem que não protege/preserva o produto convenientemente

Embalagem de utilização única / que não pode ser reutilizada

Sacos de plástico

10. No que diz respeito ao transporte das compras, como costuma proceder quando vai ao supermercado?

- 1= na maioria das vezes levo sacos de casa (reutilizo de anteriores compras ou recorro a sacos de materiais resistentes, como tecido)
- 2= na maioria das vezes compro sacos (novos) no supermercado
- 3= tanto levo sacos de casa como os compro no supermercado
- 4= não utilizo sacos (por ex. levo os produtos na mão, num carrinho de compras ou utilizo caixas de cartão/plástico) [escreva '4' e passe diretamente à pergunta 15]

! Quando responder à pergunta seguinte, tenha em atenção as seguintes definições:

O plástico de origem biológica é feito a partir de recursos renováveis (cereais fermentados, batatas, milho,...). Pode ser biodegradável ou não. Biodegradável significa que se decompõe em matéria orgânica, podendo esta ser usada como composto, um fertilizante natural.

11. Da lista de materiais em baixo, qual escolheria para utilizar como saco de compras quando vai ao supermercado?

- 1= plástico convencional
- 2= plástico de origem biológica não biodegradável
- 3= plástico biodegradável
- 4= papel
- 5= têxtil
- 6= fibra sintética (ráfia)
- 7= outro (especifique):
- 8= sem preferência

12. Até que ponto está satisfeito/a com os sacos de plástico que compra no supermercado no que diz respeito aos seguintes aspetos? [Responda de 1 a 10.]

Tamanho

Facilidade de utilização

Preço

Resistência

Satisfação global

Document:	D2.6 Summary of the state of play of the demo cases using the CEIS		
Author:	CIRCE	Version	final
Reference:	D2.6	Date:	17/12/18

13. Com que frequência se depara com as seguintes situações quando vai ao supermercado?

- 1= nunca
2= poucas vezes
3= algumas vezes
4= muitas vezes
5= sempre

Tentar colocar as compras no menor número de sacos possível

Pedir um saco maior e mais resistente, que é mais caro

Proporem-lhe um saco maior e mais resistente, que é mais caro

Pedir um saco mais resistente (reutilizável) e não estar disponível

i Quando responder à pergunta seguinte, tenha em atenção as seguintes definições:

O plástico de origem biológica é feito a partir de recursos renováveis (cereais fermentados, batatas, milho,...). Pode ser biodegradável ou não.

Biodegradável significa que se decompõe em matéria orgânica, podendo esta ser usada como composto, um fertilizante natural.

14. Quanto estaria disposto/a a pagar por um saco de plástico de origem biológica quando vai ao supermercado?

- 1= não estou disposto/a a pagar
2= não mais de 5 céntimos por saco
3= 6 a 10 céntimos por saco
4= 11 a 15 céntimos por saco
5= 16 a 20 céntimos por saco
6= mais de 20 céntimos por saco

Saco de plástico de origem biológica não biodegradável

Saco de plástico biodegradável

Reciclagem do plástico

15. Até que ponto se sente informado/a sobre a separação de resíduos no seu município (que materiais podem ser reciclados, as cores dos contentores de reciclagem, tratamento de resíduos, destino final dos materiais recolhidos separadamente, taxas de reciclagem do seu município, etc.)? [Responda de 1 a 10.]

16. Na sua casa separam-se os seguintes tipos de resíduos? [Responda, por favor, para cada tipo de material, independentemente do tipo de separação feita pelo seu município.]

- 1= não
2= sim, mas nem sempre de forma rigorosa
3= sim, de forma rigorosa

Metal

Plástico

Embalagens de cartão para alimentos líquidos / Tetrapak

Vidro

Papel/cartão

Roupa

Lixo orgânico (por ex. restos de alimentos ou resíduos do jardim)

Óleo alimentar / óleo vegetal

Medicamentos

Pilhas

Outros resíduos perigosos (tintas, lâmpadas, aparelhos eletrónicos,...)

Se, na pergunta anterior, respondeu '3' para todo o tipo de resíduos, passe diretamente à pergunta 18.

17. O que o/a impede de separar os resíduos de forma (mais) correta? [Assinale as opções que se aplicam ao seu caso.]

Todos os contentores de separação de resíduos ficam demasiado longe da minha casa

Alguns dos contentores de separação de resíduos (por ex. vidro) ficam demasiado longe da minha casa

Não existe recolha porta-a-porta dos resíduos separados

A separação dos resíduos é muito cara (custo dos ecopontos domésticos, sacos específicos para a recolha, etc.)

Não é prático / não tenho espaço para ter tantos ecopontos domésticos / sacos

Não sei como fazê-lo (falta de informação)

Perde-se tempo / dá muito trabalho

Não estou motivado/a a fazê-lo porque o lixo que produzo não é relevante / não faz a diferença

Outra razão [especifique]:

18. Até que ponto concorda com cada uma das seguintes frases relativamente ao impacto ambiental do plástico de uso doméstico?

- 1= discordo completamente
2= discordo
3= não concordo nem discordo
4= concordo
5= concordo completamente

O plástico de uso doméstico é um problema para o planeta

O plástico de uso doméstico consome muitos recursos naturais

Depois de deitado fora, o plástico de uso doméstico é um resíduo que não pode ser reutilizado

O plástico de uso doméstico oferece riscos para a segurança alimentar

O plástico de uso doméstico gera riscos para a saúde

A produção / utilização / fim de vida do plástico de uso doméstico é uma das principais fontes de poluição

SU EXPERIENCIA CON LOS ENVASES DE PLÁSTICO

Todo el mundo puede responder este cuestionario sin importar con qué frecuencia compre productos con envoltorios plásticos o use bolsas de plástico. Deberá responder únicamente aquellas preguntas o secciones que se ajusten a su experiencia.

Su perfil

1. Según usted, ¿hasta qué punto es importante tener un buen comportamiento ecológico (separar los residuos, reducir el consumo de energía, ahorrar agua, usar el transporte público, comer alimentos ecológicos, etc.)?

1= nada importante 3= algo importante
2= no muy importante 4= muy importante

2. ¿En qué medida hace algo para llevar a cabo un buen comportamiento ecológico?

1= no hago ninguna acción específica
2= hago algunas acciones
3= hago muchas acciones

3. ¿Hasta qué punto cree usted que los residuos domésticos tienen un impacto real en el medio ambiente?

1= ningún impacto 3= algún impacto
2= impacto muy pequeño 4= gran impacto

4. En general, ¿en qué medida se siente informado sobre los siguientes temas? [Anoté una respuesta de 1 a 10.]

Políticas y legislación nacional en materia de medio ambiente

Políticas y legislación medioambiental de la UE

Impacto ambiental de la contaminación (en general)

Impacto ambiental de los residuos plásticos

5. ¿Hasta qué punto influye cada uno de los siguientes aspectos en su decisión a la hora de comprar un determinado producto de consumo cotidiano como comida, detergentes, productos de higiene, etc.? [Anoté una respuesta de 1 a 10.]

El precio

La calidad

La composición

El origen

La marca (reputación)

Características del producto

La apariencia / diseño

El embalaje

Facilidad de uso / conveniencia

Promociones / ofertas

Aspectos medioambientales (p.ej. contaminantes, alimentos ecológicos)

Embalaje

6. ¿Evita comprar / usar productos que contengan plástico o con envase de plástico?

1= nunca
2= sí, a veces
3= siempre

Productos que contengan plástico

Productos con envase de plástico

! Cuando vaya a responder la siguiente pregunta tenga en cuenta:

Llamamos plásticos biológicos a aquellos que se obtienen de fuentes renovables (fermentación de cereales, patatas, maíz...) y no son necesariamente biodegradables, pueden serlo o no. Llamamos biodegradables a los que se descomponen como la materia orgánica/alimentos y pueden ser compostados.

7. ¿Qué tipo de embalaje elegiría al comprar los siguientes productos? [Por favor seleccione una única opción para cada producto.]

- Cápsulas de café

1= cápsula de plástico convencional
2= cápsula de plástico biológico (no biodegradable)
3= cápsula de plástico biodegradable
4= cápsula de aluminio
5= no tiene preferencia

- Carne fresca (p.ej. pollo)

1= bandeja de plástico convencional (p.ej. poliestireno)
2= bandeja de plástico biológico (no biodegradable)
3= bandeja de plástico biodegradable
4= otro material que no sea plástico (p.ej. papel)
5= no tiene preferencia

- Comida preparada (p.ej. una ensalada lista para comer)

1= un envase de plástico convencional (p.ej. poliestireno)
2= un envase de plástico biológico (no biodegradable)
3= un envase de plástico biodegradable
4= un envase que no sea plástico (p.ej. cartón)
5= no tiene preferencia

• **Detergente para lavadora en polvo**

- 1= bolsa de plástico convencional
- 2= bolsa/caja de plástico biológico (no biodegradable)
- 3= bolsa/caja de plástico biodegradable
- 4= caja de cartón convencional
- 5= no tiene preferencia

• **Champú/gel de baño**

- 1= envase de de plástico convencional
- 2= envase de plástico biológico (no biodegradable)
- 3= envase de otro material que no sea plástico (p.ej. cristal)
- 4= no tiene preferencia

8. ¿Qué aspectos del embalaje valora usted más en cada uno de los siguientes productos? (Indique únicamente un aspecto por cada producto.)

- 1= el material, la composición
- 2= el tamaño, peso o volumen
- 3= el diseño (apariencia, color)
- 4= forma (facilidad para aprovechar todo el contenido)
- 5= conveniencia (manejo del producto, transporte, etc.)
- 6= protección del producto
- 7= aspectos medioambientales (p.ej. se puede reutilizar, es completamente reciclable, es de material no contaminante ...)

Cápsulas de café

Carne fresca

Comida preparada

Detergente en polvo para lavadoras

Champú/gel de baño

9. ¿Con qué frecuencia observa las siguientes situaciones cuando compra productos de uso cotidiano con envases de plástico?

- 1= nunca
- 2= rara vez
- 3= algunas veces
- 4= la mayoría de las veces
- 5= siempre

Embalaje innecesario porque el producto no lo necesita

Embalaje demasiado grande teniendo en cuenta el tamaño del producto

Embalaje demasiado pesado teniendo en cuenta el peso del producto en sí

Embalaje que no es práctico o no se ajusta bien al producto

Embalaje que da una impresión de lujo o de mayor calidad de lo que es

Embalaje que no es fácil de comprimir y desechar

Embalaje que no protege / conserva el producto correctamente

Embalaje que es para un solo uso / no apto para volver a usar o rellenarlo

Bolsas de plástico

10. Respecto a las bolsas de la compra, ¿qué suele usted hacer generalmente cuando va a la compra al supermercado?

- 1= suelo llevar bolsas de casa (de otras compras anteriores o de tela)
- 2= suelo usar las que me dan (o me venden) en el propio super
- 3= suelo llevar alguna de casa y además suelo tener que utilizar las que me dan/venden en el super
- 4= no utilizo bolsas (p.ej. llevo los productos en un carro de la compra, "en mano" o utilizo cajas de cartón) [anote '4' y continúe en la pregunta 15]

! Cuando vaya a responder la siguiente pregunta tenga en cuenta:

Llamamos plásticos biológicos a aquellos que se obtienen de fuentes renovables (fermentación de cereales, patatas, maíz...) y no son necesariamente biodegradables, pueden serlo o no. Llamamos biodegradables a los que se descomponen como la materia orgánica/alimentos y pueden ser compostados.

11. De los siguientes materiales con los que es posible fabricar una bolsa de la compra, ¿cuál preferiría usted utilizar?

- 1= plástico convencional
- 2= plástico biológico (no biodegradable)
- 3= plástico biodegradable
- 4= papel
- 5= tela
- 6= fibra sintética (p.ej. poliéster)
- 7= otro material [especificar]:
- 8= no tengo preferencia

12. ¿Cuál es su nivel de satisfacción general con las bolsas de plástico que le venden en su supermercado habitual en los siguientes aspectos? (Añote una respuesta de 1 a 10.)

Tamaño

Facilidad de uso

Precio

Resistencia

Satisfacción global

13. ¿Con qué frecuencia le ocurren las siguientes situaciones cuando va a la compra al supermercado?

- 1= nunca
- 2= rara vez
- 3= algunas veces
- 4= la mayoría de las veces
- 5= siempre

Trata de colocar las compras en el menor número posible de bolsas

Pide una bolsa más resistente o más grande, que es más cara

Le ofrecen una bolsa más resistente o más grande, que es más cara

Pide una bolsa más resistente o reutilizable, y le dicen que no tienen

Le ofrecen elegir entre bolsas ligeras o bolsas reutilizables de larga duración

Le ofrecen usar bolsas de plástico biológico (no biodegradables)

Le ofrecen usar bolsas biodegradables

i Cuando vaya a responder la siguiente pregunta tenga en cuenta:

Llamamos plásticos biológicos a aquellos que se obtienen de fuentes renovables (fermentación de cereales, patatas, maíz...) y no son necesariamente biodegradables, pueden serlo o no. Llamamos biodegradables a los que se descomponen como la materia orgánica/alimentos y pueden ser compostados.

14. ¿Cuánto estaría usted dispuesto a pagar por una bolsa de la compra de plástico biológico o biodegradable en la caja del súper?

- | | |
|------------------------------------|---|
| 1= nada | 4= 11 a 15 céntimos por bolsa |
| 2= 5 céntimos por bolsa como mucho | 5= 16 a 20 céntimos por bolsa |
| 3= 6 a 10 céntimos por bolsa | 6= pagaría incluso más de 20 céntimos por bolsa |

Bolsa de plástico biológico no biodegradable

Bolsa de plástico biodegradable

Reciclado de residuos plásticos

15. ¿En qué medida se siente usted informado sobre la separación y reciclaje de residuos (materiales que pueden reciclarse, en qué contenedor debe colocarse cada uno, tratamiento de los residuos, destino final de los materiales recuperados, tasas de reciclaje, etc.)?

[Anote una respuesta de 1 a 10..]

16. Y, en su domicilio, ¿se separan los siguientes residuos? [Responda, por favor para cada tipo de residuo.]

- 1= no
2= sí, pero no de un modo muy preciso
3= sí, de un modo muy preciso

Metales

Plásticos

Envases de bebidas/tetrabriks

Vidrio

Papel/cartón

Ropa

Residuos orgánicos (p. ej. Jardín, alimentos...)

Acelte de freír

Medicamentos

Pilas

Otros residuos peligrosos (p. ej. pinturas, bombillas, componentes electrónicos, o que incluyan componentes tóxicos)

Si en la pregunta anterior respondió '3' en todas las opciones, continúe en la pregunta 18.

17. ¿Qué diría usted que le impide reciclar los residuos (de una manera más precisa)? [Anote los motivos con X.]

Todos los contenedores de reciclaje/puntos limpios están demasiado lejos de mi casa

Algunos contenedores de reciclaje/puntos limpios (por ejemplo, para el vidrio) están demasiado lejos de mi casa

No hay recogida separada de residuos puerta a puerta

Separar residuos es demasiado caro (coste de distintos cubos de basura, distintas bolsas ...)

No es práctico/es molesto tener tantos cubos/bolsas de basura en casa

No sé cómo hacerlo (falta de Información)

Lleva mucho tiempo / da demasiado trabajo

No me siento motivado para hacerlo porque lo que yo haga no significará nada

Otro motivo [especificar]:

18. ¿Hasta qué punto está de acuerdo con las siguientes afirmaciones respecto al impacto ambiental de los plásticos para uso doméstico?

- | | |
|------------------------|--------------------|
| 1= muy en desacuerdo | desacuerdo |
| 2= algo en desacuerdo | 4= algo de acuerdo |
| 3= ni de acuerdo ni en | 5= muy de acuerdo |

Los materiales plásticos para uso doméstico son un problema para el planeta

Los materiales plásticos para uso doméstico consumen muchos recursos naturales

Una vez usados los materiales plásticos para uso doméstico son residuos que no pueden reutilizarse

Los materiales plásticos para uso doméstico generan riesgos de seguridad alimentaria

Los materiales plásticos para uso doméstico generan riesgos para la salud

La producción/uso/residuos de materiales plásticos para uso doméstico es una de las causas de contaminación más importantes

19. ¿Con qué frecuencia conserva y reutiliza los siguientes embalajes plásticos?

- | | |
|------------------|----------------------------|
| 1= nunca | 4= la mayoría de las veces |
| 2= rara vez | 5= siempre |
| 3= algunas veces | |

Bandejas de plástico para carne fresca

Bandejas/envases de plástico para frutas/verduras

Envases de plástico para comidas preparadas	<input type="checkbox"/>
Botellas de plástico de agua	<input type="checkbox"/>
Botes de plástico de geles/champú	<input type="checkbox"/>
Bolsas de plástico	<input type="checkbox"/>

Nuevos materiales

i Cuando vaya a responder las siguientes preguntas tenga en cuenta:

Llamamos plásticos biológicos a aquellos que se obtienen de fuentes renovables (fermentación de cereales, patatas, maíz...) y no son necesariamente biodegradables, pueden serlo o no. Llamamos biodegradables a los que se descomponen como la materia orgánica/alimentos y pueden ser compostados.

20. A la hora de comprar un producto, ¿daría usted prioridad a productos envasados con los siguientes nuevos materiales plásticos?

- 1= no
2= sí, dependiendo del producto
3= sí, en cualquier caso

Plástico biológico (no biodegradable)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Plástico biodegradable	<input type="checkbox"/>
Plástico reciclado	<input type="checkbox"/>

21. ¿Cuánto estaría dispuesto a pagar de más por los siguientes productos, si estuvieran envueltos utilizando envoltorios biológicos/biodegradables?

- 1= nada
2= no más de 5 céntimos por bolsa
3= 6 a 10 céntimos por bolsa
4= 11 a 15 céntimos por bolsa
5= 16 a 20 céntimos por bolsa
6= pagaría incluso más de 20 céntimos por bolsa

Cápsulas de café	<input type="checkbox"/>
Carne fresca	<input type="checkbox"/>
Comida preparada	<input type="checkbox"/>
Detergente en polvo para lavadoras	<input type="checkbox"/>
Champú/gel de baño	<input type="checkbox"/>

22. Los residuos de plástico biodegradable deben ser tratados junto a los residuos orgánicos (p.ej. restos de alimentos, desechos del jardín, etc.). ¿Qué impacto tendría esto en la forma en la que usted recicla?

- 1= creo que lo haría más difícil
2= creo que no tendría ningún efecto
3= creo que lo haría más fácil

23. ¿En qué medida está usted informado sobre los nuevos materiales plásticos (biológicos/biodegradables)?

- 1= nada informado, aunque no me importa
2= nada informado, aunque me gustaría saber más
3= un poco informado
4= bien informado

24. ¿Cuánto confía usted en la información sobre nuevos materiales plásticos que proporciona cada una de las siguientes fuentes? [Anoté una respuesta de 1 a 10.]

Fabricantes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Su supermercado habitual	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Autoridades públicas (Ministerio de Medio Ambiente, Consejerías CCAA/Ayuntamientos...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Instituciones de certificación independientes (p.ej. Ecolabel)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Medios de comunicación	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Organizaciones medioambientales (p.ej. Greenpeace)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
OCU	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Para terminar...

25. Usted es:

- 1= mujer 2= hombre

26. Su edad:

años

27. ¿Qué estudios ha realizado (finalizados)?

- 1= estudios primarios (EGB / 2º ESO)
2= estudios secundarios (4º ESO /BUP /Bachillerato/FP grado medio o superior)
3= estudios universitarios (Diplomatura/Licenciatura/Grado o superiores)

28. En total, ¿cuántas personas viven actualmente en su domicilio?

Nº de adultos (incluido usted)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nº niños 12-17 años	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nº niños 4-11 años	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nº niños < 4 años	<input type="checkbox"/>

29. ¿Cómo describiría su situación económica actual:

- 1= muy difícil
2= difícil
3= suficiente para cubrir las necesidades
4= cómoda
5= muy cómoda

30. La zona donde usted vive, diría que es...

- 1= urbana (en una ciudad)
2= urbana (en las afueras de una ciudad)
3= rural (en un pueblo, en el campo, montaña...)

31. ¿En qué provincia reside usted?

[Anoté las dos primeras cifras de su código postal.]

¡MUCHAS GRACIAS POR SU COLABORACIÓN!

Código del país

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PLASTİK AMBALAJ ATIKLARIYLA OLAN DENEYİMİNİZ ©

Telif hakkı Kartal Belediyesi'ne aittir

Sevgili Kartallılar,

Kartal Belediyesi olarak Avrupa Birliği Ufuk 2020 Bilimsel Araştırma ve Yenilik Programı kapsamında 6 ülkenin (Türkiye, Belçika, Hırvatistan, İspanya, İtalya, Portekiz) katılımıyla plastik ambalaj atıkları ile ilgili bir anket yürütmekteyiz.

Bu çalışmanın temel amacı tüketicilerin gıda, temizlik maddesi, hijyenik ürünler gibi günlük kullanım malzemelerinin plastik ambalaj atıkları veya plastik içerikleri ve de büyük plastik alışveriş torbaları ile ilgili alışkanlık ve beklentilerini incelemektir.

Bu soru formu yardımıyla sizi bu konudaki deneyim ve fikirlerinizi paylaşmaya davet ediyoruz. Bu sorulara vereceğiniz yanıtlar sayesinde tüm tüketicilerle ilgili sonuçlar elde edilmesi mümkün olacaktır. Verdiğiniz yanıtlar tamamen sahibinin kim olduğu belirtilmeden alınacak ve sadece çalışma kapsamındaki istatistik verilerin temininde kullanılacaktır. Kişisel bilgileriniz üçüncü şahıslarla paylaşılmayacaktır.

Doldurulan soru formları ilgili firma tarafından Kartal Belediyesi'ne teslim edilecektir.

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Soru formu doldurulurken aşağıdaki yönteme uyulması gerekmektedir:

- Rakamlar sağdaki kutuya hizalı olmalıdır.

Örnek:

(yanlış)

(doğru)

- Sayılar her kutuya bir rakam gelecek şekilde girilmelidir.

Örnek:

(yanlış)

(doğru)

- Sizin için en uygun durumu ifade eden seçim kutucuğunu veya kutucuklarını işaretlemeniz istendiğinde durumunuzu en iyi ifade eden kutucuğun veya kutucukların içine 'X' yazınız.

	Seçenek 1
X	Seçenek 2
	Seçenek 3

Çalışmamıza zaman ayırıp katkı sunduğunuz için teşekkür ederiz.

Saygı ve sevgilerimizle,

Op. Dr. Altınok ÖZ
Kartal Belediye Başkanı

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Telif hakkı Kartal Belediyesi'ne aittir

PLASTİK AMBALAJLARLA OLAN DENEYİMİNİZ®

Bu sorulara yanıt vermek için plastik ambalajlı ürünleri ne sıklıkta satın aldığınızı veya ne kadar plastik alışveriş torbası kullandığınızı bir önemi yoktur. Soruların kişisel deneyiminiz olan kısımlarına yanıt vermeniz yeterlidir.

Çevreye olan yaklaşımınız

1. Sizce, atıkların geri dönüşüm için ayrıştırılması, enerji tüketiminin azaltılması, su israfının önlenmesi, ulaşımda toplu taşıma araçlarının kullanılması, beslenmede organik gıda tüketilmesi gibi çevre dostu davranışlara sahip olmak ne kadar önemlidir?

- 1 - Hiç önemli yok 3 - biraz önemsiyorum
2 - pek önemli değil 4 - çok önemli

2. Çevre dostu bir tutuma sahip olup hayata geçirmek konusunda ne yapıyorsunuz?

- 1 - Bu konuda bir şey yapmıyorum
2 - Biraz bir şeyler yapıyorum
3 - Çok şeyler yapıyorum

3. Sizce evlerde oluşan atıkların çevreye olan gerçek etkisi ne boyuttadır?

- 1 - Hiç etkisi yoktur 3 - biraz etkiliyordur
2 - çok az etkisi oluyordur 4 - büyük etkisi vardır

4. Genel olarak düşünersek, aşağıdakiler hakkında kendinizi ne derece bilgi sahibi buluyorsunuz? [1 ile 10 arası bir değer belirtiniz]

Türkiye'deki çevre politikası ve çevre mevzuatı	<input type="checkbox"/>
Avrupa Birliği çevre politikası ve çevre mevzuatı	<input type="checkbox"/>
Genel anlamda kirliliğin çevreye olan etkisi	<input type="checkbox"/>
Plastik atıkların çevreye olan etkisi	<input type="checkbox"/>

5. Gıda, temizlik malzemesi, hijyenik ürün gibi gündelik ürünler satın alırken ürün seçiminizde aşağıda verilen nitelikler ne derece etkili olur? [1 ile 10 arası bir değer belirtiniz]

Fiyatı	<input type="checkbox"/>
Kalitesi	<input type="checkbox"/>
İçeriği	<input type="checkbox"/>
Menşei, kaynağı	<input type="checkbox"/>
Markası (tanınmış marka olması)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ürünün özellikleri / kendine has özellikleri	<input type="checkbox"/>
Görünüşü / tasarımı	<input type="checkbox"/>

Ambalajı	<input type="checkbox"/>
Kullanışlı olması / Kullanıcıyla dost olması	<input type="checkbox"/>
Promosyonda olması / Hediye vermesi	<input type="checkbox"/>
Çevre açısından özellikleri (Örneğin içerdiği kirlenici maddeler, organik gıda olması)	<input type="checkbox"/>

Ürün ambalajı

6. Plastik içeren veya plastik ambalaja sahip ürünler satın almaktan / kullanmaktan kaçınırsınız mı?

- 1 - Hiç kaçınmam
2 - Bazen kaçınıyorum
3 - Hep kaçınıyorum

Plastik içeren ürünler	<input type="checkbox"/>
Plastik ambalaja sahip ürünler	<input type="checkbox"/>

ⓘ Bilgi: Sorulara yanıt vermeden önce okuyunuz: **Biyolojik esaslı plastik (biyoplastik)** yenilenebilir kaynaklardan yararlanılarak yani tahıllar, patates, mısır ve benzerinin fermante edilmesiyle üretilir. **Biyodegradabl** yani doğada çözünebilir ve, **biyodegradabl** olmayan yani doğada çözünmeyen de vardır. **Biyodegradabl**; doğada parçalanarak organik atık / gıda atığı haline gelen anlamına gelir ve kompost yani humus olarak kullanıma uygundur.

7. Aşağıdaki ürünleri satın alırken ambalajının hangi özellikte olmasına dikkat edersiniz? [Her ürün için bir tane seçim yapınız]

- **Kapsül kahve**
 - 1 - alışılagelmiş plastik kapsül
 - 2 - doğada çözünmeyen türde biyoplastik kapsül
 - 3 - biyodegradabl plastik kapsül
 - 4 - alüminyum kapsül
 - 5 - fark etmez
- **Taze et (tavuk ve benzeri)**
 - 1 - alışılagelmiş plastik tabak (polistiren ve benzeri)
 - 2 - doğada çözünmeyen türde biyoplastik tabak
 - 3 - biyodegradabl plastik tabak
 - 4 - plastik olmayan (örneğin kağıt tabak)
 - 5 - fark etmez
- **Hazır gıda (hazır salata ve benzeri)**
 - 1 - alışılagelmiş plastik kap (polistiren ve benzeri)
 - 2 - doğada çözünmeyen türde biyoplastik kap
 - 3 - biyodegradabl plastik kap
 - 4 - plastik olmayan karton ve benzeri kap
 - 5 - fark etmez
- **Çamaşır makinesi için toz deterjan**
 - 1 - alışılagelmiş plastik poşet / kutu
 - 2 - doğada çözünmeyen türde biyoplastik poşet / kutu
 - 3 - biyodegradabl plastik poşet / kutu
 - 4 - alışılagelmiş karton kutu
 - 5 - fark etmez
- **Duş jeli / şampuanı**
 - 1 - alışılagelmiş plastik şişe
 - 2 - doğada çözünmeyen türde biyoplastik şişe
 - 3 - plastik olmayan türde örneğin cam şişe
 - 4 - fark etmez

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8. Aşağıdaki ürünlerde aşağıdaki özelliklerin hangilerinin olmasına önem verirsiniz?

[Her ürün için bir tane seçim yapınız]

- 1 - Malzeme, İçerik
- 2 - Boyut, ağırlık veya hacim
- 3 - Tasarım (görünüş, renk)
- 4 - Biçim (elde taşınması kolay veya içindeki tamamen kullanılabilen)
- 5 - Kullanışlılık (ürünü iyi durumda tutması, rahat taşınması, kolay boşaltılması, tipasının kullanışlı olması ve benzeri)
- 6 - Ürünün korunması
- 7 - Çevre dostu özellikleri (tekrar doluma uygun olması, yüzde yüzünün geri kazanılabilmesi, kirletici madde içermemesi gibi)

Kahve kapsülü	<input type="checkbox"/>
Taze et	<input type="checkbox"/>
Hazır gıda	<input type="checkbox"/>
Çamaşır makinası toz deterjanı	<input type="checkbox"/>
Şampuan / duş jeli	<input type="checkbox"/>

9. Gündelik alışveriş sırasında plastik ambalaja sahip ürünler satın alırken aşağıdaki durumlarla ne sıklıkta karşılaşılıyorsunuz?

- 1 - hiç
- 2 - nadiren
- 3 - bazen
- 4 - çoğu zaman
- 5 - her zaman

Ürün ambalaj gerektirmiyor	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ambalaj üründen çok daha büyük	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ambalaj ürüne göre çok ağır	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ambalaj kullanışlı değil veya ürüne tam uymamış	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ambalaj ürünü gerçekte olduğundan daha lüks veya daha kaliteli gösteriyor	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ambalajın atık olarak vermek üzere katlanması / sıkıştırılması zor	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ambalaj ürünü iyi korumuyor/saklamıyor	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ambalaj tek kullanımlık / tekrar kullanmaya veya yeniden doldurmaya uygun değil	<input type="checkbox"/>

Plastik torbalar

10. Süpermarketten alışverişlerinizde torbanızı genelde ne şekilde temin edersiniz?

- 1 - Torbami evden gelirken yanımda getiririm (önceki alışverişte aldığım torbayı tekrar kullanırım veya bez çanta kullanırım)
- 2 - Alışveriş yaptığım yerden yeni torba satın alırım
- 3 - Hem evden gelirken yanımda getiririm hem de marketten veya süpermarketten satın alırım
- 4 - Alışveriş torbası kullanmam, onun yerine ürünleri elimde veya tekerlekli market arabasında ya da karton veya plastik kutularda taşırım [4' seçtiyise 15. soruya geçiniz]

Ö Bilgi: Sorulara yanıt vermeden önce okuyunuz:
Biyolojik esaslı plastik (biyoplastik) yenilenebilir kaynaklardan yararlanılarak yani tahıllar, patates, mısır ve benzerinin fermante edilmesiyle üretilir. Biyoçözünür olanı yani doğada çözünebileni de, biyoçözünür olmayanı yani doğada çözünmeyen de vardır.
Biyoçözünür; doğada parçalanarak organik atık / gıda atığı haline gelen anlamına gelir ve kompost yani humus olarak kullanıma uygundur.

11. Bakkal, market veya süpermarket alışverişlerinizde aşağıda verilen malzemelerden hangisinden yapılmış torba kullanmayı tercih edersiniz?

- 1 - alışılmamış plastik (naylon)
- 2 - doğada çözünür türde olmayan biyoplastik
- 3 - biyoçözünür plastik
- 4 - kâğıt
- 5 - kumaş
- 6 - sentetik elyaf (polyester ve benzeri)
- 7 - diğer (açıklayınız):
- 8 - fark etmez

12. Bakkal, market veya süpermarketten satın aldığınız torbalardan aşağıda verilen özellikler açısından ne derece memnunsunuz?

[1 ile 10 arası bir değer belirtiniz]

Boyut	<input type="checkbox"/>
Kullanım kolaylığı	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fiyat	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sağlamlık	<input type="checkbox"/>
Genel memnuniyet	<input type="checkbox"/>

13. Bakkal, market veya süpermarket alışverişlerinizde aşağıda verilen durumlarla ne sıklıkta karşılaşılıyorsunuz?

- 1 - hiç
- 2 - nadiren
- 3 - bazen
- 4 - çoğu zaman
- 5 - her zaman

Alışverişi mümkün olan en az sayıda torba ile sınırlı tutmaya çalışırım	<input type="checkbox"/>
Daha pahalı da olsa daha dayanıklı veya daha büyük torba isterim	<input type="checkbox"/>
Satıcı bana daha pahalı da olsa daha dayanıklı veya daha büyük olan torba teklif etti	<input type="checkbox"/>
Daha dayanıklı veya tekrar kullanılabilir torba istedim, yoktu	<input type="checkbox"/>
Satıcı bana daha hafif torba ve daha uzun ömürlü yeniden kullanılabilir torba seçenekleri sundu	<input type="checkbox"/>
Satıcı bana doğada çözünmeyen türde biyoplastik torba kullanmamı teklif etti	<input type="checkbox"/>
Satıcı bana doğada çözünen torba kullanmamı teklif etti	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Ⓛ Bilgi: Sorulara yanıt vermeden önce okuyunuz.
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Biyoçözünür; doğada parçalanarak organik atık / gıda atığı haline gelen anlamına gelir ve kompost yani humus olarak kullanıma uygundur.

14. Bakkal, market veya süpermarket alışverişlerinizde biyoplastik torba için ücret ödememiz istenirse ne kadar ödemeyi kabul edersiniz?

- 1 - hiçbir şey ödemem
- 2 - torba başına en fazla 10 kuruş
- 3 - torba başına 11 - 20 kuruş arası
- 4 - torba başına 21 - 25 kuruş arası
- 5 - torba başına 26 - 50 kuruş arası
- 6 - torba başına 50 kuruştan fazla

Doğada çözünmeyen türde biyoplastik torba
Biyoçözünür torba

Plastik atıkların geridönüşümü

15. Belediye tarafından atıkların ayrıştırılmasına yönelik yürütülen çalışmalar konusunda ne kadar bilgi sahibisiniz? (örneğin; geridönüşebilen atıklar hangileridir, geridönüşüm poşeti/kutusu/konteyneri/kumbarası renkleri nelerdir, atık bertarafını kim nasıl yapar, atıklar neye göre ayrılır ve nasıl toplanır, gerikazanılan malzemeler en son nereye gider, atıkların ne oranda geri dönüşümü sağlanır, atıkların yüzde kaç geri dönüşüme gidiyor)
[1 ile 10 arası bir değer belirtiniz]

16. Evde siz ve evdeki diğer kişiler aşağıdaki atıkları ayırıyor musunuz?
[Belediye atık toplama sistemi kapsamında toplanan her atık türü için değerlendirme yapınız]

- 1 - hayır, ayırmıyoruz
 - 2 - kabaca ayırıyoruz, türüne çok dikkat etmiyoruz
 - 3 - türüne göre dikkatle ayırıyoruz
- Metal
Plastik
İçecek ambalajı / Tetrapak
Cam
Kağıt/karton
Giysi
Biyolojik atık (bahçe, mutfak ve gıda atıkları gibi)
Yemeklerde kullanılan yağ / bitkisel yağ
İlaç
Pil

Diğer tehlikeli atıklar (boya, ampul/lamba, elektronik eşya gibi atıklar ve zehirli bileşene sahip atıklar)

[Tüm atık türleri için yanıt '3' ise 18. soruya geçiniz.]

17. Atıklarınızı türüne göre özenle ayırmanıza engel olan nedir? [İşaretleyiniz.]

- Tüm atık türleri için atık getirme noktaları evime çok uzak
- Bazı atık türleri (örneğin cam) için atık getirme noktaları evime çok uzak
- Ayrılmış atıklar için kapıdan toplama yapılmıyor
- Atıkları ayırmak için çok masraf etmek gerekiyor (ayrı çöp kovası, ayrı torba, ayrı konteyner ve benzerini satın alma maliyeti yüksek geliyor)
- Evde atıkları ayrı toplamak için bu kadar çok kova/torba kullanmak kullanışlı değil/uygulanabilir değil
- Nasıl yapılacağını bilmiyorum (bilgi eksikliği)
- Zaman kaybı / Angarya / Çok uğraşmak lazım
- Benim atıklarımı ayırmamın bir faydası olacağına inanmadığımdan yapasım yok
- Diğer [açıklayınız]:

18. Evde kullanılan plastiklerin çevreye olan etkisi hakkında aşağıdaki ifadelerle ne kadar katılıyorsunuz?

- 1 - kesinlikle katılmıyorum
- 2 - kısmen katılmıyorum
- 3 - ne katılıyorum ne katılmıyorum
- 4 - kısmen katılıyorum
- 5 - kesinlikle katılıyorum

- Evde kullanılan plastikler gezegenimiz için büyük bir sorun oluşturuyor
- Evde kullanılan plastikler doğal kaynakları fazlasıyla tüketiyor
- Evde kullanılan plastikler bir kez atıldı mı bir daha tekrar kullanılmaz, çöpe gider
- Evde kullanılan plastikler gıda güvenliğini tehdit ediyor
- Evde kullanılan plastikler sağlığı tehdit ediyor
- Evde kullanılan plastiklerin üretimi/kullanımı/atılması çevre kirliliğinin en önemli nedenlerinden biri

19. Aşağıdaki ambalaj türlerini ne sıklıkta saklıyorsunuz veya yeniden kullanıyorsunuz?

- 1 - hiç
- 2 - nadiren
- 3 - bazen
- 4 - çoğu zaman
- 5 - her zaman

- Taze et konulan plastik tabak
- Meyve / sebze konulan plastik tabak
- Hazır gıda konulan plastik tabak
- Plastik su şişesi
- Deterjan/şampuan/temizleyicilerin plastik şişeleri
- Plastik torba

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Yeni plastik malzemeler

Bilgi: Sorulara yanıt vermeden önce okuyunuz: **Biyolojik esaslı plastik (biyoplastik)** yenilenebilir kaynaklardan yararlanılarak yani tahıl, patates, mısır ve benzerinin fermante edilmesiyle üretilir. Biyoçözünür olanı yani doğada çözülebileni de, biyoçözünür olmayanı yani doğada çözünmeyen de vardır. **Biyoçözünür;** doğada parçalanarak organik atık / gıda atığı haline gelen anlamına gelir ve kompost yani humus olarak kullanıma uygundur. **Ger dönmüş plastik; atık plastikten yapılmış plastiktir.**

20. Bir ürün satın alırken, ürünün kendisinin veya ambalajının aşağıda verilen yeni malzemelerden yapılmış olması o ürünü tercih etmenizi sağlar mı?

- 1 - Hiç fark etmez
- 2 - Ürüne göre değişir
- 3 - Tercih ederim

Doğada çözünür olmayan türde biyoplastik
Biyoçözünür plastik
Ger dönmüş plastik

21. Bir ürünün biyoplastik veya biyoçözünür plastik kullanılarak üretilmiş olmasını almak için ilave ne kadar ücret öderdiniz?

- 1 - hiçbir şey ödemem
- 2 - en fazla 10 kuruş
- 3 - 11 - 20 kuruş arası
- 4 - 21 - 25 kuruş arası
- 5 - 26 - 50 kuruş arası
- 6 - 50 kuruştan fazla

Kapsül kahve
Taze et
Hazır gıda
Çamaşır makinesi toz deterjanı
Şampuan / duş jeli

22. Biyoçözünür plastik atıkların organik atıklar (örneğin gıda/mutfak atıkları, bahçe atıkları) ile birlikte diğer atıklardan ayrılması gerekir. Bunun evdeki atıklarınızla ilgili yönetim şeklinize nasıl bir etkisi olur?

- 1 - İşimi zorlaştırır
- 2 - Şimdikiye göre pek bir değişiklik olmaz
- 3 - İşimi kolaylaştırır

23. Yeni plastik malzemeler hakkında ne kadar bilginiz var?

- 1 - Hiç yok ve umurumda da değil
- 2 - Hiç yok ama bilgi edinmek isterim
- 3 - Biraz bilgim var
- 4 - Epey bilgim var

24. Yeni plastik malzemelerle ilgili bilgi aşağıdaki kaynaklardan gelirse o bilgiye ne derece güvenirsiniz?

Üretici (örneğin ürün ambalaj firması, markanın internet sitesi)
Süpermarket
Kamu kurumları (örneğin Çevre ve Şehircilik Bakanlığı, Gıda Tarım ve Hayvancılık Bakanlığı, Sağlık Bakanlığı, Bilim Sanayi ve Teknoloji Bakanlığı, Türk Akreditasyon Kurumu, TÜBİTAK)
Bağımsız belgelendirme kuruluşları (örneğin TSE-Türk Standartları Enstitüsü, TÜV, Bureau Veritas, label OK Compost, EcoLabel)
Basın-yayın kuruluşları
Çevre kuruluşları (örneğin Greenpeace, TEMA Vakfı, Doğal Hayatı Koruma Vakfı, Buğday Derneği, Yeryüzü Derneği)
Tüketici kuruluşları (örneğin TÜKODER-Tüketiciyi Koruma Derneği, ÇEVKO-Çevre Koruma ve Ambalaj Atıklarını Değerlendirme Vakfı, TÜKÇEV-Tüketici ve Çevre Eğitim Vakfı)

Bitirirken...

25. Cinsiyetiniz:

- 1 - kadın
- 2 - erkek

26. Yaşınız:

27. Öğrenim seviyeniz: [bugüne kadar mezun olduğunuz en yüksek öğrenim seviyesini belirtiniz]

- 1 - Okuma yazma bilmiyor
- 2 - Okuma yazma biliyor, diploması yok
- 3 - İlkokul
- 4 - İlköğretim
- 5 - Ortaokul
- 6 - Ortaokul dengi meslek okulu
- 7 - Lise
- 8 - Meslek lisesi
- 9 - Yüksekokul
- 10 - Üniversite (4 yıl ve üzeri)
- 11 - Yüksek lisans (master, doktora)

28. Hane halkınız:

Evdeki yetişkin sayısı (siz dahil)
Evdeki 12-17 yaş arası kişi sayısı
Evdeki 4-11 yaş arası kişi sayısı
Evdeki 4 yaşın altında kişi sayısı

29. Ekonomik durumunuz:

- 1 - gelir seviyesi çok düşük
- 2 - asgari ücret seviyesinde
- 3 - orta
- 4 - iyi
- 5 - oldukça iyi

30. Yaşadığınız yer:

- 1 - şehir içi / şehir merkezi
- 2 - şehrin dış kısımları / banliyö
- 3 - kırsal alan / köy veya mezra

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31. Oturduğunuz mahalle:

1	Atalar Mah.	11	Orta Mah.
2	Cevizli Mah.	12	Petrol İş Mah.
3	Cumhuriyet Mah.	13	Soğanlık Yeni Mah.
4	Çavuşoğlu Mah.	14	Topselvi Mah.
5	Esentepe Mah.	15	Uğur Mumcu Mah.
6	Gömüştüner Mah.	16	Yakaok Çarşı Mah.
7	Hürriyet Mah.	17	Yakaok Yeni Mah.
8	Karıktepe Mah.	18	Yalı Mah.
9	Kordonboyu Mah.	19	Yukan Mah.
10	Orhantepe Mah.	20	Yunus Mah.

İŞBİRLİĞİNİZ ÇOK TEŞEKKÜR EDERİZ!

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ANNEX B: ANP RANKING AND WEIGHING RESULTS FOR SOCIAL INDICATORS

VC1_Biodegradable polymers

Name	Ideals	Normals	Ranking
5-EoL responsibility	1	0.248304	1
11-Technology development	0.556463	0.138172	2
4-Consumers' health and safety	0.526481	0.130727	3
3-Workers' health and safety	0.341772	0.084863	4
8-Safe and healthy living conditions	0.333524	0.082815	5
6-Consumers' well-being	0.300595	0.074639	6
9-Local employment	0.297842	0.073955	7
10-Community engagement	0.180476	0.044813	8
7-Community access to material resources	0.150329	0.037327	9
12-Suppliers' relationships	0.113354	0.028146	10
2-Workers' training and education	0.113354	0.028146	11
1-Equal opportunities and discrimination	0.113133	0.028091	12
		0.999998	

VC2_Multi-material packaging

Name	Ideals	Normals	Ranking
4-Consumers' health and safety	1	0.158565	1
5-EoL responsibility	0.787029	0.124795	2
7-Community access to material resources	0.592419	0.093937	3
9-Local employment	0.578854	0.091786	4
3-Workers' health and safety	0.534846	0.084808	5
11-Technology development	0.531442	0.084268	6
12-Suppliers' relationships	0.506861	0.08037	7
2-Workers' training and education	0.437291	0.069339	8
10-Community engagement	0.426356	0.067605	9
6-Consumers' well-being	0.390355	0.061897	10
8-Safe and healthy living conditions	0.348442	0.055251	11
1-Equal opportunities and discrimination	0.172664	0.027378	12
		0.999999	

VC3_Plastic packaging (bottles)

Name	Ideals	Normals	Ranking
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5-EoL responsibility	1	0.165062	1
6-Consumers' well-being	0.68521	0.113102	2
4-Consumers' health and safety	0.668579	0.110357	3
9-Local employment	0.663704	0.109552	4
11-Technology development	0.550214	0.090819	5
12-Suppliers' relationships	0.499385	0.082429	6
2-Workers' training and education	0.490613	0.080981	7
3-Workers' health and safety	0.465827	0.07689	8
8-Safe and healthy living conditions	0.349906	0.057756	9
7-Community access to material resources	0.330016	0.054473	10
1-Equal opportunities and discrimination	0.180285	0.029758	11
10-Community engagement	0.174605	0.028821	12
		1	

VC4_Plastic bags

Name	Ideals	Normals	Ranking
5-EoL responsibility	1	0.149273	1
4-Consumers' health and safety	0.73743	0.110078	2
11-Technology development	0.73743	0.110078	3
8-Safe and healthy living conditions	0.646474	0.096501	4
3-Workers' health and safety	0.634981	0.094785	5
6-Consumers' well-being	0.600922	0.089701	6
9-Local employment	0.515036	0.076881	7
1-Equal opportunities and discrimination	0.509966	0.076124	8
12-Suppliers' relationships	0.445295	0.06647	9
2-Workers' training and education	0.445295	0.06647	10
10-Community engagement	0.295469	0.044105	11
7-Community access to material resources	0.13085	0.019532	12
		0.999998	

VC5_Food trays (tray & multi-material film)

Name	Ideals	Normals	Ranking
11-Technology development	1	0.179474	1
5-EoL responsibility	0.829874	0.148941	2
6-Consumers' well-being	0.630721	0.113198	3
4-Consumers' health and safety	0.622308	0.111688	4
12-Suppliers' relationships	0.571552	0.102579	5
9-Local employment	0.418609	0.07513	6
2-Workers' training and education	0.379025	0.068025	7
8-Safe and healthy living conditions	0.313387	0.056245	8

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3-Workers' health and safety	0.30312	0.054402	9
7-Community access to material resources	0.222138	0.039868	10
1-Equal opportunities and discrimination	0.162213	0.029113	11
10-Community engagement	0.118883	0.021337	12
		1	

VC6_Automotive components

Name	Ideals	Normals	Ranking
2-Workers' training and education	1	0.109413	1
3-Workers' health and safety	1	0.109413	1
4-Consumers' health and safety	1	0.109413	1
6-Consumers' well-being	1	0.109413	1
8-Safe and healthy living conditions	1	0.109413	1
9-Local employment	1	0.109413	1
11-Technology development	1	0.109413	1
12-Suppliers' relationships	1	0.109413	1
1-Equal opportunities and discrimination	0.094554	0.10345	2
5-EoL responsibility	0.595365	0.065141	3
7-Community access to material resources	0.224879	0.024605	4
10-Community engagement	0.224879	0.024605	4
		1	

VC7_Coffee capsules

Name	Ideals	Normals	Ranking
5-EoL responsibility	1	0.248985	1
4-Consumers' health and safety	0.55165	0.137353	2
11-Technology development	0.534718	0.133137	3
8-Safe and healthy living conditions	0.400697	0.099768	4
3-Workers' health and safety	0.370558	0.092263	5
6-Consumers' well-being	0.30286	0.075408	6
9-Local employment	0.296129	0.073732	7
10-Community engagement	0.126083	0.031393	8
12-Suppliers' relationships	0.119933	0.029861	9
1-Equal opportunities and discrimination	0.119933	0.029861	10
2-Workers' training and education	0.119933	0.029861	11
7-Community access to material resources	0.073809	0.018377	12
		1	

VC8_Absorbent Hygienic Products

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Name	Ideals	Normals	Ranking
5-EoL responsibility	1	0.178531	1
7-Community access to material resources	0.761262	0.135909	2
12-Suppliers' relationships	0.7364	0.13147	3
8-Safe and healthy living conditions	0.583248	0.104128	4
11-Technology development	0.414749	0.074046	5
6-Consumers' well-being	0.380796	0.067984	6
10-Community engagement	0.34716	0.061979	7
9-Local employment	0.335864	0.059962	8
3-Workers' health and safety	0.305745	0.054585	9
4-Consumers' health and safety	0.296057	0.052855	10
1-Equal opportunities and discrimination	0.237026	0.042316	11
2-Workers' training and education	0.202966	0.036236	12
		1	

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ANNEX C: SURVEY RESULTS FOR ENVIRONMENTAL INDICATORS

Environmental indicators survey

Multi-material packaging	Survey provided by	BUMAGA
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Environmental Indicator:	Use of virgin material (primary raw material use) (%)	Low	Medium	High
<i>Description: The percentage of the mass of virgin raw materials used over the mass of total raw materials</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Use of recycled material content (Secondary raw material use) (%)	Low	Medium	High
<i>Description: : The percentage of the mass of recycled materials (secondary raw materials) used over the mass of total raw materials</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Amount of waste generation (%)	Low	Medium	High
<i>Description: The amount of waste generated and sent to landfill or incineration per the amount of the product (i.e., the waste generated during the production process)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Expected recyclable content (%)	Low	Medium	High
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Description: <i>The mass ratio of the product that is recyclable</i>			
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Efficiency of recycling (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The mass ratio of the output of recovery process over the input</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Environmental Indicator:	Marine litter (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The ratio of plastic packaging waste leaking into oceans per generated plastic packaging waste</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Environmental Indicator:	Water consumption (m ³ /kg)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Water consumed per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Environmental Indicator:	Fossil depletion (MJ/unit product)	Low	Medium	High
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Description: <i>Contribution to the decrease of the quantity of fossil fuels in the environment per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases)</i>			
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Energy consumption (MJ/unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Energy consumed per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases). It covers all renewable and non-renewable energy sources.</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Greenhouse gas emissions (t CO ₂ -eq / unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Emitted greenhouse gases as CO₂ equivalent per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases).</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Multi-material packaging	Survey provided by	SAPONIA
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Environmental Indicator:	Use of virgin material (primary raw material use) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The percentage of the mass of virgin raw materials used over the mass of total raw materials</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	Document:	D2.6 Summary of the state of play of the demo cases using the CEIS		
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	Reference:	D2.6	Date:	17/12/18

Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Use of recycled material content (Secondary raw material use) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: : The percentage of the mass of recycled materials (secondary raw materials) used over the mass of total raw materials				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Amount of waste generation (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: The amount of waste generated and sent to landfill or incineration per the amount of the product (i.e., the waste generated during the production process)				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Expected recyclable content (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: The mass ratio of the product that is recyclable				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Efficiency of recycling (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: The mass ratio of the output of recovery process over the input				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	Document:	D2.6 Summary of the state of play of the demo cases using the CEIS		
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Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Marine litter (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The ratio of plastic packaging waste leaking into oceans per generated plastic packaging waste</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Water consumption (m ³ /kg)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Water consumed per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Fossil depletion (MJ/unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Contribution to the decrease of the quantity of fossil fuels in the environment per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Energy consumption (MJ/unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Energy consumed per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases). It covers all renewable and non-renewable energy sources.</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Greenhouse gas emissions (t CO ₂ -eq / unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Emitted greenhouse gases as CO2 equivalent per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases).</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Plastic packaging (bottles)	Survey provided by	SAPONIA
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Environmental Indicator:	Use of virgin material (primary raw material use) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The percentage of the mass of virgin raw materials used over the mass of total raw materials</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Use of recycled material content (Secondary raw material use) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The percentage of the mass of recycled materials (secondary raw materials) used over the mass of total raw materials</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Environmental Indicator:	Amount of waste generation (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The amount of waste generated and sent to landfill or incineration per the amount of the product (i.e., the waste generated during the production process)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Expected recyclable content (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The mass ratio of the product that is recyclable</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Efficiency of recycling (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The mass ratio of the output of recovery process over the input</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Marine litter (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The ratio of plastic packaging waste leaking into oceans per generated plastic packaging waste</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Environmental Indicator:	Water consumption (m ³ /kg)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Water consumed per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Fossil depletion (MJ/unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Contribution to the decrease of the quantity of fossil fuels in the environment per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Energy consumption (MJ/unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Energy consumed per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases). It covers all renewable and non-renewable energy sources.</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Greenhouse gas emissions (t CO ₂ -eq / unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Emitted greenhouse gases as CO₂ equivalent per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases).</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Plastic bags (thick and thin)	Survey provided by	ECOEMBES
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Environmental Indicator:	Use of virgin material (primary raw material use) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: The percentage of the mass of virgin raw materials used over the mass of total raw materials				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Use of recycled material content (Secondary raw material use) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: : The percentage of the mass of recycled materials (secondary raw materials) used over the mass of total raw materials				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Amount of waste generation (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: The amount of waste generated and sent to landfill or incineration per the amount of the product (i.e., the waste generated during the production process)				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Expected recyclable content (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: The mass ratio of the product that is recyclable				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Efficiency of recycling (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The mass ratio of the output of recovery process over the input</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Marine litter (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The ratio of plastic packaging waste leaking into oceans per generated plastic packaging waste</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Water consumption (m ³ /kg)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Water consumed per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Fossil depletion (MJ/unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Contribution to the decrease of the quantity of fossil fuels in the environment per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Suitable for benchmarking	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Energy consumption (MJ/unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: Energy consumed per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases). It covers all renewable and non-renewable energy sources.				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Greenhouse gas emissions (t CO ₂ -eq / unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: Emitted greenhouse gases as CO ₂ equivalent per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases).				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Plastic packaging (liq detergents)	Survey provided by	ECOEMBES
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Environmental Indicator:	Use of virgin material (primary raw material use) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: The percentage of the mass of virgin raw materials used over the mass of total raw materials				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Use of recycled material content (Secondary raw material use) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: : The percentage of the mass of recycled materials (secondary raw materials) used over the mass of total raw materials				

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Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Amount of waste generation (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The amount of waste generated and sent to landfill or incineration per the amount of the product (i.e., the waste generated during the production process)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Environmental Indicator:	Expected recyclable content (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The mass ratio of the product that is recyclable</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Environmental Indicator:	Efficiency of recycling (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The mass ratio of the output of recovery process over the input</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Environmental Indicator:	Marine litter (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The ratio of plastic packaging waste leaking into oceans per generated plastic packaging waste</i>				

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Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Water consumption (m ³ /kg)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Water consumed per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Fossil depletion (MJ/unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Contribution to the decrease of the quantity of fossil fuels in the environment per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Energy consumption (MJ/unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Energy consumed per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases). It covers all renewable and non-renewable energy sources.</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Greenhouse gas emissions (t CO ₂ -eq / unit product)	Low	Medium	High

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Description: <i>Emitted greenhouse gases as CO2 equivalent per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases).</i>			
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Food trays	Survey provided by	ECOEMBES
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Environmental Indicator:	Use of virgin material (primary raw material use) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The percentage of the mass of virgin raw materials used over the mass of total raw materials</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Use of recycled material content (Secondary raw material use) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The percentage of the mass of recycled materials (secondary raw materials) used over the mass of total raw materials</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Amount of waste generation (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The amount of waste generated and sent to landfill or incineration per the amount of the product (i.e., the waste generated during the production process)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	Document:	D2.6 Summary of the state of play of the demo cases using the CEIS		
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	Reference:	D2.6	Date:	17/12/18

Environmental Indicator:	Expected recyclable content (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The mass ratio of the product that is recyclable</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Efficiency of recycling (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The mass ratio of the output of recovery process over the input</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Marine litter (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The ratio of plastic packaging waste leaking into oceans per generated plastic packaging waste</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Water consumption (m ³ /kg)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Water consumed per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Environmental Indicator:	Fossil depletion (MJ/unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: Contribution to the decrease of the quantity of fossil fuels in the environment per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases)				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Energy consumption (MJ/unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: Energy consumed per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases). It covers all renewable and non-renewable energy sources.				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Greenhouse gas emissions (t CO ₂ -eq / unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: Emitted greenhouse gases as CO ₂ equivalent per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases).				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Multi-material packaging	Survey provided by	ECOEMBES
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Environmental Indicator:	Use of virgin material (primary raw material use) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: The percentage of the mass of virgin raw materials used over the mass of total raw materials				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

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Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Use of recycled material content (Secondary raw material use) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: : The percentage of the mass of recycled materials (secondary raw materials) used over the mass of total raw materials				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Amount of waste generation (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: The amount of waste generated and sent to landfill or incineration per the amount of the product (i.e., the waste generated during the production process)				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Expected recyclable content (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: The mass ratio of the product that is recyclable				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Efficiency of recycling (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: The mass ratio of the output of recovery process over the input				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Marine litter (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The ratio of plastic packaging waste leaking into oceans per generated plastic packaging waste</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Water consumption (m ³ /kg)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Water consumed per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Fossil depletion (MJ/unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Contribution to the decrease of the quantity of fossil fuels in the environment per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Energy consumption (MJ/unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Energy consumed per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases). It covers all renewable and non-renewable energy sources.</i>				

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Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Greenhouse gas emissions (t CO ₂ -eq / unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Emitted greenhouse gases as CO2 equivalent per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases).</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Multiple VCs	Survey provided by	KARTAL MUN
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Environmental Indicator:	Use of virgin material (primary raw material use) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The percentage of the mass of virgin raw materials used over the mass of total raw materials</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Use of recycled material content (Secondary raw material use) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The percentage of the mass of recycled materials (secondary raw materials) used over the mass of total raw materials</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	Document:	D2.6 Summary of the state of play of the demo cases using the CEIS		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	final
	Reference:	D2.6	Date:	17/12/18

Environmental Indicator:	Amount of waste generation (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The amount of waste generated and sent to landfill or incineration per the amount of the product (i.e., the waste generated during the production process)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Expected recyclable content (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The mass ratio of the product that is recyclable</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Efficiency of recycling (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The mass ratio of the output of recovery process over the input</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Marine litter (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The ratio of plastic packaging waste leaking into oceans per generated plastic packaging waste</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	Document:	D2.6 Summary of the state of play of the demo cases using the CEIS		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	final
	Reference:	D2.6	Date:	17/12/18

Environmental Indicator:	Water consumption (m ³ /kg)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Water consumed per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Fossil depletion (MJ/unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Contribution to the decrease of the quantity of fossil fuels in the environment per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases)</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Energy consumption (MJ/unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Energy consumed per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases). It covers all renewable and non-renewable energy sources.</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental Indicator:	Greenhouse gas emissions (t CO ₂ -eq / unit product)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Emitted greenhouse gases as CO₂ equivalent per unit quantity of product over the life cycle (including raw material, production, consumption and disposal phases).</i>				
Significant environmental issue for your business (or for the sector)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Significant environmental issue for the society		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects consumer perspective on the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Provides competitive advantage		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Easily understandable for consumers		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	Document:	D2.6 Summary of the state of play of the demo cases using the CEIS		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	final
	Reference:	D2.6	Date:	17/12/18

ANNEX D: SURVEY RESULTS FOR ECONOMIC INDICATORS

Multiple VCs Survey provided by BUMAGA

Economic Indicator:	CAPEX (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: Capital Expenses including investments of new equipment, upgrading of equipment and refurbishment of equipment				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Economic Indicator:	OPEX (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: Operational expenses including purchasing, disposal energy, maintenance costs and revenues				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Economic Indicator:	Externalities (Environmental Cost) (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: Costs or benefits associated with environmental impacts of a process or product				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Economic Indicator:	Life cycle cost (LCC) (Whole life cycle cost using NPV) (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: The net present value (NPV) of all the cash flows incurred during the life cycle of each product (costs associated with construction, operation, maintenance and end-of-life + externalities + revenues and other costs)				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	Document:	D2.6 Summary of the state of play of the demo cases using the CEIS		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	final
	Reference:	D2.6	Date:	17/12/18

Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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Economic Indicator:	Net present value (NPV) of investments (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Sum of the discounted future cash flow along the exploitation period including initial investment cost</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Economic Indicator:	Internal rate of return on investments (IRR) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The annual return rate of an investment, expressed as a percentage of the initial investment</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Economic Indicator:	Return of investment (payback) – ROI (years)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The time in years that is needed to return the initial investment cost</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Economic Indicator:	Net added value (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The difference between the revenues and the costs of goods and services, purchases plus the depreciation of tangible assets</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Multiple VCs Survey provided by ECOEMBES

Economic Indicator:	CAPEX (€)	Low	Medium	High
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	Document:	D2.6 Summary of the state of play of the demo cases using the CEIS		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	final
	Reference:	D2.6	Date:	17/12/18

Description: <i>Capital Expenses including investments of new equipment, upgrading of equipment and refurbishment of equipment</i>			
Significant for taking an investment decision	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Economic Indicator:	OPEX (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Operational expenses including purchasing, disposal energy, maintenance costs and revenues</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Important for setting the price of the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Economic Indicator:	Externalities (Environmental Cost) (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Costs or benefits associated with environmental impacts of a process or product</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Important for setting the price of the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Suitable for benchmarking	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Economic Indicator:	Life cycle cost (LCC) (Whole life cycle cost using NPV) (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The net present value (NPV) of all the cash flows incurred during the life cycle of each product (costs associated with construction, operation, maintenance and end-of-life + externalities + revenues and other costs)</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Important for setting the price of the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Suitable for benchmarking	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Economic Indicator:	Net present value (NPV) of investments (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Sum of the discounted future cash flow along the exploitation period including initial investment cost</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Important for setting the price of the product	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Suitable for benchmarking	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

	Document:	D2.6 Summary of the state of play of the demo cases using the CEIS		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	final
	Reference:	D2.6	Date:	17/12/18

Economic Indicator:	Internal rate of return on investments (IRR) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The annual return rate of an investment, expressed as a percentage of the initial investment</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Economic Indicator:	Return of investment (payback) – ROI (years)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The time in years that is needed to return the initial investment cost</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Economic Indicator:	Net added value (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The difference between the revenues and the costs of goods and services, purchases plus the depreciation of tangible assets</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Multiple VCs Survey provided by **KARTAL MUN**

Economic Indicator:	CAPEX (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Capital Expenses including investments of new equipment, upgrading of equipment and refurbishment of equipment</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Economic Indicator:	OPEX (€)	Low	Medium	High
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	Document:	D2.6 Summary of the state of play of the demo cases using the CEIS		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	final
	Reference:	D2.6	Date:	17/12/18

Description: <i>Operational expenses including purchasing, disposal energy, maintenance costs and revenues</i>			
Significant for taking an investment decision	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Economic Indicator:	Externalities (Environmental Cost) (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Costs or benefits associated with environmental impacts of a process or product</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Important for setting the price of the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Economic Indicator:	Life cycle cost (LCC) (Whole life cycle cost using NPV) (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The net present value (NPV) of all the cash flows incurred during the life cycle of each product (costs associated with construction, operation, maintenance and end-of-life + externalities + revenues and other costs)</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Important for setting the price of the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Economic Indicator:	Net present value (NPV) of investments (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Sum of the discounted future cash flow along the exploitation period including initial investment cost</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Important for setting the price of the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Economic Indicator:	Internal rate of return on investments (IRR) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The annual return rate of an investment, expressed as a percentage of the initial investment</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Important for setting the price of the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

	Document:	D2.6 Summary of the state of play of the demo cases using the CEIS		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	final
	Reference:	D2.6	Date:	17/12/18

Economic Indicator:	Return of investment (payback) – ROI (years)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The time in years that is needed to return the initial investment cost</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Economic Indicator:	Net added value (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The difference between the revenues and the costs of goods and services, purchases plus the depreciation of tangible assets</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Multiple VCs	Survey provided by	SAPONIA
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Economic Indicator:	CAPEX (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Capital Expenses including investments of new equipment, upgrading of equipment and refurbishment of equipment</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Economic Indicator:	OPEX (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Operational expenses including purchasing, disposal energy, maintenance costs and revenues</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	Document:	D2.6 Summary of the state of play of the demo cases using the CEIS		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	final
	Reference:	D2.6	Date:	17/12/18

Economic Indicator:	Externalities (Environmental Cost) (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Costs or benefits associated with environmental impacts of a process or product</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Economic Indicator:	Life cycle cost (LCC) (Whole life cycle cost using NPV) (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The net present value (NPV) of all the cash flows incurred during the life cycle of each product (costs associated with construction, operation, maintenance and end-of-life + externalities + revenues and other costs)</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Economic Indicator:	Net present value (NPV) of investments (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>Sum of the discounted future cash flow along the exploitation period including initial investment cost</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Economic Indicator:	Internal rate of return on investments (IRR) (%)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The annual return rate of an investment, expressed as a percentage of the initial investment</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Economic Indicator:	Return of investment (payback) – ROI (years)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The time in years that is needed to return the initial investment cost</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	Document:	D2.6 Summary of the state of play of the demo cases using the CEIS		
	Author:	CIRCE	Version	final
	Reference:	D2.6	Date:	17/12/18

Suitable for benchmarking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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Economic Indicator:	Net added value (€)	Low	Medium	High
Description: <i>The difference between the revenues and the costs of goods and services, purchases plus the depreciation of tangible assets</i>				
Significant for taking an investment decision		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Important for setting the price of the product		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Useful to indicate benefits as well as costs		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suitable for benchmarking		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>